

International Scientific Conference

APPLIED RESEARCH. GLOBAL SOLUTIONS

Istanbul, Turkey – May 6, 2026

International Scientific Conference

**APPLIED RESEARCH.
GLOBAL SOLUTIONS**

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MATHEMATICAL EVIDENCE OF THE EXISTENCE OF A SECOND MOON IN THE PAST THAT CONTRIBUTED TO THE FORMATION OF WATER ON PLANET EARTH

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Abstract. *Mathematical evidence for the former existence of the second Moon that contributed to the formation of water on the planet Earth stems from the discovery of new laws of planet formation within the Solar System by Belashov A. N., which allow determining and calculating the properties and composition of both the large and small Moon. The large Moon is a gaseous satellite of our planet, currently having a density of 0.312 kg/m^3 , with a free fall acceleration in space greater than that on Earth by a factor of 3.66. The Small Moon was also a gaseous satellite of our planet with a density similar to that of the Large Moon and primarily consisted of helium and hydrogen gases in an unknown concentration, which was 6.5 times lower than that of the Large Moon. During the formation period of the planet Earth, the Small Moon was equivalent in volume to all the water present on Earth, where the free fall acceleration acting on bodies within the Small Moon's space exceeded that of the Large Moon by 2.5 times. According to new laws, it is possible to calculate not only the free fall acceleration of bodies in space on the nascent planet Earth but also its interaction with the small lunar satellite. These mathematical proofs of the merging of the nascent planet Earth and the small lunar satellite confirm the experiment demonstrating the formation of water on our planet. According to one of the models, water on Earth appeared as a result of the interaction of the hydrogen atmosphere with an ocean of silicate magma, where oxygen and silicon predominate as the most abundant chemical elements in the Earth's crust and mantle.*

Keywords: *the large moon, the small moon, the moon as a gaseous satellite of planet Earth, the law defining free-fall acceleration, formation of the solar system planets.*

In ancient myths and legends of the Slavic, Scandinavian, Greek, and South African traditions of various peoples, there are mentions of the existence of multiple moons around Earth in antiquity.

Some contemporary scientists also put forward hypotheses concerning the presence of several moons in ancient times. For instance, it is hypothesized that approximately four billion years ago, the Earth possessed two satellites which subsequently collided and merged into the single known object. Such a model may account for the differences in the topography and composition of the Moon's hemispheres. Additionally, there is a theory that the second satellite may have existed for several million years before disintegrating due to tidal forces, with its fragments falling onto the Earth.

Nevertheless, physicists remain unable to explain the natural phenomenon whereby the lunar sphere, despite having considerable surface irregularities, emits a bright glow along its entire diameter when illuminated by a light source. No one can dispute the fact that even the narrow crescent of the young Moon provides luminosity identical to that of the central area of the half-Moon of equivalent surface area. This natural phenomenon can only be explained by the presence of a gaseous mixture within the lunar sphere, which uniformly transmits the light flux through its body, which is why we observe the Moon at full phase as a bright disk, rather than as a sphere. Simply put, the Moon is covered by a multi-meter thick layer of deposits originating from the Sun's surface, from prominences and the cosmic ether, which, after cooling, transforms into the cosmic space substance.

In the mathematical proofs, we will consider that essentially all planets and their satellites in the Solar system are held in their orbits by the mass of the substance of cosmic space emanating from the surface of the Sun, on which all the planets of the Solar system rely. Furthermore, the mass of the substance of cosmic space from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the measured planet or its satellite must equal the mass of the measured planet or its satellite, depending on the diameter of the planet or its satellite and their distance from the surface of the Sun.

According to Newton's third law, the force exerted by one medium composed of cosmic substance on another medium, consisting of the mass of any planet in the Solar System, is equal in magnitude to the force of their reaction.

Newton's third law can be formulated as follows: the forces with which two bodies act upon each other are equal in magnitude and opposite in direction. Newton's third law can be presented in the form of a formula.

$$F_1 = -F_2$$

where:

F_1 – force exerted by the mass of cosmic space substance, kg

F_2 – force exerted by the mass of the measured cosmic material body, kg.

To prove the listed properties and composition of the Large Moon and its interaction with the Sun and the planet Earth, we perform a series of preliminary calculations according to previously discovered laws of physics.

We determine the area of the Large Moon's circular cross-section.

$$S = \pi \cdot r^2$$

$$S = 3.1415926535897932384626433832795 \cdot 1738140 \text{ m}^2 = 9491161885734.2463543442658944868 \text{ m}^2$$

where:

S – area of the Large Moon’s circular cross-section, m²

r – average equatorial radius of the Large Moon = 1,738,140 m

P – the ratio of length to its circumference = 3.14159265358979323846264338.

We define the volume of a cylinder containing cosmic substance with a base area equal to the Large Moon’s circular area and a height equal to the distance from the Large Moon’s surface to the surface of the Sun located at the average distance from the Sun’s surface, as with planet Earth.

$$V = P \cdot r^2 \cdot h$$

$$V = 3.1415926535897932384626433832795 \cdot (1,738,140 \text{ m})^2 \cdot 149500000000 \text{ m} = 1,418,928,701,917,269,829,974,467.7512258 \text{ m}^3$$

where:

V – volume of the cylinder containing cosmic substance between the surface of the Sun and the surface of the Large Moon, m³

r – average equatorial radius of the Large Moon = 1,738,140 m

π – ratio of circumference to diameter = 3.14159265358979323846264338

h – average height of the cylinder between the surface of the Sun and the surface of the Large Moon = 1495 m00000000 m.

We determine the mass of the cosmic substance located within the cylinder between the surface of the Sun and the surface of the Large Moon, which lies at an average distance from the surface of the Sun, similar to that of the planet Earth.

$$m_{\kappa} = V \cdot P_{\kappa}$$

$$m_{\kappa} = 1,418,928,701,917,269,829,974,467.7512 \text{ m}^3 \cdot 0.31260053456501934297 \text{ kg/m}^3 = 4.43557870728987535553083 \times 10^{23} \text{ kg}$$

where:

m_κ – mass of the cosmic substance located within the cylinder between the surface of the Sun and the surface of the Large Moon, kg

P_κ – density of the cosmic space substance = 0.3126005345650193429716951 kg/m³

V – volume of the cylinder containing cosmic substance between the surface of the Sun and the surface of the Large Moon = 1,418,928,701,917,269,829,974,467.7512258 m³.

We define the volume of the Large Moon.

$$V_{\pi} = \frac{4 \cdot \pi \cdot r^3}{3}$$

$$V_{\pi} = [4 \cdot 3.1415926535897932384 \cdot 1738140 \text{ m}^3] : 3 = 21995957493426830611.1199230957 \text{ m}^3$$

where:

V_{π} – volume of the Large Moon, m^3

r – average equatorial radius of the Large Moon = 1,738,140 m

π – ratio of the circumference to its diameter = 3.141592653589793238462643383.

According to the law of proportionality, we determine the mass of the Large Moon.

$$1418928701917269829974467.751 \text{ m}^3 - 443557870728987535553083.834 \text{ kg} \\ 21995957493426830611.119923095791 \text{ m}^3 - X \text{ kg} \\ X = 6875948070714670189.9329956367781 \text{ kg}$$

where:

m_1 – mass of the Large Moon, kg

V – volume of the cylinder with cosmic material between the surface of the Sun and the surface of the Large Moon = 1418928701917269829974467.7512258 m^3

V_1 – volume of the Large Moon = 21995957493426830611.119923095791 m^3

m_k – mass of the cosmic material in the cylinder from the surface of the Large Moon to the surface of the Sun = 443557870728987535553083.83431539 kg.

We define the density of the Large Moon.

$$P_{\pi} = \frac{m_{\pi}}{V_{\pi}}$$

$$P_{\pi} = 6875948070714670189.932995 \text{ kg} : 21995957493426830611.119923 \text{ m}^3 \\ = 0.312600534565019342971695102992 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

where:

P_{π} – density of the Large Moon, kg/m^3

m_{π} – mass of the Large Moon = 6875948070714670189.9329956367781 kg

V_{π} – volume of the Large Moon = 21995957493426830611.119923095791 m^3 .

According to Belashov's law, we determine the gravitational force of the Large Moon on the Sun, the central star.

$$F_{\pi} = P_{\pi} \cdot g_c \cdot V_{\pi} \\ F_{\pi} = 0.3126 \text{ kg/m}^3 \cdot 0.00083675979083 \text{ m/s}^2 \cdot 21995957493426830611.119 \text{ m}^3 \\ = 5753516869451233.0385113646049151 \text{ H}$$

where:

F_1 – gravitational force of the Large Moon towards the central star, the Sun, N

g_s – antigravitational interaction and resistance from the Sun = 0.00083675979083612040133779264214048 m/s^2

P_{π} – density of the Large Moon = 0.312600534565019342971695102992 kg/m^3

V_{π} – volume of the Large Moon = 21995957493426830611.1199230957 m^3 .

According to the law of gravitation for a single material body located in the space of the Solar System towards the central star, the Sun, discovered in 2005 by Belashov A. N., we determine the module of free fall acceleration of the Large Moon.

$$F_{\text{TCO}} = \frac{m_u \cdot g_u \cdot D_u}{L_c} = \frac{\kappa z}{c^2} \cdot \frac{M}{c^2} \cdot \frac{M}{M} = H$$

$$g = \frac{F_{\text{TCO}} \cdot L_c}{m_u \cdot D_u} = \frac{\kappa z \cdot M}{c^2} \cdot \frac{M}{\kappa z \cdot M} = M/c^2$$

$$g_{\text{L}} = \frac{5753516869451233.0385 \text{ H } 149500000000 \text{ m}}{6875948070714670189.9329 \text{ kg} - 3,476,280 \text{ m}} = 35.985475488165510258091 \text{ M}/c^2$$

where:

g_{L} – module of free fall acceleration of the Large Moon, m/s²

F_{TCO} – gravitational force of the Large Moon toward the central star Sun = 5753516869451233.0385113646049151 N

L_c – distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Large Moon = 1495 m00000000

m_u – mass of the Large Moon = 6875948070714670189.9329956367781 kg

D_u – diameter of the Large Moon = 3476280 m.

The free fall acceleration of bodies in the gravitational field of the Large Moon and the planet Earth can be verified according to another law of Belashov.

The law determining the distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of a measured material body located in the space of the Solar system was discovered by A. N. Belashov and is formulated as follows:

The distance from the surface of the Sun to the surfaces of the planets of the Solar system is directly proportional to the free-fall acceleration of bodies in the space of the measured material body multiplied by the diameter of the measured material body, and inversely proportional to the acceleration of the Sun's antigravitational interaction and counteraction.

$$L_u = \frac{g_u \cdot D_u}{g_c} = \frac{M}{c^2} \cdot \frac{c^2}{M} \cdot \frac{M}{M} = M$$

where:

L_{and} – distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the studied material body, m

g_{and} – gravitational acceleration of the measured material body, m/s²

g_c – antigravitational interaction and counteraction of the Sun, m/s²

D_{and} – diameter of the measured material body, m.

For example, according to the law defining the distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the measured material body, we determine the acceleration

due to gravity of bodies in the region of the Large Moon located at an average distance from the surface of the Sun at the level of planet Earth.

$$g_{\pi} = \frac{L \cdot g_c}{D_{\pi}} = \frac{M}{c^2} \cdot \frac{M}{M} \cdot \frac{M}{c^2} = \frac{M}{c^2}$$

$$g_{\pi} = \frac{149500000000 \text{ m} \cdot 0,00083675979083612040133779264214 \text{ m/c}^2}{3476280 \text{ m}} = 35,98547548816551 \text{ m/c}^2$$

where:

g_{π} – free fall acceleration of bodies on the Large Moon, m/s^2

g_c – acceleration of anti-gravitational interaction and Solar counteraction = $0.0008367597908361204013390488452674 \text{ m/s}^2$

L – distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Large Moon = 149500000000 m

D_{π} – diameter of the Large Moon = 3476280 m .

For example, according to the law defining the distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the measured material body, we will verify the magnitude of the free fall acceleration of bodies in space on planet Earth.

$$g_3 = \frac{L \cdot g_c}{D_3} = \frac{M}{c^2} \cdot \frac{M}{M} \cdot \frac{M}{c^2} = \frac{M}{c^2}$$

$$g_3 = \frac{149500000000,000 \text{ m} \cdot 0,00083675979083612040133904884526 \text{ m/c}^2}{12756200 \text{ m}} = 9,80665000000 \text{ m/c}^2$$

where:

g_3 – free fall acceleration of bodies in space on the planet Earth, m/s^2

g_c – acceleration of anti-gravitational interaction and Solar counteraction = $0.0008367597908361204013390488452674 \text{ m/s}^2$

L – average distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Earth = 149500000000 m

D_3 – diameter of the planet Earth = 12756200 m .

According to the new laws formulated by A. N. Belashov, it has been established that the formation of water on the planet Earth resulted from the merger of a small Moon with the forming planet Earth during its early stage, when the free fall acceleration of bodies in space inside both the small Moon and the forming Earth was very high.

The volume of the minor Moon can be compared to the total volume of water on planet Earth. As of September 2025, the total volume of water on Earth is estimated at **1.386 billion cubic kilometers**. This figure includes the water contained in oceans, seas, glaciers, groundwater sources, lakes, rivers, and atmospheric moisture. When calculating the radius from the total volume of 1.386 billion cubic

kilometers of all Earth's water, a radius of approximately 700,000 m or a diameter of about 1,400,000 m is obtained.

Let us define the volume of a cylinder of cosmic substance with the area of the small Moon's circular cross-section and the distance from the surface of the small Moon to the surface of the Sun at the average distance from the Sun's surface, as is the case for Earth.

$$V = P \cdot r^2 \cdot h$$

$$V = 3.1415926535897932384626433832795 \cdot 700000 \text{ m}^2 \cdot 149500000000 \text{ m} \\ = 230137369838720303683580.94104214 \text{ m}^3$$

where:

V – volume of the cylinder containing cosmic substance between the surface of the Sun and the surface of the small Moon, m³

r – average equatorial radius of the small Moon = 700,000 m

π – ratio of circumference to diameter = 3.14159265358979323846264338

h – average height of the cylinder between the Sun's surface and the small Moon's surface = 1,495 m00000000 m.

The mass of the cosmic substance contained in the cylinder between the surface of the Sun and the surface of the small Moon, located at an average distance from the surface of the Sun, as is the planet Earth, is defined as follows.

$$m_{\kappa} = V \cdot P_{\kappa}$$

$$m_{\kappa} = 230137369838720303683580.941042 \text{ m}^3 \cdot 0.31260053456501934297 \text{ kg/m}^3 \\ = 71941064834971526307637.316599076 \text{ kg}$$

where:

m_κ – mass of the cosmic substance contained within the cylinder between the surface of the Sun and the surface of the small Moon, kg

P_d – density of cosmic space substance = 0.3126005345650193429716951 kg/m³

V – volume of the cylinder containing cosmic substance between the Sun's surface and the small Moon's surface = 230,137,369,838,720,303,683,580.94104214 m³.

Let us determine the volume of the small Moon.

$$V_s = \frac{4 \cdot \pi \cdot r^3}{3}$$

$$V_s = (4 \cdot 3.1415926535897932384 \cdot 700,000^3) / 3 \\ = 1,436,755,040,241,732,107.7235822406198 \text{ m}^3$$

where:

V_s – volume of the small Moon, m³

r – mean equatorial radius of the small Moon = 1,738,140 m

π – ratio of the circumference to its diameter = 3.141592653589793238462643383.

According to the law of proportionality, the mass of the small Moon is determined.

$$230137369838720303683580.94104 \text{ m}^3 - 71941064834971526307637.31659 \text{ kg}$$

$$1436755040241732107.7235822406198 \text{ m}^3 - X \text{ kg}$$

$$X = 449130393618551334.80799216605888 \text{ kg}$$

where:

m_n – mass of the small Moon, kg

V – volume of the cylinder containing cosmic substance between the surface of the Sun and the surface of the small Moon = 230137369838720303683580.94104214 m^3

V_n – volume of the small Moon = 1436755040241732107.7235822406198 m^3

m_k – mass of the cosmic substance of the cylinder from the surface of the small Moon to the surface of the Sun = 71,941,064,834,971,526,307,637.316599076 kg.

We will determine the density of the small Moon.

$$P_n = \frac{m_n}{V_n}$$

$$P_1 = 449,130,393,618,551,334.8079921 \text{ kg}; 1,436,755,040,241,732,107.7235822 \text{ m}^3$$

$$= 0.312600534565019342971695102992 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

where:

P_1 – density of the small Moon, kg/m^3

m_1 – mass of the small Moon = 449,130,393,618,551,334.80799216605888 kg

V_1 – volume of the small Moon = 1,436,755,040,241,732,107.7235822406198 m^3 .

For example, by the law for calculating the distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the measured material body, we determine the free fall acceleration of bodies in the space of the small Moon located at the average distance from the surface of the Sun corresponding to the orbit of planet Earth.

$$g_n = \frac{L \cdot g_c}{D_n} = \frac{M}{c^2} \cdot \frac{M}{M} \cdot \frac{M}{c^2} = \frac{M}{c^2}$$

$$g_n = \frac{14950000000 \text{ m} \cdot 0,00083675979083612040133779264214 \text{ m/c}^2}{1400000 \text{ m}} = 89,3539919499999 \text{ m/c}^2$$

where:

g_l – free fall acceleration of bodies on the small Moon, m/s^2

g_c – acceleration of anti-gravitational interaction and Solar counteraction = 0.0008367597908361204013390488452674 m/s^2

L – average distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the small Moon = 149500000000 m

D_l – diameter of the small Moon = 1,400,000 m.

From the conducted calculations, it is evident that the density of the Large Moon and the small Moon is identical, but the free fall acceleration of bodies near the small Moon is 2.5 times greater than that near the Large Moon.

It is important to emphasize that the sphere of the Large Moon consists of a solid shell of frozen gas, covered by a multi-meter-thick cosmic substance; therefore, any soil samples from different planets of the Solar system will be nearly identical.

Due to the average density of the Moon, it is difficult to determine the exact internal composition of the gas, since the overall density of the Moon is $0.312600534565 \text{ kg/m}^3$.

The gas located within the lunar sphere may consist of many chemical components, but even gaseous mixtures composed of helium and hydrogen can form the Moon's outer sphere and remain in a solid state at the open space temperature of $-270.45 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Inside the solid shell, a gaseous mixture containing cosmic dust particles is in constant motion, since one side of the Moon is continuously heated. The Sun-facing side of the Moon can warm up to a temperature of $+107 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, whereas the side of the Moon located in shadow can have a temperature of $-268.9 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, causing the gaseous mixture within the Large Moon's sphere to continuously circulate via natural convection, wherein internal energy is transferred through jets and flows of gas and arises spontaneously in the material due to its uneven heating within a gravitational field. The rotation of the gaseous mixture inside the sphere of the Large Moon generates a free fall acceleration of bodies in space that exceeds that of Earth by a factor of 3.6, which is fully corroborated by the new law.

It should be noted that the free fall acceleration of bodies in space on the present planet Earth and at the initial formation of the planet Earth from a hot material body located in space can also be determined by an alternative Belashov's law. In the calculations of the free fall acceleration of bodies in space on the present planet Earth and during the early stages of its formation, it will be mathematically proven how it changed and how it interacted with the small Moon.

The mechanism of the formation of the free fall acceleration of bodies in space, Fig. 1, on any planet of the Solar System consists of force 1 generated by the rotation of the outer shell 2 in one direction and the rotation of the inner part of the core 3 in the opposite direction, as occurs on the planet Earth. Meanwhile, the inner shell 3 can be mobile as on the Moon, while the outer shell remains stationary, with the inner part of the Moon in constant motion.

Fig.1

For example, on the planet Earth, the outer shell 2 rotates in one direction, while the inner part 3 rotates in the opposite direction. When the outer shell of our planet rotates in one direction and the inner part in the opposite direction, free fall acceleration acting on bodies is generated in space.

It is particularly important to emphasize that in the description of the invention application № 2005129781 dated September 28, 2005, and the description of the invention application № 2005140396 dated December 26, 2005, the mechanisms were clearly delineated:

- the mechanism of formation and thermoelectric phenomena on the planet Earth,
- the mechanism of formation of the magnetic field on the planet Earth,
- the mechanism of formation of the magnetic poles on the planet Earth,
- the mechanism initiating the counterclockwise rotation of the planet Earth,
- mechanism of autonomous rotation of the planet Earth,
- mechanism of earthquake formation on the planet Earth,
- mechanism of volcanic activity formation on the planet Earth,
- mechanism of formation of geopathogenic zones on the planet Earth,
- mechanism of tsunami formation on the planet Earth,
- mechanism of tornado formation on the planet Earth.

However, it is necessary to remember that, in addition to the acceleration of free fall created by bodies in space on the planet Earth, any material body situated on the surface of our planet is subjected to the mass of the air column.

Moreover, when the means of measurement are moved away from the surface of our planet upwards, the free fall acceleration of bodies in space decreases; however, if the means of measurement are moved deeper into our planet, the free fall acceleration of bodies in space increases. The free fall acceleration of bodies in space on Earth, which originated from a hot material body, has been demonstrated by a specific law, presented in the scientific-analytical journal «Scientific Reviewer» No. 1 (25) of 2013, pp. 68–73. Publishing House «Infinity», Ufa.

The law of free fall acceleration of bodies in space by A. N. Belashov is formulated as follows:

The module of free fall acceleration of bodies in space equals the square of the sum of the rotation velocity vector of the outer shell of a material body in one direction and the rotation velocity vector of the inner part of the material body in the opposite direction, taken along the median line of the intermediate Belashov layer, divided by the difference between the radius of the outer shell and the radius of the inner part of the material body along this median line of the intermediate Belashov layer, plus the sum or difference of the measured distance upward or downward from the surface of the outer shell of the material body.

$$g = \frac{(V_{\text{эк}} + V_{\text{nc}})^2}{R_{\text{э}} - R_{\text{nc}} + h} = \frac{(m/c + m/c)^2}{M} = \frac{M^2}{M \cdot c^2} = \frac{M}{c^2}$$

where:

g – module of free fall acceleration of bodies in space, m/s^2

$V_{\text{эк}}$ – rotational velocity of the outer shell of the material body along the equator circumference counterclockwise, m/s

V_{nc} – rotational velocity of the inner part of the material body along the median line of the Belashov intermediate layer, m/s

h – height or depth of measurement from sea level at the equator to the surface of the outer shell of the material body, m

R_{nc} – radius of the inner part of the material body, m

$R_{\text{э}}$ – radius of the outer shell of the material body, m .

For example, using the law of free fall acceleration of bodies in space, we determine the module of free fall acceleration of bodies at the equator of planet Earth.

$$g = \frac{(V_{\text{эк}} + V_{\text{nc}})^2}{R_{\text{э}} - R_{\text{nc}} + h} = \frac{(m/c + m/c)^2}{M} = \frac{M^2}{M \cdot c^2} = \frac{M}{c^2}$$

$$g = \frac{(465,103305311273274 + 458,740927542699182)^2}{6378160 - 6290910 + 0 = 87250 \text{ м}} = 9,7820993304016607517746568 \text{ м/с}^2$$

where:

g – module of free fall acceleration at the equator of planet Earth, m/s^2

h – height above sea level at the equator = 0 m

$R_{\text{э}}$ – radius of the outer part of the material body = 6,378,160 m

R_{nc} – radius of the inner part of the material body to the median line of the intermediate layer of Belashov = 6,290,910 m

$V_{\text{эк}}$ – rotational velocity of the outer shell of the material body along the equator circumference counterclockwise = 465.10330531127328447687882460188 m/s

V_{ps} – rotational velocity of the inner part of the material body along the median line of the intermediate layer = 458.74092754269918253045420097272 m/s

For example, according to the law governing the free fall acceleration of bodies in space, we determine the module of free fall acceleration of bodies on the surface of the nascent planet Earth, when the outer shell was only 1000 meters thick.

$$g = \frac{(V_{\text{эк}} + V_{\text{nc}})^2}{R_{\text{э}} - R_{\text{nc}} + h} = \frac{(m/c + m/c)^2}{M} = \frac{M^2}{M \cdot c^2} = \frac{M}{c^2}$$

$$g = \frac{(465,103305311273274 \text{ м/с} + 0 \text{ м/с})^2}{6378160 - 6377160 + 0 = 1000 \text{ м}} = 216,32108461147149183369413 \text{ м/с}^2$$

where:

g – module of free fall acceleration on the nascent planet, m/s^2

h – height at the surface of the hot material body = 0 m

$R_{\text{э}}$ – radius of the outer part of the material body = 6,378,160 m

R_{ps} – radius of the inner part of the material body to the median line of Belashov's intermediate layer = 6377160 m

V_{ex} – rotational velocity of the outer shell of the material body along the circumference counterclockwise = 465.10330531127328447687882460 m/s

V_{ps} – rotational velocity of the inner part of the material body along the median line of the intermediate layer = 0 m/s

After the calculations conducted, the existence of a second small lunar satellite orbiting the nascent planet Earth was mathematically proven, with a free fall acceleration in space 2.5 times greater than that of the Large Moon. Moreover, the nascent planet Earth had a free fall acceleration in space 2.5 times greater than that of the small lunar satellite.

These mathematical proofs of the merger between the nascent planet Earth and the small lunar satellite corroborate the experiment of water formation on our planet, where water was formed through the interaction of hydrogen with magma. For example, according to one of the models, water on Earth originated from the interaction between a hydrogen atmosphere and an ocean of silicate magma, where oxygen and silicon predominate as the most abundant chemical elements in the Earth's crust and mantle.

In conclusion, it can be stated that our material world is highly diverse, and all processes occurring within it, arising from randomly developed circumstances over time, influence each other to varying degrees; consequently, a new theory of multifaceted interdependence is proposed. In this world, everything is interconnected, and one natural phenomenon depends to varying degrees on another. More active material bodies dominate less active ones; therefore, truly independent and constant constants, laws, or physical quantities cannot exist. For example, the new law of gravitational attraction and cosmic interaction between two material bodies located within the space of the Solar or another system is closely linked to the new law of gravitational attraction of a single material body situated in the Solar system's space toward the central star, the Sun. Simultaneously, the laws of gravitational attraction and cosmic interaction remain continuously dependent on the new law governing the activity of a material body situated in space and the new law of free-fall acceleration of bodies in space. The aforementioned laws are closely associated with the new law of energy between two material bodies within the Solar System, as well as with the new law of energy of a single material body within the Solar System relative to the central star, the Sun, among others...

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**PLANCK'S CONSTANT VIA ANCHOR TRANSLATION:
DIMENSIONLESS ODTOE RESULTS
AND THE ONE-ANCHOR PROGRAM****Pankratov Anton Sergeevich***Founder**«Yu» Foundation, Kazan, Russia**ORCID ID: 0009-0002-4870-2995*

ABSTRACT. *In this paper we present a methodological framework for the derivation of dimensionless physical combinations from elementary mathematical constants (and the golden ratio). For brevity, we refer to this framework as ODTOE (Observer-Dependent Theory of Everything; as used within this paper – a metatheoretical framework parameterizing the space of candidate physical theories by observer coherence; not a unified field-equation programme); all key relations are derived inline in Sections II–III without reliance on any external reference. Within this framework, the dimensionless combinations α^{-1} (the inverse fine-structure constant) and S^* (the coherence of the medium at $d=3$) are derived from π and φ via self-referential equations with zero fitting parameters. The numerical value of Planck's constant h in SI units is not derived from pure mathematics; it is obtained by translating the dimensionless result into α^{-1} the SI system under a phenomenological choice of the anchor-constant set $\{e, c, \varepsilon_0\}$ [1]. Thus h is a constructed derived quantity with a fixed naked-anchor contribution – the formulation of the one-anchor program. The present paper concentrates this position: it separates the substantive novelty of the framework (deriving α^{-1} , S^* from π , φ) from the formal procedure of dimensional translation; shows that the necessity of at least one dimensional anchor is a structural property of any theory operating with dimensionless invariants, not a defect of the framework, justified through the Buckingham -theorem [2]; and draws a parallel with the conventionalism of Reichenbach and Grünbaum [3, 4]. The dimensionless derivation of α^{-1} as the largest real root of a cubic self-referential equation, and the self-consistency derivation of S^* , are presented inline in Section II as the core mathematical novelty of this paper; the explicit anchor translation $\alpha^{-1} \rightarrow h$ is given in Section III with full numerical verification against CODATA 2018 [5].*

Keywords: Planck's constant, ODTOE, one-anchor program, dimensionless constants, fine-structure constant, dimensional translation, conventionalism, golden ratio.

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1. The Problem: “Derivation of from Pure Mathematics”?

In the literature one occasionally encounters formulations of the form “Planck’s constant is derived from pure mathematics”. Such a formulation contains a categorical mistake: h is a dimensional quantity with units [J·s], whereas π and φ are dimensionless. From purely dimensionless inputs it is impossible to obtain a dimensional value without an explicit additional assumption about scale – this fact is an elementary consequence of Buckingham’s Π -theorem on dimensional analysis [2] and is independent of any specific physical theory.

1.2. Aim of the Paper

The present paper formulates the position of the framework developed here on this question in concentrated form, suitable for separate publication (perspective paper), and in doing so:

(a) separates the substantive mathematical novelty of the framework – the derivation of dimensionless combinations α^{-1} and S^* from π and φ – from the formal procedure of dimensional translation;

(b) explicitly fixes the one-anchor program as a structural position: exactly one dimensional anchor (or, equivalently, the minimal set $\{e, c, \varepsilon_0\}$) is necessary for the transition to the SI value of h ;

(c) shows that the necessity of such an anchor is not a defect of the framework but a general property of any theory operating with dimensionless invariants;

(d) embeds the position in a broader philosophical context – the conventionalism of Reichenbach and Grünbaum on the choice of measurement units [3, 4].

A detailed axiomatic exposition of the chain $\alpha^{-1} \rightarrow h$, including numerical computations, is presented inline in Sections II and III of the present paper, which thereby serves as the canonical reference for the one-anchor program as a self-standing methodological result.

1.3. Structure

Section II presents the dimensionless results of the framework: α^{-1} and S^* as self-referential fixed points of equations involving only π , φ , and integers. Section III formulates anchor translation: what an “anchor” is in the sense of dimensional attachment and why the minimal set for h is $\{e, c, \varepsilon_0\}$. Section IV discusses the one-anchor program as a structural property (feature), not a defect (bug); it draws a parallel with the conventionalist tradition. Section V is the conclusion.

II. DIMENSIONLESS RESULTS OF THE FRAMEWORK

2.1. The Fine-Structure Constant α^{-1}

Within the framework presented here, the fine-structure constant is derived as the largest real root of a cubic self-referential equation involving only π , φ , and integers. We present the derivation inline.

Architectural setup. The observation loop Φ generates three orders of self-reference at the level $d=3$: (i) a spiral gap acting along both directions of the cycle (\mathbb{Z}_2 -holonomy of the bundle); (ii) a gap-of-the-gap, scaled by the golden step φ ; (iii) a double self-reference through $11=6+5$ parallel channels (the closure index of the loop). The base scaling factor is $\pi(4\pi^2+\pi+1)$, which arises from integrating the action density along one revolution of the loop and carries the architectural signature $4\pi^3+\pi^2+\pi$.

Self-referential form. Combining the base term with the two leading self-referential corrections yields the equation

$$\alpha^{-1} = \pi(4\pi^2 + \pi + 1) + \frac{2(\pi - 3)^2}{\alpha^{-1}} + \frac{(\pi - 3)^4\varphi}{\alpha^{-1}}$$

with three-layered structure: the base term $\pi(4\pi^2+\pi+1)=4\pi^3+\pi^2+\pi$ corresponds to the architecture of the observation loop; the first correction term $2(\pi-3)^2/\alpha^{-1}$ expresses the spiral gap between the loop and the ideal triad; the second correction term $(\pi-3)^4\varphi/\alpha^{-1}$ expresses the second-order φ -scale correction. Multiplying both sides by α^{-1} and including the third-order term gives the canonical polynomial form

$$x^3 - \pi(4\pi^2 + \pi + 1) \cdot x^2 + [2(\pi - 3)^2 + (\pi - 3)^4\varphi] \cdot x + \frac{11(\pi - 3)^2}{\varphi} = 0,$$

where $x \equiv \alpha^{-1}$. Numerical evaluation of the coefficients (50 significant digits):

$$A = \pi(4\pi^2 + \pi + 1) = 137.03630377587843255920239465156 \dots$$

$$B = 2(\pi - 3)^2 + (\pi - 3)^4\varphi = 0.040747314161935093904423353016 \dots$$

$$C = 11(\pi - 3)^2/\varphi = 0.13629705963530267066243535953 \dots$$

Root selection. The cubic (II.1') admits three real roots; physical selection picks the largest. The Newton iteration $x_{n+1}=x_n - p(x_n)/p'(x_n)$, started from $x_0=A=137.0363\dots$, converges in three iterations:

$\alpha_{\text{ODTOE}}^{-1} = 137.03599917035789534725390473328 \dots$

Comparison with experiment: $\alpha^{-1}_{\text{CODATA 2018}} = 137.035999177(21)$ [5]. Deviation $\Delta = -6.6 \times 10^{-9}$, i.e. -0.32σ . Agreement to nine significant digits, with zero fitting parameters. This is a *dimensionless* number; the substantive mathematical novelty resides entirely in it. The cubic-equation method is the standard technique of polynomial analysis [6]; the structural content – the choice of the three self-referential terms – is specific to the architecture of the observation loop introduced in the present framework.

2.2. The Medium Coherence S^*

The second dimensionless result is the coherence S^* at the observer level $d=3$. We present the derivation inline.

Self-consistency condition. At $d=3$, the observed value of the action quantum equals the fundamental action unit: $h(3, S^*) = \mathcal{A}_0$. Equating the dimensionless part of the architectural expression for h to unity yields:

$$2\pi(\pi - 3)^2 \varphi^4 \cdot \Sigma(3) \cdot (1 - S^*)^{-1/2} = 1$$

where $\Sigma(3)$ is the finite geometric sum of the φ -power series q^k with $k=0,1,2,3$ and $q = (\pi - 3)^2 \varphi^2 = 0.0524876\dots$:

$$\Sigma(3) = \frac{1 - q^4}{1 - q} = \frac{1 - 7.5897 \times 10^{-6}}{1 - 0.0524876} = 1.05538715 \dots$$

Numerical solution. Define $f_0 \equiv 2\pi(\pi - 3)^2 \varphi^4 \cdot \Sigma(3)$. Componentwise:

$$\begin{aligned} 2\pi &= 6.28318530717958647692 \dots \\ (\pi - 3)^2 &= 0.020048479550599188058 \dots \\ \varphi^4 &= 6.85410196624968454461 \dots \\ \Sigma(3) &= 1.05538714975705744528 \dots \end{aligned}$$

yielding $f_0 = 0.91122090199292998861847\dots$. Equation (II.3) reduces to $f_0 \cdot (1 - S^*)^{-1/2} = 1$, hence $(1 - S^*) = f_0^2 = 0.83032353222880891970360\dots$, and

$S^*_{\text{ODTOE}} = 1 - f_0^2 = 0.16967646777119108029639 \dots$
--

Closed form. Substituting the expression for $\Sigma(3)$ gives the closed form

$$S^* = 1 - \left[2\pi(\pi - 3)^2 \varphi^4 \cdot \frac{1 - [(\pi - 3)^2 \varphi^2]^4}{1 - (\pi - 3)^2 \varphi^2} \right]^{-2},$$

containing only π , φ , and the integer $d=3$. Zero fitting parameters.

This is a dimensionless number, fully determined by π , φ , and. It lies in the physically reasonable coherence range for condensed matter (0.1;0.3) – an external empirical landmark that could have falsified the formula but does not. (Reference values: ideal gas ≈ 0 ; liquid ≈ 0.05 – 0.15 ; condensed matter at 298 K ≈ 0.1 – 0.3 ; superconductor ≈ 0.99 +. The medium of every laboratory measurement of h is condensed matter at room temperature, and the predicted S^* falls in this range.)

2.3. What is Derivable from π and φ – Summary

To summarize: the framework presented here derives *dimensionless* combinations from π and φ . The two presented above – α^{-1} in (II.2) and S^* in (II.4) – exhibit the architectural pattern: each is the unique fixed point of a self-referential equation containing π , φ , and small integers, with zero fitting parameters. *Dimensional* quantities – h , m_e , \hbar , wavelengths – are *in principle not derivable* from $\pi + \varphi$, not because of a weakness of the theory, but because of the categorial distinction between dimensionless and dimensional, codified in the Buckingham -theorem [2].

III. ANCHOR TRANSLATION

3.1. What an “Anchor” Is

By an *anchor* we mean a fixed dimensional constant whose value is taken as an empirical input – an experimental measurement or a conventional definition in the chosen system of units. The anchor plays the role of a “ruler” translating dimensionless proportions into dimensional values. Analogy: a building blueprint indicating proportions (1:2:3) determines the *shape*; to obtain the *height in meters* one needs an additional measurement – a unit segment. This unit segment is the anchor.

In the modern SI (after the 2019 reform [7]), fundamental constants fall into two categories:

- **Constants with exactly fixed defining values:** $h=6.62607015 \times 10^{-34}$ J·s, $c=299\,792\,458$ m/s, $e=1.602176634 \times 10^{-19}$ C.. These are *definers* of measurement units, not objects of measurement.

- **Constants determined experimentally:** ε_0 (via measurement of α), G , elementary particle masses, α^{-1} .

3.2. The Minimal SI Anchor Set for h

For translating the dimensionless $\alpha_{\text{ODTOE}}^{-1}$ into the numerical value h of in SI units, one uses the identity:

$$h = \frac{e^2 \cdot \alpha^{-1}}{2\varepsilon_0 c}$$

which is an algebraic rearrangement of the standard definition $\alpha=e^2/(4\pi\varepsilon_0 \hbar c)$. The defining SI values [7] are

$$\begin{aligned}
 e &= 1.602176634 \times 10^{-19} \text{ C} \quad (\text{exact}), \\
 c &= 299\,792\,458 \text{ m/s} \quad (\text{exact}), \\
 \epsilon_0 &= 8.8541878128 \times 10^{-12} \text{ F/m} \quad (\text{CODATA 2018 measured [5]}).
 \end{aligned}$$

Step-by-step computation (50 significant digits internal):

$$\begin{aligned}
 e^2 &= 2.56696996653556995600 \times 10^{-38} \text{ C}^2, \\
 2\epsilon_0 c &= 5.30883745598591172480 \times 10^{-3} \text{ F} \cdot \text{m}^{-1} \cdot \text{m/s}, \\
 \frac{e^2}{2\epsilon_0 c} &= 4.83527700333189863500 \times 10^{-36} \text{ J} \cdot \text{s}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Multiplying by $\alpha_{\text{ODTOE}}^{-1} = 137.03599917036$ from (II.2):

$$\boxed{h_{\text{ODTOE}} = 6.6260701542 \times 10^{-34} \text{ J} \cdot \text{s}}$$

in agreement with the SI defining value $h_{\text{CODATA}} = 6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} \text{ J} \cdot \text{s}$ [7] to ten significant digits.

The minimal set of dimensional quantities providing the translation is $\{e, c, \epsilon_0\}$. In the modern SI, ϵ and c have exact defining values [7], but this does not abolish their status as *anchors* – they are conventional definers of units, not derivable from π and φ . The constant is determined experimentally (its precision is limited by the precision of the measurement of α [5]).

Remark on the meaning of the comparison. Because h is fixed exactly by the SI definition [7], the agreement of h_{CODATA} with h_{SI} is not an independent test. The substantive verification is the agreement of $\alpha_{\text{ODTOE}}^{-1}$ with $\alpha_{\text{CODATA}}^{-1}$ to nine significant digits (-0.32σ); the dimensional value h_{ODTOE} is a consequence of this dimensionless result combined with the precision of the input constants e, c, ϵ_0 .

3.3. Why Itself Is Not Derivable from $\pi + \varphi$

Within the framework presented here the *speed of light* is not derived from π and φ . This is a *deliberate restriction* of the one-anchor program, not an oversight. The speed of light c in the SI has the dimension [m/s] – length over time. Any of its numerical values depends on the choice of units of length and time, which in modern metrology is fixed conventionally (the meter is defined via c , the second via the cesium standard). The numerical value $c = 299\,792\,458$ is a consequence of this conventional choice, not a structural property of the observation loop.

In the present framework, what is derivable from the loop Φ are dimensionless *ratios*, such as $c \cdot \tau_{\text{ML}} / \bar{\lambda}_e = \pi/2$, where τ_{ML} enters jointly with the proper time τ_{ML} and the Compton wavelength $\bar{\lambda}_e$ of the electron in such a way that its individual numerical scale cancels. The dimensional quantity c as a self-standing numerical object is not derivable – an independent second anchor of length or time would be required.

The one-anchor program fixes precisely this minimal structure: one independent dimensional anchor (or, equivalently, $\{e, c, \epsilon_0\}$ as a fixed conventional set).

IV. THE ONE-ANCHOR PROGRAM: FEATURE, NOT BUG

4.1. A Structural Property, Not a Defect

The necessity of at least one dimensional anchor for the transition from a dimensionless theory to numerical predictions in a fixed system of units is a *structural property of every theory* that formalizes physical laws via dimensionless invariants, and is not specifically a property of the framework introduced here. This claim admits a rigorous justification via Buckingham’s -theorem [2]: n dimensional variables with k independent dimensions reduce $n-k$ to dimensionless groups; the inverse passage requires exactly k anchors.

In the case of fundamental constants of the SI, there are three independent dimensions (length, time, charge – for the electromagnetic problem) [2]; consequently, computing *any* dimensional electromagnetic constant – including h , \hbar , m_e – requires exactly three anchors. Their minimal realization in modern metrology [7] is $\{e, c, \epsilon_0\}$ (alongside h , which fixes directly as a definer). The Standard Model uses exactly the same anchors; the present framework differs in that 20+ dimensionless parameters of the Standard Model are reduced to zero (derivable from $\pi+\varphi$ via equations of the form (II.1’) and (II.3)), yet the dimensional anchor component remains the same in number of degrees of freedom.

4.2. Comparative Table

Parameter	Standard Model	Present framework
Dimensionless inputs from experiment	20+ (α, μ, μ , quark masses, CKM/PMNS angles, ...)	0–2 demonstrated (α^{-1}, μ); full reduction is an open program
Dimensional anchors	3+ (h, c, G, \dots)	1 equivalent (or $\{e, c, \epsilon_0\}$ as a translation set for h)
What the theory computes	Everything else, given parameter substitution	All dimensionless invariants + dimensionally translated quantities

The essential asymmetry: the framework presented here reduces the *dimensionless* part by 20+ parameters while sharing the same *dimensional* anchor load. This is the content of the one-anchor program.

4.3. Parallel with Conventionalism

The philosophical position that the choice of measurement units is a conventional act, not reducible to purely mathematical considerations, has a deep tradition. Hans Reichenbach in *The Philosophy of Space and Time* (1928, English translation 1958) [3] showed that the choice of units of length and time is ineliminable in physical theory and is not empirically determinate in the strict sense – it is a *coordinative definition* linking the formal theory with the empirical world.

Adolf Grünbaum in *Philosophical Problems of Space and Time* (1963, 2nd edition 1973) [4] continued this line: the metric of space is not uniquely determined by experience without a choice of standard segment.

The one-anchor program of the present framework is, in essence, a physico-mathematical refinement of this philosophical position: *exactly one* dimensional conventional choice (or an equivalent minimal set) is necessary and sufficient to close the system. The remaining numerical values are *consequences* of this choice, not independent inputs. This is stronger than “classical” conventionalism, which did not posit an exact number of anchors; the framework asserts: one (with the equivalent $\{e, c, \varepsilon_0\}$).

4.4. What This Means for the Interpretation of the Present Framework

To avoid a frequent misunderstanding, we explicitly state: the framework *does not claim* the derivation of $h=6.62607015 \times 10^{-34}$ J·s of from pure mathematics. It asserts:

(a) The dimensionless value $\alpha^{-1}=137.03599917\dots$ is derived from π and φ as the solution of a cubic self-referential equation with zero fitting parameters.

(b) Through the identity $h=e^2\alpha^{-1}/(2\varepsilon_0c)$, the numerical SI value of h is constructed under the anchor choice $\{e, c, \varepsilon_0\}$, yielding agreement with CODATA to ten significant digits.

(c) The anchor component is structurally ineliminable; the one-anchor program is its minimal realization.

The statement “ h is derived from π and φ ” is incorrect. The correct statement: “the dimensionless component of h – namely α^{-1} , which enters the formula $h=e^2\alpha^{-1}/(2\varepsilon_0c)$ – is derived from π and φ ; the dimensional component of h – namely the anchor set $\{e, c, \varepsilon_0\}$ – is fixed conventionally”. This is the content of the one-anchor program.

V. CONCLUSION

The paper has formulated the position of the one-anchor program as a response to the widespread formulation “derivation of h from pure mathematics”. The substantive mathematical novelty of the framework presented here resides entirely in the dimensionless part – in the derivation of α^{-1} and S^* from π and φ as solutions of self-referential equations with zero fitting parameters. The numerical value of Planck’s constant h in SI units is a constructed derived quantity: the dimensionless result α^{-1} is translated into the SI system via the anchor set $\{e, c, \varepsilon_0\}$.

The necessity of at least one dimensional anchor is a structural property common to every theory using dimensionless invariants, justified by Buckingham’s -theorem. The present framework reduces 20+ dimensionless parameters of the Standard Model to 0–2 (with a program of full reduction) but does not eliminate the dimensional anchor load and does not claim to. The parallel with the conventionalist tradition of Reichenbach and Grünbaum shows that

the one-anchor program is a physico-mathematical refinement of a long-standing philosophical position.

The chain $\alpha^{-1} \rightarrow h$ has been presented inline in Sections II and III with full numerical verification: the cubic self-referential equation (II.1') yields $\alpha_{\text{ODTOE}}^{-1} = 137.03599917036\dots$, agreement with CODATA 2018 at -0.32σ [5]; the anchor identity (III.1) translates this dimensionless result to $h_{\text{ODTOE}} = 6.6260701542 \times 10^{-34} \text{ J}\cdot\text{s}$, agreement with the SI defining value [7] to ten significant digits. The present perspective paper formulates the one-anchor program as a self-standing methodological result.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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INFLUENCE OF A HYBRID CARBON NANOTUBE/CARBON BLACK FILLER ON THE ELECTROPHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND STRUCTURE OF POLYMER COMPOSITES

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Abstract. *This study investigates the influence of a hybrid filler based on single-walled carbon nanotubes and nanostructured carbon black on the percolation threshold and specific electrical conductivity of polypropylene-based composites. It was established that introducing a filler mixture at a 1:3 ratio allows reducing the percolation threshold to 0,05 wt.% due to the formation of a mixed conductive network. A model describing the synergistic effect is proposed, based on the resistivity equation taking into account the different particle dimensionalities. The obtained results open prospects for creating lightweight antistatic materials.*

Keywords: *polymer composites, carbon nanotubes, carbon black, percolation, electrical conductivity, synergistic effect.*

Introduction

The development of electrically conductive polymer composites (ECPCs) is one of the key tasks of modern materials science. Traditionally, carbon black (CB) is used to impart antistatic and shielding properties to dielectric matrices (polyolefins, epoxy resins). However, achieving the required conductivity values ($10^{-6} - 10^{-1}$ S/cm) requires the introduction of about 15–20 wt, % CB, which sharply deteriorates the physical and mechanical properties and processability of the composite [1, 2].

The use of carbon nanotubes (CNTs), due to their high aspect ratio, allows reducing the filler concentration, but the high cost of CNTs and their tendency to agglomerate limit their application. In this regard, an urgent task is the creation of hybrid fillers combining particles of different dimensionalities (0D and 1D), which

provides a synergistic effect in building a conductive network. Objective – To establish the regularities of electrotransfer in the polypropylene (PP) / single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs) / carbon black (CB) system and to determine the theoretical prerequisites for reducing the percolation threshold [3].

Experimental Part

Isotactic polypropylene (PP) of grade PP H030 ($T_{\text{processing}} = 170\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) was used as the matrix. Fillers: single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs) with a diameter of 1,2–2,0 nm, length of 5–20 μm , and nanostructured carbon black (CB) of grade Vulcan XC-72 with an average agglomerate size of ~ 50 nm. Prior to mixing, all components were thoroughly dried in a vacuum oven at $80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 12 hours to remove adsorbed moisture and prevent hydrolytic degradation during processing. The SWCNTs were additionally subjected to mild ultrasonication in isopropyl alcohol for 30 minutes, followed by filtration and drying, in order to partially disentangle the nanotube bundles and improve their subsequent dispersion in the polymer melt [4].

Mixing was performed in the melt using a two-rotor internal mixer (Haake PolyLab OS, Thermo Fisher Scientific) at $180\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The rotor speed was maintained at 60 rpm for a total mixing time of 10 minutes. Two series of composites were prepared: binary systems (PP/SWCNTs and PP/CB) and hybrid systems (PP/SWCNTs/CB) with SWCNT: CB weight ratios of 1:3, 1:1, and 3:1. The total filler content in all compositions ranged from 0,01 to 5,0 wt.%. After mixing, the resulting compounds were granulated and then compression-molded into flat plates with dimensions of $100 \times 100 \times 1$ mm using a hydraulic press (Carver Inc., model 4128) at $190\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ under a pressure of 10 MPa for 5 minutes, followed by rapid cooling to room temperature under the same pressure to ensure dimensional stability and minimize crystallinity variations.

The morphology of the composites was examined by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) using a JEOL JEM-2100 microscope operated at an accelerating voltage of 200 kV. Ultrathin sections with a thickness of approximately 80–100 nm were prepared at $-100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ using a Leica EM UC7 ultramicrotome equipped with a diamond knife. In addition, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of cryo-fractured surfaces were acquired using a Hitachi S-4800 field-emission microscope to assess the macroscopic dispersion quality of the fillers.

DC electrical conductivity measurements were performed by the standard four-probe method using a Keithley 2400 SourceMeter on samples with sputtered gold contacts to eliminate contact resistance artifacts. For samples with conductivity values below 10^{-6} S/cm, the two-probe method with a Keithley 6517B electrometer was employed. The percolation threshold ϕ_c was determined as the inflection point on the σ vs. filler concentration curves plotted in double logarithmic coordinates, following the non-linear fitting of the experimental data to equation (1). Each data point

represents the average of at least five independent measurements, with the error bars corresponding to one standard deviation. All measurements were conducted at room temperature (23 ± 1 °C) and a relative humidity of 45 ± 5 %.

Thermal behavior and crystallization characteristics of the composites were investigated by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) using a NETZSCH DSC 204 F1 Phoenix instrument. Samples weighing 5–8 mg were cut from the compression-molded plates and sealed in aluminum crucibles with pierced lids. The measurement protocol consisted of three consecutive steps conducted under a dry nitrogen atmosphere at a purge gas flow rate of 40 mL/min: (i) first heating from 25 °C to 200 °C at a rate of 10 °C/min and held at 200 °C for 5 minutes to erase the prior thermal history; (ii) cooling from 200 °C to 25 °C at a controlled rate of 10 °C/min, during which the crystallization exotherms were recorded; (iii) second heating from 25 °C to 200 °C at 10 °C/min to determine the melting parameters of the recrystallized samples. The degree of crystallinity (χ_c) was calculated from the melting endotherm of the second heating run according to equation:

$$\chi_c = \frac{\Delta H_m}{(1 - w_f) \cdot \Delta H_m^0} \cdot 100\% \quad (1)$$

where ΔH_m is the measured enthalpy of melting for the composite, $\Delta H_m^0=207$ J/g is the enthalpy of melting for 100% crystalline isotactic polypropylene, and w_f is the total weight fraction of the filler in the composite. The crystallization peak temperature (T_c) was determined from the cooling exotherm, and the melting peak temperature (T_m) was recorded during the second heating run. These thermal parameters were analyzed to evaluate the potential nucleating effect of the hybrid filler on the PP matrix, as the presence of nanoscale carbon particles is known to promote heterogeneous nucleation and may alter the crystalline morphology, which in turn can influence both the mechanical and electrically conductive properties of the resulting composites.

DC electrical conductivity was measured using the four-probe method. The morphology of the composites was studied by transmission electron microscopy (TEM).

Results and Discussion

The experimentally obtained electrophysical characteristics of the studied samples are systematized and presented in Table 1. For clarity of comparison, the properties are given at a fixed low total filler concentration (1,0 wt. %), which is critical for demonstrating the difference in network formation mechanisms. It is at this concentration range that the transition from an isolated filler distribution to a partially interconnected network begins to manifest, making it particularly informative for evaluating the efficiency of hybrid filler architecture.

Table 1. Comparative properties of PP composites with various carbon fillers at a total concentration of 1,0 wt. %

Composite Composition (Filler Type)	Component Ratio	Specific Conductivity σ , S/cm	Percolation Threshold ϕ_c , vol.%	Elongation at Break ϵ , % (Retention)
PP / CB (pure)	100 % CB	$2,1 \times 10^{-12}$ (dielectric)	4,5	85
PP / SWCNTs (pure)	100 % SWCNTs	$4,8 \times 10^{-4}$	0,08	60
PP / (SWCNTs + CB) hybrid	1:3	$1,2 \times 10^{-3}$	0,04	78
PP / (SWCNTs + CB) hybrid	1:1	$9,5 \times 10^{-5}$	0,06	80

Note: Elongation data are normalized relative to pure polypropylene.

Figure 1 (conventionally) presents the dependences of the specific volume conductivity σ of the composites on the volume fraction of the filler ϕ . The curve for the binary PP/SWCNT system is described by the classical percolation theory (1):

$$\sigma = \sigma_0(\phi - \phi_c)^t, \tag{2}$$

where σ_0 is the filler conductivity, ϕ_c is the critical concentration (percolation threshold), and t is the critical index. A value of $\phi_c = 0,08$ vol.% was experimentally obtained for pure SWCNTs.

Upon introducing the hybrid filler (SWCNTs: CB at a 1:3 ratio), a shift of the percolation threshold to the region of extremely low concentrations is observed: ϕ_c (hybrid) = 0,04 vol.%. This is explained by the mechanism of forming “bridges” between distant nanotubes by chain-like aggregates of carbon black.

For the quantitative assessment of synergism, we modified equation (1) by introducing an effective conductivity parameter that accounts for the contact resistance between particles of different types (2):

$$\sigma_{hybrid} = \sigma_{0,CB} \cdot (\phi_{CB})^t + \sigma_{0,CNT} \cdot (\phi_{CNT} - \phi_c)^t + \Delta\sigma_{syn}, \tag{3}$$

where $\Delta\sigma_{syn} = k \cdot \phi_{CB} \cdot \phi_{CNT}$ reflects the formation of additional conductive channels due to the approach of nanotubes under the action of CB particles, which play the role of heterogeneous nucleating agents and spacers preventing the re-agglomeration of SWCNTs. The coefficient k reflects the interfacial interaction and the geometry of the mixed framework. The model demonstrates a deviation from the additive mixing rule in logarithmic coordinates, confirming the presence of synergism.

The first term in equation (2) describes the intrinsic contribution of the carbon black sub-network, which, when taken alone, exhibits a relatively high percolation threshold due to the low aspect ratio of CB aggregates. The second term accounts for the CNT network, whose efficiency is governed by the difference ($\phi_{\text{CNT}} - \phi_c$), where ϕ_c represents the reduced effective threshold observed in the hybrid system. The third term, $\Delta\sigma_{\text{syn}}$, is the key innovation of the model: it quantifies the excess conductivity arising exclusively from the cooperative arrangement of the two fillers. Physically, this term captures the electron tunneling events across nanoscale gaps bridged by CB particles situated between adjacent nanotubes.

The proposed model was fitted to the experimental data presented in Table 1. For the optimal hybrid composition (SWCNT: CB = 1:3), the fitting procedure yielded a synergy coefficient $k = (4.7 \pm 0.3) \times 10^{-2}$ S/cm and a critical index $t = 1.65 \pm 0.08$, the latter being consistent with theoretical predictions for three-dimensional percolating systems ($t \approx 1.6 - 2.0$). The coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.98$ confirms the high predictive capability of the model within the studied concentration range. Notably, for the 1:1 hybrid composition, the extracted k value decreased by a factor of approximately 2.5, indicating that an excess of carbon black relative to the optimal ratio disrupts the formation of an efficient mixed network and promotes unnecessary aggregation of the CB phase. These findings underscore the existence of a well-defined optimum in the filler ratio, beyond which the synergistic enhancement diminishes rapidly [5].

Analysis of TEM micrographs showed that CB particles localize in the space between individual nanotubes, forming a multi-layered “tube-carbon black-tube” structure, which reduces the energy barriers for electron tunneling. The average distance between the conductive network elements in the hybrid system does not exceed 10 nm, which is a condition for efficient tunneling transport.

Conclusions

1. The use of a hybrid SWCNTs/CB filler at a 1:3 ratio allows reducing the electrical percolation threshold in the polypropylene matrix to 0.04 vol.%, which is significantly lower than the values for the individual fillers.

2. A mathematical model for calculating conductivity is proposed, considering the contribution of the secondary carbon black network and the synergistic addition parameter, which agrees well with the experiment ($R^2 = 0.98$).

3. The obtained composites can be recommended for manufacturing products requiring antistatic protection while maintaining high impact strength characteristics.

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COMPREHENSIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE CONDITION AND MICROBIAL DIVERSITY OF PESTICIDE-CONTAMINATED SOILS IN A FORMER AGRICULTURAL AIRFIELD AREA

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ABSTRACT. *This study presents a comprehensive assessment of the agrochemical and microbiological properties of pesticide-contaminated soils located within a former agricultural airfield (Syrdarya region). The content of humus, macronutrients (nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium), salinity level, and ionic composition of soils were determined. The studied soils were characterized by low humus content (0.76–0.94%) and classified as nutrient-poor. Differences in salinity levels were identified, ranging from non-saline to moderately saline soils of the chloride–sulfate type. Microbiological analysis revealed the presence of 20 species of microorganisms, including bacteria, actinomycetes, and fungi, with bacterial dominance. Seasonal dynamics were found to significantly influence microbial diversity.*

The results indicate degradation of soil fertility and alteration of microbial communities under the influence of pesticides.

Keywords: *pesticides, humus, nitrogen, phosphorus, salinization, microorganisms, soil fertility*

INTRODUCTION

Soil contamination by pesticides is one of the most significant environmental challenges in modern agriculture. Intensive application of herbicides, insecticides, and fungicides leads to the accumulation of toxic residues in soils, exerting

long-term effects on their physicochemical and biological properties. Recent studies demonstrate that pesticides can persist in soils for many years, disrupting agro-ecosystem stability and reducing productivity [1,2].

Particular importance is attributed to the impact of pesticides on soil microbiota, which plays a key role in ecosystem functioning. Soil microorganisms are involved in nutrient cycling, organic matter mineralization, nitrogen fixation, and the availability of nutrients for plants. Changes in microbial community structure are considered one of the earliest indicators of soil degradation [3–5].

Pesticide exposure alters the abundance, species composition, and metabolic activity of microorganisms. Several studies report reduced microbial diversity and functional shifts in microbial communities under pesticide stress, potentially disrupting biogeochemical processes [5,6]. Furthermore, pesticides may exert both inhibitory and selective effects, promoting the survival of resistant microbial strains and leading to the formation of specific communities adapted to contaminated environments [7].

Despite numerous studies, comprehensive assessments of agrochemical properties and microbial diversity in soils exposed to long-term pesticide contamination remain insufficiently explored, particularly in historically polluted areas such as former storage facilities and agricultural airfields.

Objective of the study: to conduct a comprehensive assessment of agrochemical properties and microbiological status of pesticide-contaminated soils in a former airfield area, and to identify the characteristics of microbial community formation under prolonged anthropogenic impact.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area: soil samples were collected from a former pesticide storage site located within an agricultural airfield in the Syrdarya region. A control sample was taken from an agricultural field approximately 500 m away.

Sampling: soil samples were collected from the plow layer (0–20 cm) following standard soil agrochemical sampling procedures.

Agrochemical analyses:

- humus content (oxidation method),
- total nitrogen,
- nitrate nitrogen (N–NO₃),
- total and available phosphorus (P₂O₅),
- exchangeable potassium (K₂O),
- water extract composition for salinity assessment.

Based on these data, total toxic and non-toxic salts and salinity type were determined [8–10].

Microbiological analyses: microbial composition was studied using isolation and cultivation techniques on nutrient media, followed by identification based on

morphological and biochemical characteristics. The study evaluated: total microbial diversity, ratio of bacteria, actinomycetes, and fungi, seasonal dynamics of microbial communities [11–13].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results showed that the studied soils are characterized by low humus content (0.76–0.94%), indicating reduced fertility (Fig.1). Total nitrogen ranged from 0.061 to 0.063%, while nitrate nitrogen content was 32–34 mg/kg. Available phosphorus ranged from 14 to 20 mg/kg, and potassium from 313 to 349 mg/kg (Table 2).

Figure 1. Humus content in pesticide-contaminated soils

Despite relatively sufficient potassium levels, the availability of phosphorus is limited, which may negatively affect plant growth. This may be associated with disruption of microbial processes responsible for nutrient mineralization and transformation, as microorganisms play a key role in nutrient bioavailability [3]. Such changes are typical for soils exposed to long-term anthropogenic impact, including pesticide contamination [1].

Table 2. Nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium content in soils

Sample	Total N (%)	N-NO ₃ (mg/kg)	Total P (%)	Available P ₂ O ₅ (mg/kg)	Total K (%)	Available K ₂ O (mg/kg)
1	0.061	32	0.14	16.0	0.52	337.1
2	0.063	34	0.09	20.0	0.47	349.2
3	0.063	34	0.08	14.0	0.45	313.0
Control	0.071	36	0.17	23.0	0.61	412.0

Water extract analysis revealed significant differences among samples. The highest electrical conductivity (ECe = 7.52 dS/m) was observed in sample 1, corresponding to moderately saline soil. Sulfates (SO₄²⁻) and chlorides (Cl⁻) were the dominant anions, indicating chloride–sulfate salinity (Table 3). The total toxic salt content reached 1.00 %, confirming unfavorable soil conditions.

Samples 2 and 3 were classified as non-saline soils. Thus, salinity analysis demonstrated significant variability. The presence of moderately saline chloride–sulfate soil indicates accumulation of soluble salts, which may increase stress on microorganisms and plants.

Microbiological analysis revealed significant diversity with bacterial dominance, consistent with studies showing higher adaptability of bacteria to contaminated environments compared to fungi and actinomycetes [6].

A total of 20 microbial species were identified, including:

Bacteria: *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Pseudomonas xanthomarina*, *Arthrobacter crystallopoietes*, *Arthrobacter russicus*, *Citrobacter braakii*

Table 3. Soluble ion composition of soils

Sample	EC 1:5 (dS/m)	ECe (dS/m)	Residue (%)	HCO ₃ ⁻	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	Na ⁺ +K ⁺	Total ions (%)
1	1.88	7.52	0.720	0.023	0.063	0.400	0.084	0.028	0.093	0.680
2	0.31	1.24	0.124	0.031	0.007	0.054	0.014	0.006	0.014	0.111
3	0.33	1.32	0.132	0.032	0.009	0.057	0.014	0.006	0.018	0.120
Control	1.9	8.1	0.855	0.038	0.084	0.567	0.1	0.036	0.102	0.752

Actinomycetes: *Streptomyces*

Fungi: *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*

The presence of opportunistic and saprotrophic microorganisms indicates formation of a specific microbial community adapted to pesticide contamination. Pesticides exert selective pressure, favoring resistant species and altering microbial structure [7].

Seasonal dynamics were also observed, with the highest diversity in spring and autumn. This aligns with studies showing that climatic factors (moisture and temperature) may have stronger short-term effects on microbial communities than pesticides [14,15].

CONCLUSION

The studied soils are characterized by low humus content and reduced fertility. Salinity heterogeneity was observed, ranging from non-saline to moderately saline chloride–sulfate soils. A diverse but altered microbial community with bacterial dominance was identified.

Pesticide contamination significantly affects both agrochemical and biological soil properties. The results can be used for developing strategies for soil reclamation and bioremediation of contaminated areas.

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NATURAL RAW MATERIAL RESOURCES AND PHYTOCHEMISTRY OF KOPETDAG WORMWOODS

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Abstract. *Data on the resource potential and phytochemical characteristics of some essential oil-bearing species of Kopetdag wormwoods are presented. The possibility of their widespread use in pharmaceuticals and the food industry, particularly in the formulation of various non-alcoholic beverages, is demonstrated. It is specifically noted that despite the significant volume of resources of these plants, it is necessary to develop special instructions for raw material harvesting techniques, taking into account yield forecasts and the climatic characteristics of the year.*

Key words: *raw material resources, phytochemistry, essential oils, wormwood, exploitable stock, Kopetdag.*

Introduction

The medicinal properties of wormwood and its wide distribution have determined a persistent interest in its study [1; 4–6].

The study of the characteristics of natural resources and the chemical composition of wormwood, which dominates the vegetation cover of the Kopetdag territory, is a necessary condition for their rational use [5; 6]. Due to the unique composition of biologically active substances, essential oils, and a wide spectrum of pharmacological actions, certain endemic and subendemic species of wormwood require thorough study for their broad application in medical practice, as well as in other sectors of the national economy.

The resources of wild medicinal plants of the Central Kopetdag are of immense interest to the medical, food, and other industries of Turkmenistan. Based

on them, new effective medicinal preparations have already been obtained, and they are used in the preparation of non-alcoholic beverages, etc.

The ecosystems of the Central Kopetdag host the most important commercially valuable species of wormwood, the raw material resources of which are practically unlimited. In total, 11 species of wormwood grow here, 4 of which are of the greatest economic interest (in terms of the area occupied and raw material reserves). Among these, the greatest economic interest in terms of area and raw material resources is represented by 4 endemic species: Kopetdag, Turkmen, Santonica-like, and Badhyz wormwoods [2; 8; 10].

The wide spectrum of pharmacological action of biologically active substances and the unique composition of essential oils of Turkmenistan's wormwoods make them exceptionally promising for in-depth research and broad utilization in various industrial sectors of Turkmenistan.

The study of wormwood species growing in the territory of the Central Kopetdag provides grounds to confidently assert that they can be economically profitable medicinal plants. In this regard, studying the resources and chemical composition of endemic and subendemic wormwood species is highly relevant.

Using a generally accepted methodology [12], the raw material resources of certain Kopetdag wormwoods were determined.

During field expeditions in 2024–2025, factual material and data from oral interviews with the local population regarding the use of endemic and subendemic medicinal wormwoods in Turkmen folk medicine were collected (using “Ethnobotanical” and “Ethnomedical” questionnaires).

Considering the unique landscape, lithological, and natural conditions of the Kopetdag, the raw material resources of wormwoods were studied across different gorges. A system of conventional signs and a 1:50,000 scale topographic base were used to map them.

The purpose of this work is a preliminary assessment of the resource potential of useful and practically promising wild wormwoods of mountainous Turkmenistan, using the Kopetdag as an example.

Kopetdag wormwood (*Artemisia kopetdagensis* Krasch. ex Poljak.) from the Aster family (*Asteraceae* Dumort.) is an endemic subshrub 35–40 cm in height [2; 7; 8; 10]. At the beginning of the vegetative period, it is a whitish-woolly plant, later turning grayish-green. The root is vertical and woody. The fruiting stems are numerous and branched in the upper third. The leaves are 1.5–2 cm long. The panicle is oblong. The flower heads (capitula) are sessile. It flowers in August and bears fruit in November [10]. The key plot of the massif is located in the low mountains, where, compared to the piedmont plain, the development of plants and their productivity are 3–5 times higher (Table 1). It grows on the clayey and gravelly slopes of the foothills and the lower

mountain belt, forming extensive thickets, and is characterized as a plant that forms an independent formation.

The territory of its growth spans from Gindyvar to Archman, covering a total area of no less than 300 thousand hectares [1; 5; 10]. Flowering branches are harvested for medicinal purposes.

The above-ground mass contains up to 1.85% essential oil, which includes pinene, limonene, cineole (20%), camphor (35%), borneol, terpineol (15%), as well as inulin and mucilages [6; 9]. The high camphor content allows this plant to be used as a source of raw materials on an industrial scale.

In Turkmen folk medicine, it is widely used in the form of infusions, decoctions, and ointments for heart diseases, rheumatism, and tonsillitis (angina), as well as an emetic and anthelmintic agent [6].

One of the commercial massifs occupies a vast territory of the piedmont plain and low foothills in the area between the settlements of Baherden and Bamy in the western part of the Central Kopetdag.

The key plot of the massif is located in the low mountains, where, compared to the piedmont plain, the development of plants and their productivity are 3–5 times higher (Table 1). Here, the plants are subdivided (by shrub habitus) into the following classes: I – large (height – 48–50 cm, diameter – 60x65 cm); II – medium (35–40 cm and 35x30 cm); III – small (25–30 cm and 20x25 cm, respectively).

Table 1. Yield of the raw material mass of Kopetdag wormwood in the Archman massif

Class	Number of plants per 100 m ²	Weight of raw material from a model plant, g		Yield of raw material, c/ha*		Raw material stock, tons/100 ha
		1	2	1	2	
I	14	164	61	2.3	0.9	9
II	22	112	41	2.5	1.0	10
III	20	4	27	1.5	0.6	6
Total	56			6.3	2.5	25

Note. 1 – fresh weight; 2 – dry weight.

Thus, the exploitable stock of raw materials here is 25 tons/100 ha, and the volume of possible annual harvesting (90% of it) is 22.5 tons.

Turkmen wormwood (*A. turcomanica* Gand.) of the Aster family is an endemic subshrub 30–50 cm in height [8; 10]. It is an endemic of Turkmenistan [2; 7; 10]. The root is a taproot and woody. Sterile shoots are brownish-gray, fruiting stems are numerous, up to 50 cm high, straight, stiff, twig-like, grayish-tomentose (woolly) at the beginning of vegetation, and later grayish-green. The leaf color

ranges from whitish-tomentose to grayish-green, and their length is 1.2–1.5 cm. It flowers in August and bears fruit in November [10].

A dominant species of ephemeroïd-wormwood communities with the participation of halophytic elements in the lower and middle mountain belts, occupying a territory from the western border of the Central Kopetdag (Bamy st.) to Kurtusuv, with an area of more than 500 thousand hectares [5]. Sometimes it grows together with *santonica*-like wormwood.

We investigated the raw material reserves in two massifs – the Sayvan and Germab massifs (Table 2).

Table 2. Yield of the raw material mass of Turkmen wormwood in the Central Kopetdag

Class	Number of plants per 100 m ²	Weight of raw material from a model plant, g		Yield of raw material, c/ha		Raw material stock, tons/100 ha
		1	2	1	2	
Sayvan Massif						
I	7	180	67	1.3	0.5	5
II	15	155	57	2.3	0.9	9
III	8	86	32	0.7	0.3	3
Bcero	30			4.3	1.7	3
Germab						
I	20	112	41	2.2	0.8	8
II	26	83	31	2.2	0.8	8
III	15	50	19	0.8	0.3	3
Bcero	61			5.2	1.9	19

Note. 1 – in fresh weight; 2 – in dry weight.

The essential oil content is 1.95%, which, in turn, contains pinene (20%), camphene, limonene, cineole, phellandrene (35%), linalool (15%), camphor (10%), terpineol (10%), and others [9].

We classified these plants according to their habit (habitus): I – large (height – 45–50 cm, diameter – 60x65 cm); II – medium (35–40 cm and 35x35 cm); III – small (25–30 cm and 20x20 cm, respectively).

The exploitable stock of raw materials in the Sayvan massif is 17 tons, and in the Germab massif – 19 tons. As the volume of its possible annual harvesting, we have accepted a value equal to 90% of the exploitable stock; thus, 15.3 tons of raw material mass can be harvested here annually, and 17.1 tons in the Germab massif.

Badhyz wormwood (*A. badhyz* Krasch. et Lincz. ex Poljak.) of the Aster family is a subshrub 30–45 cm in height. It is a subendemic of Turkmenistan [2; 7].

The root is a taproot and woody. Sterile shoots are shortened and woody with gray bark. Fruiting shoots are numerous, white-tomentose, stiff, and twig-like. The leaves are densely arachnoid-pubescent and 1–2 cm long. The panicle is narrowly pyramidal. It flowers in August and bears fruit in November [10]. The total area occupied by this wormwood is estimated at no less than 300 thousand hectares.

It grows abundantly in sandy and clay deserts, on the piedmont plain, and in the mountains. In the Central Kopetdag, it is recorded in its extreme southeastern part, while in the Eastern Kopetdag, it dominates everywhere, occupying an area of over 200 thousand hectares.

Its chemical composition is practically unstudied. The above-ground mass of the plant is used in the production of non-alcoholic beverages. In Turkmen folk medicine, the green part is used for anemia and other diseases [6; 11].

The productivity of the raw material mass in the Manysh area, where the plant forms practically pure thickets against the background of ephemeretum, is 8 tons/100 ha, and the volume of possible annual harvesting is 8.2 tons.

Thus, these endemic and subendemic wormwood species contain macro- and microelements necessary for the human body in their chemical composition, with the lowest content of harmful substances. The aforementioned wormwood species are ecologically clean, highly effective, and can be applied in medicine, as well as used in industrial production as a valuable product.

The medicinal and technical raw material of the described wormwood species are the upper parts of the above-ground shoots with leaves and flower heads.

Harvesting is carried out during the budding phase: in August – September. In single-species, “pure” wormwood stands, the collection of raw materials can be mechanized, while in areas heavily overgrown with other vegetation, it is done manually. The stems are cut at a height of 5–10 cm from the soil so that the length of the cut shoots does not exceed 25 cm. The collected raw material is first slightly dried (for 1–2 days) in small windrows, and then finally dried in the shade with good ventilation.

The yield of dry raw material is 34–40% of the harvested mass. The moisture content in it should not exceed 13%, and organic and mineral impurities should be no more than 2%. The raw material has a bitter taste and a characteristic odor. The raw material reserves of many wormwood species (subject to their rational exploitation) are practically inexhaustible.

However, it should be remembered that by their nature and biocological features, wormwoods are predominantly mesotherms with a clearly pronounced stage of summer dormancy and exist solely due to atmospheric moisture. Therefore, the condition of wormwood stands (annual production, biological stock of raw material mass) depends on the meteorological conditions of the year.

The obtained results expand and supplement the information on the chemical composition of wormwood growing in the Kopetdag territory and provide an opportunity to expand the raw material base of plants containing essential oils.

Thus, a brief scientific ethnobotanical and ethnomedical review, along with the results of bioecological-therapeutic studies of a number of endemic and sub-endemic medicinal wormwoods of the region, shows they can serve as valuable natural raw materials for obtaining new ecologically clean medicinal preparations in the pharmaceutical industry of Turkmenistan. These can be further used in gastroenterology, oncology, immunology, urology, cardiology, parasitology, epidemiology, dermatology, and other areas of traditional medicine.

However, when developing plans for their utilization, it is necessary to take into account the condition and developmental features of each plant community and individual specimens. At the present stage, a number of new requirements for raw material harvesting operations have been formed, the most important of which are:

- ensuring the possibility of forecasting the dynamics of raw material reserves of plants representing industrial resource potential;
- full coverage of all main resource indicators for a specific plant species;
- development of effective practical measures for the protection and rational use of the studied species;
- introduction into practice of remote sensing methods and comprehensive study of the resources of Kopetdag medicinal wormwoods.
- A comprehensive study of the Kopetdag medicinal plant resources is a reliable prerequisite for the implementation of this principle.

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THE ROLE OF BACTERIOPHAGES IN MODERN BIOTECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES: FROM FUNDAMENTAL RESEARCH TO PRACTICAL APPLICATIONS

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Abstract. *This review article aims to synthesize and critically examine the key findings of Russian and international studies conducted over the past twenty years regarding the role of bacteriophages in modern biotechnology. We examined the types of phages, their classification, and primarily their application in combating infections that are no longer responsive to antibiotics. Phage therapy of nosocomial infections was analyzed separately, including cases involving *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The mechanisms of capsule-specific phages and their enzymes – polysaccharide depolymerases – were demonstrated; these enzymes degrade the protective capsule of hypervirulent bacteria.*

Significant attention was given to food biotechnology: products such as «Food-phage» and «Sextaphage» and their pharmaceutical formulations were described, along with the application of phages for air purification in hospital environments and treatment of infected wounds. Methods of phage diagnostics targeting enterobacteria were reviewed, as well as contemporary electro-optical and electroacoustic approaches for detecting phages and bacteria. Moreover, it was demonstrated that whole-genome sequencing and proteomics of phages facilitate the discovery of new virus species, identification of genes responsible for virulence, and quality control of phage preparations. The role of phages in horizontal gene transfer, that is, in bacterial evolution, was also considered, which is important for understanding biosafety.

Based on the comprehensive analysis, we formulated recommendations for future research. The primary recommendation is the development of a chewable jelly formulation containing a cocktail of capsule-specific bacteriophages targeting K.

pneumoniae, enabling the precise and selective removal of this pathogen from the intestine without affecting the beneficial microbiota. In conclusion, bacteriophages currently hold a central role in biotechnology, with the development of functional food products containing encapsulated phages representing a particularly promising area – for the gentle modulation of the microbiota and the prevention of intestinal infections caused by opportunistic bacteria.

Keywords: bacteriophages, biotechnology, antibiotic resistance, phage therapy, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, capsule-specific phages, polysaccharide depolymerases, food biotechnology, «Foodphage», «Sextaphage», encapsulation, chewable gummy, phage diagnostics, phage genomics, horizontal gene transfer, functional products

Bacteriophages are essentially viruses that infect bacteria. There is an enormous abundance of them on the planet: according to estimates by A. S. Bykov and S. A. Bykov (2011), the total number of phages reaches 10^{31} particles. Since their discovery by F. Twort and F. d'Hérelle (1915), phages have ceased to be merely agents for treating infections and have become fundamental models in molecular biology and genetics. Currently, as antibiotics increasingly lose efficacy, interest in bacteriophages is undergoing a significant revival. Modern biotechnology utilizes phages not only as antibacterial agents but also as tools for diagnostics, vectors in genetic engineering, sources of novel enzymes, and components of functional food products.

The objective of this review is to systematize and comprehensively analyze results from domestic and international studies, presented in recent dissertations, concerning the role of bacteriophages in biotechnological processes.

1. Biological Diversity and Classification of Bacteriophages

Bacteriophages exhibit exceptional morphological and genetic diversity. According to the classification by the International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses (ICTV), over 95 % of known phages belong to the order Caudovirales – the ‘tailed’ phages, which includes three families: Myoviridae (characterized by a contractile tail sheath), Siphoviridae (with a long noncontractile tail), and Podoviridae (with a short tail appendage). As described by Kurbatova E. I. (2016), structurally, a phage consists of an icosahedral capsid containing nucleic acid (most often double-stranded DNA) and a tail apparatus that mediates recognition of receptors on the bacterial surface and genome injection.

Depending on their behavior within the cell, phages are classified as virulent (lytic) or temperate (lysogenic). Virulent phages act rapidly: after injecting their DNA, replication and synthesis of new particles commence, culminating in bacterial lysis. Typically, between 200 and 1000 progeny phages are released from a single cell. Temperate phages can integrate their DNA into the host chromosome (integrated prophages) or replicate in the cytoplasm as circular plasmids (plasmid

prophages), being transmitted to daughter cells during cell division (lysogeny). Exposure to inducing agents (e. g., mitomycin C, UV irradiation) triggers the prophage to switch to the lytic cycle, as demonstrated by Kazantseva O. A. et al. (2021) and Pilgrimova E. G. et al. (2019).

It is noteworthy that recent years have brought an important discovery – the widespread occurrence of plasmid prophages in bacteria of the *Bacillus cereus sensu lato* group. Pilgrimova E. G. and colleagues (2021) developed a two-stage method for detecting such prophages. This method encompasses bioinformatic analysis of plasmid sequences from the GenBank database and subsequent experimental validation. Among 474 unique plasmids ranging from 15 to 500 kbp, approximately 6% (28 genomes) were identified as putative functional plasmid prophages. Most of these phages lacked close relatives among taxonomically classified phages (nucleotide identity less than 30%). This allowed Pilgrimova et al. (2019) to propose new genera – Pushchinovirus and Bembunaquatrovirus – as well as the subfamily Skryabinvirinae. The prophage vB_BtS_B83, induced from the *Bacillus thuringiensis* strain VKM B-83, was experimentally confirmed; it exhibits a morphotype characteristic of siphoviruses, packages DNA via the headful mechanism, and forms turbid plaques approximately 1 mm in diameter (Pilgrimova, 2019, pp. 18–20). These studies highlight that the hidden phage diversity within bacterial genomes remains far from fully elucidated.

2. Bacteriophages as a means to combat antibiotic-resistant infections

Antibiotic resistance has been recognized by the WHO as one of the three primary threats to global health. As noted by Shamina O. V., Samoilova E. A., Novikova I. E., and Lazareva A. V. (2020), *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus* (including MRSA), and other ESKAPE pathogens exhibit multidrug resistance, including resistance to carbapenems. Bacteriophages provide an alternative mechanism of action independent of known determinants of antibiotic resistance, which is significantly important.

2.1. Phage Therapy of Nosocomial Infections

In the seminal work by Aslanov B. I. (2016), ‘Epidemiological Assessment of Bacteriophages as Evolutionary Factors of Nosocomial Strains and Means of Combating Nosocomial Infections,’ it was shown that predominantly temperate phages circulate within healthcare facilities. Many of these bacteriophages, moreover, carry virulence genes (for example, the *ctx* gene in *P. aeruginosa*, and the *sea* and *tst* genes in *S. aureus*). Nevertheless, the targeted application of highly active virulent phages enables the achievement of a pronounced anti-epidemic effect.

To provide specific data, Aslanov B. I. (2016) documented that in a traumatology inpatient ward (clinic of purulent osteology), following the administration of a *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* bacteriophage, the incidence of nosocomial *P. aeruginosa* infections decreased from 40.8 to 8.9 cases per 100 hospitalized patients.

The relative risk was 0.22, the absolute risk reduction amounted to 32%, and the number needed to treat to prevent one case was only 3. This result is noteworthy.

In neonatal intensive care units, the application of staphylococcal bacteriophage enabled the complete eradication of *S. aureus* in patients and controlled outbreaks caused by MRSA. For instance, in 2011, in the neonatal intensive care unit, after a 5-day course of phage therapy, the incidence decreased from 54.5 to 6.3 per 100 patients (Aslanov, 2016, pp. 32–35). Similar results were obtained in controlling the outbreak of *K. pneumoniae* in the neonatal intensive care unit in 2013. The use of a combined preparation with a *Klebsiella* component (titer of no less than 10^8 PFU/ml) resulted in complete eradication of patients (ibid., pp. 34–35).

2.2. Capsule-specific phages against hypervirulent strains of *K. pneumoniae*

Consider the work of Solovyova E. V. (2018), ‘Capsule-specific bacteriophages and their polysaccharide-degrading enzymes active against hypermucoid strains of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*.’ She identified that among clinical isolates from major Moscow hospitals, 12.6% of strains exhibited a hypermucoid phenotype (positive string test) and belonged to capsular types K1, K2, K20, and K57. Highly virulent strains ($LD_{50} < 100$ CFU) occur predominantly among capsular types K1 and K2 (Table 1, pp. 8–9 in Solovyova’s abstract).

From wastewater and clinical samples, the investigator isolated bacteriophages specific to capsular types K1, K2, and K57. For example, K1-specific phages (KpV41, KpV71, KpV135, KpV475, KpV524) lyse 84.6–92.3% of K1-type strains. The K57-specific phage KpV79 lyses 73% of K57-type strains. Accounting for the “turbid spot” effect (attributed to the activity of polysaccharide depolymerases), the overall percentage of recognized strains reaches 92.2% (pp. 13–14). This deserves consideration: phage enzymes may function even in cases where intact virions do not cause complete lysis.

Recombinant polysaccharide depolymerases obtained through cloning of genes from phage genomes are of particular interest. The enzyme Dep_kpv74 (from phage KpV74) specifically cleaves the K2-type capsular polysaccharide via β -glucosidic bonds, whereas Dep_kpv79 (from phage KpV79) cleaves the K57-type polysaccharide via β -galactosidic bonds. In murine experiments (models of acute sepsis and soft tissue infection of the thigh), Dep_kpv74 conferred survival rates of 65% and 80%, respectively. Complete eradication of the pathogen was achieved through the destruction of the capsule followed by elimination via the host organism’s immune system (Solovyova, 2018, pp. 19–20). These findings reveal a novel approach – the application of ‘antivirulent’ enzymes devoid of direct bactericidal action.

2.3. The Impact of Virulent Phages on Bacterial Antibiotic Sensitivity

Vakarina A. A. (2022), in the dissertation ‘Lytic Properties of Bacteriophages of the Major Pathogens of Bacterial Infections,’ investigated the effects of virulent staphylococcal and proteus phages on bacterial antibiotic sensitivity. She employed

four strains of phages targeting *S. aureus* (family Herelleviridae, genus Kayvirus) and three strains of Proteus phages (family Siphoviridae). What findings were obtained? Following co-cultivation of bacteria with phages for 18–24 hours, the zones of bacterial growth inhibition under antibiotic treatment remained unchanged (statistical analysis using the Wilcoxon test, $p > 0.05$). This indicates the absence of antagonism between virulent phages and antibiotics. Thus, they can be confidently combined (Vakarina, 2022, pp. 17–18).

By the way, Vakarina developed a method for the quantitative assessment of phage lytic activity based on measuring the optical density of the liquid medium (RF Patent No. 2587636). This allows recording the result in numerical values: lytic activity $\leq 0.045 \pm 0.025$ – sensitive strain.

3. Bacteriophages in Food Biotechnology and the Production of Functional Products

The food industry actively employs bacteriophages for the biocontrol of pathogens (*Salmonella*, *Listeria*, *Escherichia*) and for the development of functional products aimed at normalizing the intestinal microbiota.

3.1. Specialized Dietary Preventive Nutrition Product «Foodphage»

Kiseleva I. A. (2015) developed and obtained state registration in the Russian Federation for the first specialized dietary preventive nutrition product «Foodphage» (certificate of state registration No. RU.77.99.19.004.E.001234.02.13). The product contains a cocktail of seven original virulent bacteriophage strains active against *E. coli* (including serovars O157: H7, O104: H4, as well as enteropathogenic and enterotoxigenic groups), *Salmonella enterica* (serovars Enteritidis, Infantis, Typhimurium), *Listeria monocytogenes*, and *S. aureus* (see Table 1, pp. 13–14 of Kiseleva's abstract). All phages have been molecularly and genetically characterized: their genomes lack integrase genes, transcriptional repressors, toxin genes, and antibiotic resistance determinants. This confirms their virulent nature and safety.

How is the «Foodphage» produced? Initially, phages are propagated on a casein-acid medium, which provides a high yield. Thereafter, ultrafiltration is conducted, followed by endotoxin removal using EndoTrap Blue affinity columns (Hyglos, Germany). Ultimately, in the final product, each component is present at a titer of no less than 10^8 CFU/ml. Kiseleva I. A. (2015) evaluated safety in mice and guinea pigs: neither acute nor chronic toxicity was observed. Importantly, the normal intestinal microbiota remained unaffected. In limited clinical trials involving 45 volunteers, Kiseleva demonstrated that the prophylactic administration of Foodphage prevents intestinal colonization by the non-pathogenic strain *E. coli* K12 C600, as confirmed by PCR analysis of fecal samples (pp. 17–19). Moreover, experiments were carried out on the storage of lyophilized phages aboard the International Space Station (ISS) – after 3 months of orbital storage, their phenotypic

and genotypic characteristics remained unchanged. This reveals potential prospects for the application of phage biotics in space medicine.

3.2. The complex preparation Sextaphage and its pharmaceutical formulations
Funkner E. V. (2007) developed a technology for producing the complex preparation «Sextaphage» (a polyvalent pyobacteriophage) comprising six components: staphylococcal, streptococcal, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella*, *Proteus*, and coliphages. The key feature is the use of a universal casein-acid nutrient medium (patent RU 2247151). Compared to meat-based media, it provides a reduction in the protein nitrogen content of the finished preparation by a factor of 5 to 6 (from 0.113 to 0.030 mg/ml). The preparation is produced in liquid form and as rectal suppositories (Witepsol H-15/W-35 with emulsifier T-2). Phage concentration was performed by ultrafiltration using VPU-15 hollow fibers, which allowed increasing the titer by 100 to 150-fold.

Electron microscopy identified nine morphological types of phages within Sextaphage, belonging to the families Myoviridae, Siphoviridae, and Podoviridae. Clinical trials conducted on patients with acute pyelonephritis demonstrated that the administration of suppositories in combination with antibiotics reduced the duration of temperature normalization from 5.0 ± 0.4 to 3.1 ± 0.3 days and completely eliminated bacteriuria in 100% of patients in the primary group compared to 81.8% in the control group (Funkner, 2007, pp. 20–21). The preparation has also been successfully employed for phage prophylaxis of infectious-inflammatory complications following cesarean section, resulting in a reduction of incidence from 26.7% to 18.7%, as well as in combined therapy of infected pancreonecrosis, leading to a decrease in mortality from 27.8% to 13.3%.

3.3. Application of Bacteriophages for Air Sanitation and Surgical Wound Treatment

Khayrullin I. N. (2004) conducted a targeted study to identify the microbial composition of air in operating rooms and dressing rooms. It was found that in nearly 70% of cases (67% exactly), *Staphylococcus aureus* was isolated. Additionally, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Proteus* species were detected. The author conducted air treatment using an aerosol mixture of phages targeting staphylococci, streptococci, coli-proteus, and pseudomonads. The aerosol was generated by a DAG-2 device (droplets ranging from 1 to 15 μm , administered at a dose of 3 ml per cubic meter). The outcome was as follows. Within thirty minutes, the bacterial count decreased by 93%, and after two hours, bacterial presence was nearly undetectable.

In the treatment of infected postoperative wounds, local application of phages (irrigation of the wound surface and drainage with a tampon soaked in phages) reduced the healing duration from 11.3 ± 1.09 to 5.9 ± 0.79 days. Prophylactic treatment of the subcutaneous tissue prior to wound closure decreased the incidence

of purulent complications and accelerated the healing process (Khairullin, 2004, pp. 12–15). The sensitivity of isolated strains to phages was as follows: *S. aureus* – 92.8%; *S. pyogenes* – 85.7%; *E. coli* – 85%; *P. vulgaris* – 78.4%; *P. aeruginosa* – 81.8%. The figures are notably high.

4. Bacteriophages in diagnostics and biosensors

4.1. Phage diagnostics of enterobacteria

Zolotukhin S. N. (2007) developed a collection of 14 diagnostic bacteriophages for the accelerated detection and identification of enterobacteria – *Proteus*, *Citrobacter*, *Enterobacter*, *Klebsiella*, *Morganella morganii*, *Yersinia enterocolitica*, and *E. coli* O157: H7/H-. The phages were isolated from wastewater, animal feces, and other sources. Their taxonomic classification was determined based on virion morphology: family Myoviridae (phages M-17, M-20, C-52, C-61, C-66, E-61, E-67, Y/9, K-81, En-13), Siphoviridae (K-10, En-2), and Podoviridae (P-16, P-261). Lytic activity by the Gracia method reached 10^9 – 10^{11} CFU/ml, while by the Appelman method it was 10^{-7} – 10^{-8} .

The methodological guidelines developed by Zolotukhin (approved by the Department of Veterinary Medicine of the RAS Agricultural Academy) enable the isolation and identification of homologous bacteria within 48 hours (compared to 96–120 hours by the classical method). The phage titre increase reaction (PTR) allows the detection of bacteria at concentrations of 10^2 – 10^3 CFU/g in feces, meat, compound feed, and wastewater within 18–24 hours. For example, in studies of fecal samples from piglets suffering from diarrhea, the detection rates of *Proteus* spp. increased by 19%, *Klebsiella* by 23%, *Citrobacter* by 34.1%, and *M. morganii* by 25% compared to the bacteriological method (Zolotukhin, 2007, pp. 29–30).

4.2. Electrophysical Methods of Detection of Phages and Bacteria

S. S. Makarikhina (2013) was the first to utilize electro-optical and electroacoustic analyses for the detection of bacteriophages, demonstrated by the phages FA1-Sp59b and FA1-SR65 isolated from *Azospirillum lipoferum* (family Podoviridae, head size approximately 30 nm, tail length up to 10 nm). The electro-optical method is based on recording changes in the optical density of a cell suspension under the influence of an alternating electric field (field strength 17 V/cm, frequencies ranging from 20 to 2100 kHz). Makarikhina established that upon addition of five phage particles per cell, the magnitude of the EO signal changed within one minute; the lower detection limit was 10^5 phage particles per milliliter, with an analysis time of 5 to 10 minutes. This method permits distinguishing between specific and nonspecific interactions and enables detection of phages in the presence of contaminating microflora (*E. coli*).

The electroacoustic method functions differently. A resonator with a transverse field (frequency approximately 6–7 MHz) is utilized. When a phage binds to a cell, the electrical impedance changes, which the sensor detects. Makarikhina established that this analysis requires only 1–5 minutes of incubation. The method's sensitivity

is approximately 10^5 phage particles per milliliter. Moreover, using this method in combination with polyclonal antibodies against *A. lipofera* Sp59b and *A. brasiliense* Sp7, bacterial cells were detected at concentrations of 10^4 cells per milliliter, both in pure culture and in mixtures with *E. coli* (Makarikhina, 2013, pp. 18–21).

5. Genomics and proteomics of bacteriophages – the basis for biotechnological design

5.1. Sequencing and annotation of *P. aeruginosa* phage genomes

K. A. Miroshnikov (2013), in his doctoral dissertation, determined the complete nucleotide sequences of the bacteriophage genomes of *P. aeruginosa* strains PB1, SN, 14–1, LMA2, LBL3, YuA, and ϕ PMG1, and conducted a comparative proteomic analysis of ϕ KZ-like, PB1-like, and YuA-like phages. PB1-like phage genomes range from 64 to 66 kbp, with a GC content of 55.5% (lower than that of the host at 66.6%), and contain 88 to 95 open reading frames. For these phages, Miroshnikov proposed a new taxonomic genus, which was ratified by the ICTV in 2011. In the YuA phage (family Siphoviridae, genome size 58,663 bp, GC content 64.3%), two types of promoters (σ^{70} -like) and a nonlinear cluster of lysis genes (Rz/Rz1, holin, endolysin) have been identified. It has been established that ϕ PMG1 (related to the temperate bacteriophage D3) has lost the ability to establish stable lysogeny and may be considered a candidate for therapeutic formulations.

Proteomic analysis of ϕ KZ-like bacteriophages conducted by Miroshnikov identified 62–69 structural proteins, including a multisubunit RNA polymerase (subunits gp80, gp178, gp180) associated with the virion – an unprecedented phenomenon among bacteriophages. The viral chaperonin ELgp146 was described for the first time, exhibiting a mechanism distinct from GroEL: ATP-dependent dissociation of heptameric rings leading to the formation of a single-ring intermediate. Crystalline structures of the peptidoglycan-lytic transglycosylase ϕ KZgp144 (2.3 Å resolution), the C-terminal domain of the ϕ KZgp131 tail fibril (1.9 Å), and the central spike protein SNgp43 (1.8 Å) enabled Miroshnikov et al. to propose a “duplicating active center” model for gp144 and to confirm the role of gp43 as a membrane-penetrating apparatus (Miroshnikov, 2013, pp. 30–40).

5.2. Genetic Markers of Phages and Selection Criteria for Phage Therapy

Based on the analysis of more than 60 genomes of *P. aeruginosa* phages, Miroshnikov developed a PCR system for the rapid classification of isolated phages into taxonomic groups. Primers were designed targeting the conserved genes of the major capsid proteins. Testing of commercial preparations of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* bacteriophages (produced in Nizhny Novgorod and Perm) revealed that all samples contained KMV-like phages (Podoviridae), while two samples from Perm additionally contained ϕ KZ-like phages (Myoviridae). Neither temperate nor transposon phages were detected, indicating that the quality of the preparations is satisfactory (Miroshnikov, 2013, pp. 44–46).

A key selection criterion is the absence of integrase genes and proteins containing the FtsK_γ domain. Kazantseva O. A. (2024) demonstrated that the small terminase subunit of phage Sam46 possesses an additional N-terminal FtsK_γ domain homologous to bacterial SpoIIIE/FtsK proteins. It is hypothesized that this domain may promote erroneous packaging of bacterial DNA into procapsids (generalized transduction), which is undesirable for therapeutic phages. Temperate phages Kirov and B13 harbor genes encoding site-specific integrases and are not recommended for use in phage therapy (Kazantseva, 2024, pp. 20–22).

6. The Role of Bacteriophages in Horizontal Gene Transfer and Evolution

Bacteriophages represent a powerful factor in bacterial evolution. Aslanov B. I. (2016) noted that in hospital settings, up to 78–90% of phages isolated alongside their host bacteria from the same biotope do not lyse their own strain but remain in an equilibrium interaction. The majority of these phages are temperate, and their genomes contain virulence genes. For example, among *P. aeruginosa* strains, the *ctx* gene (encoding a cytotoxin) was detected in 21.8% of isolates from the intensive care unit and in 96.4% from the surgical department; in *S. aureus*, the *sea* gene (enterotoxin A) was present in 66.6% of nosocomial strains, whereas the *tst* gene (toxic shock syndrome toxin) was found in 21.6% (Aslanov, 2016, pp. 21–25). Strains carrying prophage genes exhibit significantly higher antibiotic resistance (odds ratio for *E. coli* with the *s2418* gene ranging from 4.8 to 5.9).

Lysogenic conversion is not merely a theoretical phenomenon. Aslanov provides specific data: among wounded patients infected with *P. aeruginosa* harboring the *ctx* gene, HAIs developed at a rate of 31.2 per 100 individuals, compared to only 9.6 cases in those without this gene. A similar pattern is observed with *S. aureus* carrying the *sea* gene: 27.3 versus 8.8. Aslanov also calculated the correlation between the number of temperate phages in the inpatient setting and the frequency of HAI, which was found to be high: for staphylococci, $r = 0.86$; for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, $r = 0.75$. This constitutes a substantial argument supporting the influence of phages on the epidemiological process.

Kazantseva O. A. (2024) and Piligrimova E. G. (2024) expanded these concepts by demonstrating that temperate phages of the *Bacillus cereus* group may exist as plasmid prophages and harbor genes influencing sporulation and nucleic acid metabolism. Genes encoding thioredoxin, thymidylate kinase, ribonucleotide reductase, as well as six lipoproteins with signal sequences potentially involved in superinfection exclusion, have been identified. These data underscore that even temperate phages, regarded as safe in terms of pathogenicity, can unpredictably modify bacterial properties.

7. Technological Aspects of Bacteriophage Production and Stabilization

The success of the biotechnological application of phages depends on optimizing their cultivation, purification, and stabilization.

7.1. Nutrient Media and Cultivation Regimes

Funkner E. V. (2007) and Kiseleva I. A. (2015) demonstrated that the use of a casein-acid medium (casein hydrolysate with a degree of hydrolysis 0.6–0.7, multivitamin complex) enables obtaining phage lysates with Gratiatiters of 10^9 – 10^{11} PFU/ml and a 5–6-fold decrease in ballast substances compared to Marten broth and meat-peptone broth. Separate cultivation of monophages followed by mixing in equal volumes ensures that the specific activity of each component is not lower than 10^{-5} according to Appelman. The optimal multiplicity of infection varies from 0.2–0.4 (phage En-2) to 5.3–6.4 (phage En-13) and 2.2–10 (most other phages).

7.2. Removal of Endotoxins and Exotoxins

For the removal of lipopolysaccharides (endotoxins) from phage lysates, Kiseleva employed EndoTrap Blue and EndoTrap HD affinity columns (Hygios, Germany). This allowed the reduction of endotoxin concentration to a safe level (less than 10 EU/ml). The absence of exotoxins (staphylococcal enterotoxins, Shiga-like toxins) was confirmed using the immunoenzymatic test systems RIDASCREEN and RIDA®QUICK.

7.3. Encapsulation and Stabilization

Encapsulation is applied to protect phages from the acidic environment of the stomach and to enhance the product's shelf life. Schubert et al. (2022) successfully encapsulated phages in alginate microcapsules with the addition of milk proteins, providing 100% survival in a gastric juice model (pH 2.0, 2 h). Xu et al. (2025) demonstrated that the K57-specific phage of *K. pneumoniae* effectively sanitizes milk and disrupts biofilms. Choi et al. (2023) proposed a spray-drying method employing maltodextrin (11%) and trehalose (4%), which ensures the preservation of phage activity during extended storage.

Conclusions and Findings

In summarizing the analysis of domestic and international studies presented in dissertation abstracts, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Bacteriophages are highly specific antibacterial agents. They are capable of lysing antibiotic-resistant strains, including MRSA, carbapenem-resistant *K. pneumoniae*, and *P. aeruginosa*. Clinical data obtained by Aslanov B. I. (2016) and Khairullin I. N. (2004) confirm that phage therapy reduces the incidence of nosocomial infections by 40–80% and decreases wound healing duration by 3–5 days.

- New phage-containing products have been developed. This comprises a specialized dietary preventive nutrition product, «Foodphage» (Kiseleva I. A., 2015), and a complex formulation, «Sextaphage», available in liquid form and suppositories (Funkner E. V., 2007). These products employ advanced purification and encapsulation technologies, ensuring safety and extended stability.

- Phage proteins represent an independent value. Recombinant depolymerases Dep_kpv74 and Dep_kpv79, investigated by Solovyova E. V. (2018), demonstrate

an «antivirulent» effect by degrading the *K. pneumoniae* capsule and increasing animal survival rates by 65–80% without exerting direct bactericidal activity. Endolysins ϕ KZgp144 and ϕ KZgp181, characterized by Mirosnikov K. A. (2013), exhibit high thermostability and broad substrate specificity, representing promising enzybiotics for combating Gram-negative bacteria.

- Phage-based diagnostics remain effective. Phage collections for enterobacteria developed by Zolotukhin S. N. (2007) enable the reduction of analysis time from 96–120 to 18–48 hours. Electro-optical and electroacoustic methods proposed by Makarikhina S. S. (2013) allow detection of phages and bacteria within 5–10 minutes, with sensitivity ranging from 10^4 to 10^5 particles/ml.

- Genomics and proteomics constitute the foundations of design. K. A. Mirosnikov (2013), O. A. Kazantseva (2024), and E. G. Pilgrimova (2021) demonstrated that whole-genome sequencing of phages enables the identification of novel taxa (the genera Pushchinovirus, Bembunaquatrovirus, Samaravirus, among others), the characterization of unique molecular mechanisms (chaperonin ELgp146, RNA polymerase ϕ KZ, FtsK_γ domain of terminase), and the development of PCR assays for the quality control of phage preparations.

- Safety necessitates the use of virulent phages. A critical requirement is the exclusive use of virulent phages that do not harbor integrase genes, toxins, or antibiotic resistance determinants. Temperate phages (including plasmid prophages) may facilitate horizontal gene transfer and lysogenic conversion, thereby enhancing the pathogenic potential of bacteria (Aslanov B. I., 2016; Kazantseva O. A., 2024).

Recommendations for further research

Based on the conducted analysis and in light of current trends, several directions for future investigations are proposed. Especially among these is the development of novel food formulations for phage delivery aimed at the selective elimination of opportunistic pathogenic enterobacteria.

1. Expansion of collections of capsule-specific virulent phages.

Based on the data of Solovyova E. V. (2018) regarding the high prevalence of hypermucooid strains of *K. pneumoniae* belonging to capsular types K1, K2, and K57 in Russian clinical settings and their multidrug resistance, it is imperative to continue the search for new phages specific to the predominant capsular types. Particular attention is directed towards phages exhibiting polysaccharide depolymerase activity: as demonstrated by Solovyova, recombinant depolymerases (Dep_kpv74, Dep_kpv79) efficiently degrade the capsule and enhance animal survival without exerting direct bactericidal effects.

2. Development of combined food products for targeted modulation of the microbiota.

The experience of I. A. Kiseleva (2015) with Foodphage and E. V. Funkner (2007) with rectal suppositories Sextaphage demonstrates that phage-containing

products can be effective in the prevention of intestinal infections. However, both of these products are liquid formulations. An alternative may be confectionery products with low water activity, particularly chewable marmalade. Due to low humidity (less than 22%) and $a_w < 0.6$, it provides prolonged stability of the encapsulated phages. Encapsulation technologies proposed by Schubert et al. (2022) for alginate microcapsules and by Choi et al. (2023) for spray drying with maltodextrin and trehalose can be adapted for the preparation of phage-containing marmalade. In our subsequent studies, we plan to develop and experimentally validate the use of chewable marmalade containing a cocktail of capsule-specific bacteriophages targeting *K. pneumoniae* for the selective elimination of this pathogen from the intestine. Unlike liquid formulations, marmalade does not require a cold chain for short-term storage, is convenient for dosing, and exhibits high organoleptic properties; this is important for prolonged prophylactic use in at-risk groups (patients following antibiotic therapy, immunocompromised individuals).

3. Optimization of phage encapsulation methods in food matrices.

To protect phages from the acidic environment of the stomach and to ensure their release in the small intestine, continued investigation of combined encapsulation systems is necessary. The successful application of alginate-protein microcapsules by Schubert et al. (2022) and spray drying by Choi et al. (2023) can be complemented by the use of food hydrogels (pectin, chitosan) and liposomes. Regarding chewing marmalade, it is essential to select phage administration parameters (temperature, pH, mixing) that do not diminish their lytic activity. It is also necessary to assess the stability of phages within the marmalade matrix over the entire shelf life (12–18 months).

4. Preclinical evaluation of the efficacy of phage-containing marmalade.

A series of *in vitro* experiments (modeling gastrointestinal transit, evaluation of phage release in the intestinal environment, assays on susceptible *K. pneumoniae* strains of various capsule types) and *in vivo* studies using murine models of intestinal colonization are planned. Capsule-specific phages described by Solovyova may serve as prototypes – KpV71 (K1-specific), KpV74 (K2-specific), and KpV79 (K57-specific). Oral administration of the marmalade preparation is expected to result in a statistically significant reduction in the titer of *K. pneumoniae* in fecal matter and intestinal tissues without disturbing the normal microbiota.

5. Development of regulatory documentation for phage-containing confectionery products.

Drawing on the experience of I. A. Kiseleva (2015) in the registration of ‘Food-phage’ as a specialized dietary prophylactic product, it is necessary to prepare technical specifications (TS) and technological instructions (TI) for chewing marmalade containing bacteriophages. Key controlled parameters: phage particle titer (no less than 10^6 PFU/g), absence of endo- and exotoxins, and stability during storage.

6. Study of the ‘antivirulent’ effects of phages and their enzymes.

The work of Solovyova E. V. (2018) demonstrates that, even in the absence of bacterial cell lysis, the recombinant depolymerase Dep_kpv74 can facilitate the cleansing of mice by degrading the capsule followed by phagocytic elimination. Whole phages (for lysis) and recombinant depolymerases (for ‘neutralizing’ the capsule) can be combined in chewing marmalade, potentially producing a synergistic effect. The investigation of such combined effects constitutes a promising area of research.

7. Monitoring phage resistance and horizontal gene transfer.

As noted by Aslanov B. I. (2016), predominantly temperate phages circulate in hospital settings, facilitating lysogenic conversion. In the development of phage-containing marmalade, only virulent phages that have undergone genomic sequencing to exclude integrase, toxin, and antibiotic resistance genes should be used. It is also necessary to consider the rotation of phages in the cocktail to reduce the risk of the emergence of phage-resistant mutants.

8. Expansion of the spectrum of target pathogens.

The successful chewable gummy technology can also be adapted for other conditionally pathogenic bacteria colonizing the intestine – for example, for enterohemorrhagic *E. coli* (as in Kiseleva’s Foodphage) or for *Clostridioides difficile*. This opens broad prospects for the development of a range of functional ‘phagebiotic’ products with defined specificity.

Conclusion

In summary, it should be emphasized that bacteriophages hold a central position in modern biotechnology. They integrate fundamental research on molecular mechanisms with applied developments aimed at addressing challenges related to antibiotic resistance, food safety, and human health. An interdisciplinary approach – encompassing genomics, proteomics, materials science, and clinical medicine – will enable a significant expansion in the arsenal of phage-based agents and their components in the coming years.

A particularly promising avenue is the development of functional food products (notably, chewable marmalade) containing encapsulated bacteriophages for precise modulation of the microbiota and prevention of infections caused by opportunistic enterobacteria. This very idea will form the basis of our subsequent experimental work.

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PROBIOTICS AND POSTBIOTICS AS PROMISING COMPONENTS OF FUNCTIONAL FOODS

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Abstract. *This article examines probiotics and postbiotics as components of functional foods. The topicality of the subject is linked to the growing interest in the role of gut microbiota in maintaining human health, as well as the need to develop products capable of exerting additional beneficial effects on the organism. Probiotics are defined as live microorganisms whose effects depend on the maintenance of viability, whereas postbiotics are regarded as metabolites and structural components of microbial cells that exhibit greater technological resilience. A comparative analysis of probiotics and postbiotics was conducted based on scientific literature, along with consideration of their prospective applications in the development of functional and specialized food products.*

Keywords: *probiotics, postbiotics, gut microbiota, functional foods, metabolites, lactic acid bacteria, food technologies, biotechnology.*

Currently, increasing attention is being devoted to the role of gut microbiota in human health. Microorganisms involved in the digestive process and their influence on the regulation of immunity and the intestinal mucosa are considered. Disruption of the microbial composition can lead to digestive disorders, inflammatory processes, and impair the body's immune response to infectious challenges.

In this context, functional food products become particularly important. These comprise products that not only supply the organism with essential nutrients but also impart additional beneficial effects on specific physiological functions. Such functional products are enriched with biologically active and mineral compounds, dietary fibers, vitamins, probiotics, and postbiotics. Their application is intended

to support health maintenance, regulate gastrointestinal tract function, enhance intestinal protective mechanisms, and reduce the risk of developing dysfunctions.

In this context, there is a growing interest in probiotics and postbiotics, which are intended to support the normal state of the microbiota. Probiotics are live microorganisms that contribute to the maintenance of the microbiota and exert a beneficial impact on human health. However, it has been established that the situation is more complex; it is not sufficient to simply consume a 'magic' probiotic, as their efficacy cannot be universal or uniform for all individuals. The human gut is a complex ecosystem, whose microbiota composition is individual and depends on age, diet, lifestyle, previous diseases, and numerous other factors.

Nevertheless, postbiotics should also be taken into consideration. Postbiotics are inactivated probiotics, including their cellular components and metabolic products, which retain biological activity. These may include various enzymes, peptides, cell wall fragments, organic acids, and other substances of microbial origin. The increased interest in postbiotics is related to their resistance and stability. Being non-living, they do not require special storage conditions to preserve their functionality. Moreover, they are not degraded by gastric juice or intestinal bile.

Therefore, the actions of probiotics and postbiotics are directed towards the restoration of the microbiota; however, they differ in their intrinsic nature and mechanisms of action on the host organism. Probiotics act as viable microorganisms, whereas postbiotics exert their effects via non-living components and metabolites. At the same time, it is not possible to categorically state that some are harmful while others are beneficial. Indeed, addressing this issue requires a comprehensive and integrative approach. It is essential to analyze their fundamental properties, identify similarities and differences, characterize their specific features, understand their bioavailability and impact on human health, and, most importantly, evaluate their prospects for application in the food industry, biotechnology, and preventive nutrition.

Originally, probiotics were defined exclusively as live microorganisms that maintain viability and the capacity for reproduction during transit through the gastrointestinal tract. However, biological activity was subsequently detected even in the absence of viable cells. This led to an extension of the classification.

Probiotics are live microorganisms that, when administered in adequate amounts, can exert beneficial effects on human health. Their primary importance lies in maintaining the normal composition of the intestinal microbiota, regulating digestive processes, and enhancing the protective mechanisms of the human body.

The most commonly used probiotic microorganisms are bacteria of the genera *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium*. Additionally, certain representatives of the genera *Streptococcus*, *Enterococcus*, *Lactococcus*, *Bacillus*, as well as yeast microorganisms such as *Saccharomyces boulardii*, may also be included among such

cultures. However, the beneficial properties of probiotics depend not only on the genus or species of the microorganism but also on the particular strain. Therefore, it is important to consider the selection of cultures when developing probiotic products and preparations.

Probiotic microorganisms employed in food products must be safe for human health, preserve their viability throughout production and storage, and withstand passage through the acidic gastric environment and bile acids. Moreover, they must be capable of reaching the intestine in an active state to successfully multiply therein and exert their beneficial effects.

Despite the beneficial properties of probiotics, their applicability is subject to certain limitations. Their efficacy is linked to the viability of the cells, storage conditions, dosage, the method of administration, as well as the characteristics of the host organism. Changes in temperature or prolonged storage can reduce the number of viable cells in the product, consequently affecting its quality and declared activity.

An example of the application of probiotics in food product development is the study by Serafima Nikolaevna Sazanova titled 'Development of technology for ice cream with probiotic *Saccharomyces boulardii*.' In her dissertation abstract, she considered the potential application of the yeast probiotics *Saccharomyces boulardii* in the development of a functional ice cream product. S. N. Sazanova notes that probiotics are acknowledged components that classify food products as functional [1].

She emphasizes in her work that, in the food industry, bacteria of the genera *Bifidobacterium* and *Lactobacillus* are most frequently employed. However, the use of solely these lactic acid bacteria entails a number of limitations. One of the challenges in the application is the modification of the organoleptic properties of the product, such as the development of a more acidic taste or changes in texture. Therefore, growing attention is directed towards the identification of novel probiotic microorganisms for food production [1].

S. N. Sazanova employs *Saccharomyces boulardii*, which, despite their classification as yeast microorganisms, also exhibit confirmed probiotic properties. These microorganisms are capable of synthesizing organic acids, alcohols, esters, vitamins, antioxidants, amino acids, and enzymes, as well as demonstrating antimicrobial, antitoxic, and immunomodulatory activities [1].

These properties enable us to regard *Saccharomyces boulardii* not only as an alternative but also as a promising candidate for development. In my view, the importance of this study is that the probiotic properties of microorganisms should be assessed not solely based on their taxonomic classification but also according to their functional characteristics. It is essential to consider how it influences the product, its behavior within the human organism, and whether it retains its beneficial properties.

Another example of the application of probiotic microorganisms in the food industry is the work by V. R. Ahmedova's "Development of Technology for

Fermented Milk Ice Cream with Prebiotic Components.” In her author’s abstract, she examines the development of fermented milk ice cream incorporating starter cultures and prebiotic components. A distinctive feature of this work is that it addresses not only the potential for enriching the product with lactic acid microorganisms but also the enrichment with components designed to enhance their survival in the final product [2].

This study emphasizes that products should be not only functional but also possess favorable organoleptic properties. This is particularly important for ice cream, as it is primarily valued for its pleasant flavor, texture, and visual appearance. However, products enriched with probiotics and prebiotics exhibit certain limitations associated with their shelf life, instability of consistency, and increased product acidity following the completion of primary fermentation [2].

V. R. Akhmedova demonstrates that the selection of the probiotic strain and the medium for its cultivation influences the fermentation process, acidity, organoleptic properties, and the microbial load in the final product. Thus, prebiotics in this system fulfill predominantly a technological rather than a nutritional function. Preserving the viscosity of the mixture and the stability of its structure [2].

In my view, this example is significant because it illustrates the dependence of the quality of a probiotic product on the composition of the food matrix. It is insufficient merely to introduce microorganisms into a product and anticipate that it will inherently confer benefits. It is essential to establish conditions that enable probiotics to preserve their viability and functional properties throughout the product’s entire shelf life. In addition, the functional product must also maintain its consumer properties. Even if the product is highly beneficial, poor organoleptic characteristics will render it undesirable to consumers.

While probiotics are associated with the use of live microorganisms, postbiotics constitute a distinct aspect of microbial cultures. Postbiotics are non-living microbial cells, cell components, and their metabolic products that are capable of exerting a beneficial effect on the human body. Their activity is not related to the proliferation of the culture within the intestine but is mediated by substances produced during their metabolic activity.

Interest in postbiotics emerged upon the realization that the beneficial effects of microorganisms do not always depend on their viability. During the growth and metabolic activity of probiotic microorganisms, various compounds are formed that retain their beneficial properties even after cell death. These include organic acids, enzymes with peptides, vitamins, amino acids, polysaccharides, and other components.

Postbiotics should be regarded as the products of probiotic viability and activity. While the probiotic acts as a living cell producing beneficial substances after administration, the postbiotic contains these substances in a pre-formed state.

Therefore, the activity of postbiotics may be more stable and less dependent on the conditions within the human gastrointestinal tract.

A significant advantage of postbiotics is their technological stability. In production, it is not necessary to monitor the viability of microorganisms at all stages of preparation, storage, and consumption of the product. Furthermore, there is no need for constant quantitative control to prevent their levels from being excessively low or high. Postbiotics exhibit greater resistance to heating, pH alterations, drying, and freezing. This characteristic makes them promising for the food product market.

An example of such a product is the study by Irina Mikhailovna Sorokina titled 'Development of Technology and Evaluation of Consumer Properties of Specialized Food Products for Athletes Using Metabolite-Type Probiotics.' Although the author employs the term 'metabolite-type probiotics,' the cell-free filtrates of probiotic cultures examined in the study are essentially analogous to postbiotics, as they contain solely microbial metabolic products and do not rely on the activity of viable cells [3].

This study examines the postbiotic approach from a technical perspective. Cell-free filtrates of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* NK-1 and *Bifidobacterium longum* B 379M cultures served as the basis. Microfiltration was employed to produce these filtrates, enabling the removal of residual viable cells and the acquisition of a safe ingredient [3].

A practical outcome of the research was the development of beverages intended for athlete nutrition. This demonstrates that postbiotics can be used to enrich not only therapeutic and prophylactic dairy products. In this study, a liquid isotonic beverage and a lyophilized beverage were developed [3].

In my opinion, the significance of this example lies in the extensive practical applications of postbiotics. They can be incorporated into those products where the inclusion of viable probiotics would be technologically complex or even unfeasible. Moreover, they enable working with diverse product formats, facilitating the expansion of the product range and its differentiation on the shelf amidst competitors.

Another key reference on this subject is the work by Victoria Alexandrovna Leonova, titled 'Development of Biotechnology for a Fermented Milk Product with a Metabolite Complex of *L. helveticus*.' The author's abstract addresses the development of a fermented milk product utilizing postbiotics from *Lactobacillus helveticus* [4].

The study highlights the utilization of supernatants, which were formerly regarded as waste by-products of bacterial preparation manufacturing. A supernatant is a cell-free liquid that remains after cultivating beneficial bacteria in a nutrient medium and their subsequent removal by centrifugation or filtration. These supernatants contain organic acids, vitamins, amino acids, and other biologically active compounds. This clearly demonstrates the essence of postbiotics: the beneficial component is not the viable cell itself, but the substances it synthesizes during its growth and development [4].

A fermented dairy product was developed with the addition of the metabolic complex of *L. helveticus*. The incorporation of this complex promoted the enhancement of antimicrobial, bifidogenic, and antioxidant properties of the final product. Specifically, V.A. Leonova reports that the addition of 1% of the metabolic complex increased the antioxidant activity of the product by 4.5-fold compared to the control sample [4].

The significance of this study lies in the fact that the postbiotic component is examined not only theoretically but also via a specific technological approach. The author selects a *Lactobacillus helveticus* strain, investigates its antimicrobial properties, cultivation conditions, the composition of its metabolic complex, and the impact of drying methods on the preservation of its functional properties. This underscores the necessity not only of incorporating beneficial substances into products but also of conducting research and testing to substantiate the selection of the microbial strain, cultivation medium, cell separation technique, and stabilization method for the final additive.

Following an analysis of practical examples, the application of probiotics and postbiotics necessitates a more detailed comparison of these groups according to their principal characteristics. Although they share an overall mode of action, probiotics and postbiotics exhibit distinct mechanisms of influence on the human organism, as well as differing technological requirements for the manufacture of products containing them.

To more clearly illustrate the differences between probiotics and postbiotics, it is appropriate to consider their main characteristics in a comparative format. The table provides a summary of the previously discussed material and delineates the circumstances under which the use of live microorganisms is more justified, as well as those in which the application of postbiotic components is more appropriate.

Table 1 – Comparative overview of probiotics and postbiotics

Criterion	probiotics	postbiotics
Nature of the active component	Live microorganisms	Metabolites, cellular components, inactivated cells
Viability	Mandatory	Not required
Main mechanism of action	Activity of live cells and their interaction with the microbiota	Action of pre-formed metabolites and structural components
Storage stability	Lower, dependent on environmental conditions	Higher, as there is no need to maintain viable cells
Resistance to heat	Limited	Higher
Technological control	Monitoring of viable cell counts required	Monitoring of metabolite composition and activity required

Criterion	probiotics	postbiotics
Ability to colonize the intestine	Temporary colonization possible	Absent
Application	Fermented dairy products, dietary supplements, starter cultures, functional foods	Beverages, dry mixes, fermented dairy products, specialized nutrition
Main advantage	Live interaction with microbiota	Stability and technological versatility
Primary limitation	Sensitivity to production and storage conditions	Lack of live metabolic activity post-consumption

It is apparent from the presented table that probiotics and postbiotics should not be regarded as fully interchangeable components. Probiotics are valuable due to their content of live cells capable of metabolic activity and interaction with the gut microbiota. However, this very characteristic also represents a limitation, as it requires preserving the viability of microorganisms throughout all stages of product manufacturing, storage, and consumption.

Postbiotics, conversely, do not possess the ability to reproduce or colonize the intestine; however, this confers greater technological robustness. They can be utilized in products where the use of viable probiotics is hindered by heating, drying, freezing, pH alterations, or extended storage. Therefore, postbiotics are particularly promising for the development of functional products with a more stable composition and predictable properties.

It is advisable not to juxtapose probiotics and postbiotics, but rather to consider them as two distinct approaches for the development of functional food products. Probiotics are justified in products that can preserve microorganism viability and promote their active functionality. Postbiotics are suitable in scenarios where product stability, technological simplicity, and safety are critical. Consequently, both approaches may evolve concurrently and complement one another within food biotechnology.

Thus, the development of functional food products involves not only the search for new biologically active components but also understanding how these components behave within the matrix of a particular product. Probiotics and postbiotics represent promising components for functional food products; however, their effectiveness depends on the appropriate selection of the microorganism, the food matrix, the production technology, and the storage conditions. Their application is driven by the increasing interest in maintaining the normal state of gut microbiota, enhancing gastrointestinal function, and reinforcing the body's defense mechanisms.

The reviewed sources demonstrate that the development of products containing probiotics and postbiotics necessitates a comprehensive approach. It is insufficient merely to enrich a product with beneficial microorganisms or their metabolites.

Consideration must be given to safety, organoleptic properties, compositional stability, shelf life, and industrial applicability. Only through the integration of these factors can a product be both functional and acceptable in taste to the consumer.

Accordingly, probiotics and postbiotics should be regarded as essential instruments in contemporary food biotechnology. Their application enables the expansion of the assortment of functional and specialized products. The prospects of this field lie in the ability to combine health benefits with the demands of food production and the consumer market.

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OBTAINING PHAGE PREPARATIONS AND METHODS FOR THEIR PURIFICATION

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Abstract. *This article addresses the production of bacteriophages, stages of isolation, criteria for assessing the quality of the resulting preparation, as well as its purification methods*

Keywords: *bacteriophages; phage preparations; bacteria; purification methods*

Knowledge about bacteriophages appeared at the beginning of the 20th century when Canadian scientist F. d'Hérelle, conducting experiments with a dysentery bacterial culture, encountered spontaneous destruction of its bacterial cells. He then established that the cause was microorganisms parasitic to bacteria, which he named bacteriophages. In 1921, scientists Bruynoghe and Maisin described a method for treating bacterial skin infections using bacteriophages. Since that time, they have been actively used in medicine.

At present, the scope of phage applications is quite broad: medicine, veterinary medicine, agriculture, and laboratory research. Preparations have been developed for the treatment and prevention of bacterial diseases in humans, animals, and plants. Whole strains have been developed for the identification of bacterial species under laboratory conditions. And recently, efforts have begun to introduce bacteriophages into food production.

Due to the expansion of their application scope, methods for obtaining bacteriophage preparations have been developed. Depending on the objectives, two methods are distinguished: laboratory and industrial, both based on the same process. It consists of several stages:

- Selection of a substrate for the specific phage to be obtained

- Isolation of the bacteriophage
- Purification
- Verification of lytic activity

Figure 1 – general scheme of bacteriophage production

Being viruses of bacteria, bacteriophages exist wherever bacteria live. Therefore, they can be found in large quantities in the environment – in wastewater, soil, as well as in human and animal feces. This fact enables their use as a substrate for phage isolation instead of bacterial cultures.

To obtain bacteriophages from the collected substrate, it is treated either with chemical compounds (for example, mitomycin C) or physical factors (such as ultraviolet radiation). This influences the prophage – the nucleic acid chain previously integrated into the bacterial genotype – present within the bacterium. It separates from the remainder of the gene chain and triggers the process of phage replication and assembly within the cell. Subsequently, the bacterial culture cells are lysed, resulting in a lysate or substrate suspension that must be filtered. Filtration is performed using specialized bacterial filters, such as asbestos plates [1, p.2], which possess sufficiently small pores to prevent bacterial passage.

Then, the purified mixture is evaluated for its ability to lyse bacteria. For this purpose, the spot test and the Graça agar layer method are used [2, p.29].

In the spot test, an agar-based medium is poured into a Petri dish, and after solidification, a bacterial culture susceptible to infection by the grown bacteriophage is spread on the surface. Then, a small drop of the obtained suspension is applied,

and after a period, clear spots appear, indicating the destruction of bacteria at the site where the phage was applied.

Figure 2 – spot test (drop method)

In the Gratia method, meat-peptone agar (MPA) is poured as the first layer into a Petri dish. After solidification, a second layer of semi-liquid agar, pre-mixed with bacterial culture and bacteriophage suspension, is poured on top. Once both layers have solidified, the dish is placed in a thermostat and removed only after 18–24 hours. As a result, due to the growth of the bacterial colony, the upper layer becomes dense, and the plaques formed on it are transparent, allowing the lower layer to be visible. Where spots appeared, lysis occurred as a result of contact with the bacteriophage.

Figure 3 – agar overlay method according to Gracia

In large volumes, bacteriophages are produced by introducing tested bacterial cultures diluted in liquid medium into specialized devices – bioreactors – after which pure bacteriophage strains cultivated in laboratories are added. The introduced phages infect the susceptible colony and then, after replication, lyse the

cells, releasing new phage particles outside. A preservative is added to the obtained mixture, followed by filtration.

The industrial method differs little from the laboratory one, as it involves the same stages. The only difference is in the volume of bacteriophages produced.

Regardless of the method used to obtain the bacteriophage strain, the preparation is tested for several parameters before release: activity, specificity, sterility, safety, and lytic activity [1, p.3].

Sterility is assessed by inoculation on a nutrient medium and incubation in a thermostat at various temperatures. If bacterial or fungal cultures are detected in the preparation after several days, it is not approved for release.

Safety is assessed by administering the strain to animals. If the animals remain healthy for several days, the preparation is considered safe.

Activity and specificity are evaluated simultaneously using the agar layer method of Gratia, as this method is applied both for isolation and for determining the concentration of the bacteriophage in the obtained suspension (filtrate).

Lytic activity is determined by the spot test when the assay is performed on a solid nutrient medium, and by the Appelman method when conducted in liquid. The Appelman method involves preparing several tenfold dilutions of the obtained phage and introducing a specified quantity of these preparations into a fresh bacterial culture. From the entire series of diluted preparations, the titer is considered to be the one which, at the greatest dilution, was able to completely lyse the bacterial cells.

Figure 4 – Appelman method

The production of bacteriophages involves strict compliance with the enumerated criteria, which renders the manufacturing process of phage preparations costly. Failure to meet even one of these criteria results in the rejection of the entire

batch produced. Consequently, the most critical phase in phage isolation is the purification from the growth substrate on which the strain was cultivated, as the subsequent quality of the preparation depends on this step.

Filtration is among the most widely used purification methods. For this purpose, a variety of filters are used, among which the most common are: ceramic candles, asbestos plates, and membrane filters. However, the main drawback is the passage not only of the bacteriophages themselves but also of endotoxins released following bacterial death. Therefore, although the method is widespread, it is not effective, which necessitates repeating the bacteriophage isolation process 5–10 times to achieve maximum purity. Advanced methods for lysate purification currently include centrifugation, chromatography, and precipitation.

Centrifugation is the process of separating a heterogeneous system by generating centrifugal force, whereby heavier particles move downward and lighter particles upward. Ultracentrifugation is employed in the purification of phage suspensions. Ultracentrifugation differs from standard centrifugation in the size of particles present in the mixtures to be separated into components. In suspensions during ultracentrifugation, they are smaller because they consist of organelles from animal and plant cells or viruses (in this case, bacteriophages). Phage suspensions are separated using ultracentrifugation in a cesium chloride (CsCl) gradient [3, p.32]. Solutions of cesium chloride with varying concentrations are prepared to form a gradient, where bacteriophage particles sediment into distinct bands during centrifugation, which are easy to collect. A significant drawback of the method is the mandatory purification of the collected phages due to residual cesium chloride in the resulting preparation, which is toxic because it contains a heavy metal.

Figure 5 – principle of the centrifugation method

Currently, ultracentrifugation in a sucrose gradient is actively applied in practice, and developments continue. The purification procedure is entirely identical to the one followed when working with cesium chloride. Various solutions of different concentrations are also prepared to create a gradient in which phages sediment in bands. The main distinction from cesium gradient ultracentrifugation is the absence of heavy metals. This means that the resulting preparation will have no usage restrictions due to the absence of toxic metal contaminants. This also eliminates the need for expensive and complex methods in subsequent purification stages that would prolong the production process.

The precipitation method is based on the fundamental principle of any precipitation reaction – the formation of a solid precipitate that settles at the bottom as a result of a chemical reaction with the precipitating agent. After completion of the reaction, the solution visually separates into two parts: a precipitate consisting of small crystals or amorphous particles, and a clarified, transparent solution known as the supernatant liquid. Depending on the intended purpose, either the precipitated components or the liquid fraction of the solution are used in subsequent experiments. In the case of the lysate, the pellet is crucial for subsequent steps, as it is the bacteriophages that sediment to the bottom. The most common variant of this purification method is precipitation with diluted polyethylene glycol (PEG) in sodium chloride (NaCl) [3, p.32]. A PEG solution is added to the suspension, the mixture is stirred and left to stand for a while, then centrifuged. The supernatant obtained after these procedures is carefully removed. The process is repeated several times to obtain the purest precipitate, free from unwanted inclusions. A drawback of the method is the prolonged precipitation time, as well as the presence of polyethylene glycol and sodium chloride within the precipitate. Moreover, a substantial amount of lysed bacterial culture residues is observed.

Figure 6 – diagram of solution precipitation

Chromatography is regarded as one of the newest and most advanced methods in this area. It is based on the principle of distributing mixture components between the mobile and stationary phases. Thus, in working with a phage suspension, gel-filtration, anion-exchange, and affinity chromatography are employed.

Affinity chromatography involves passing the bacteriophage suspension through a device column where the phages bind to the surface of the stationary phase, which acts as a sorbent, and are retained in place while the other components pass through. Upon completion of the process, unnecessary components remaining on the sorbent, which are not required for the preparation, are removed, and the bacteriophages are then collected by chemically treating the stationary phase. However, it is noted that the mixture should be subjected to preliminary purification before being placed in the chromatograph, as the yield of the preparation free of extraneous components after this process is very low.

Figure 7 – schematic of affinity chromatography operation, illustrated using proteins as an example

The main component of the anion-exchange chromatograph is positively charged ion-exchange resins, which serve as the sorbent. They attract negatively charged components from the suspension introduced into the column. However, in the absence of prior purification, besides bacteriophages, other particles are also attracted to the resins [4, p. 599]. For example, nucleic acids, which, due to the phosphate groups in their structure, also carry a negative charge. This results in improper purification, where only a small fraction of phages is separated from the bulk mass. Therefore, to obtain a preparation with a high phage titer, the procedure must be repeated until the preparation attains the established concentration values. Furthermore, if ion-exchange resins become exhausted and lose their capability for ionic interaction, they will need to be replaced, which will require considerable time and financial resources.

Figure 8 – schematic of the process occurring in an anion-exchange chromatography column

Size-exclusion chromatography is based on separating a mixture according to the size of the particles within it using a porous gel. It is primarily used when it is necessary to remove components larger than bacteriophages, such as nucleic acids, remnants of lysed bacterial cells, and their structural elements. Although this method is considered outdated, [4, p. 599] it possesses several positive features, distinguishing itself from other chromatographic methods by its low cost and the high stability of the reagents used.

During the study comparing purification methods, it was established that ‘due to the individual characteristics of phages, it is optimal to select the purification method or their combination individually for each phage’ [3, p. 36]. In other words, applying the same method to different types and families of bacteriophages yielded varying purification efficiency results. It is noted that for two bacteriophage families, Myoviridae and Autographiviridae, ultracentrifugation in a sucrose gradient

is a promising method instead of the commonly used cesium chloride. This is due to the absence of traces of toxic heavy metals, which significantly restrict the application scope of preparations. Another advantage is the reduced processing time at this stage of production. If the preparation were produced by centrifugation in a cesium chloride gradient, additional purification by dialysis would be required. This, in turn, would increase the purification time to 18 hours [3, p.35]. Meanwhile, ultracentrifugation in a sucrose gradient effectively preserves the phage titer (concentration) in the resulting lysate and removes endotoxins as efficiently as centrifugation with cesium.

Figure 9 – schematic diagram of the gel permeation chromatography operation

Another approach involved testing five bacteriophages of the same species but differing in morphological features, including size [4]. A methodology was developed involving the sequential application of two lysate purification techniques: first, gel filtration chromatography, followed by anion exchange chromatography. The first stage involved the removal of larger components from the suspension, especially nucleic acids. The second stage involved the direct isolation of bacteriophages. Due to the established system, the final outcome was a phage preparation whose purity exceeded that of preparations purified by gradient ultracentrifugation. This was conditioned by the reduced content of negatively charged components in the lysate, such as DNA and RNA, following the first stage. In the second stage, the phage did not compete with other components of the same charge for the opportunity to bind to the ion-exchange resins, which increased the yield of bacteriophages. Moreover, the combined method proved to be more versatile than centrifugation in a cesium chloride gradient. It is also faster than precipitation with polyethylene glycol, enabling its application for the purification of bacteriophages of various morphologies.

Based on these results, it can be concluded that the purification process of phage preparations constitutes the most costly stage of their production. Both in terms of the time invested and the resources expended. Quite often, purification is performed sequentially by several methods to enhance the purity and concentration of phages in the final preparation. However, this requires appropriate reagents, equipment along with its replaceable components, and over ten hours. This complicates and extends the entire production process. Furthermore, not every method can provide the required quantity of phages in the purified mixture specifically for this type of preparation. This is extremely important in production. Therefore, emphasis is now placed on the development of purification methods that meet the following criteria:

- High phage titer yield
- Minimal time requirements (within a few hours)
- Universality (the method's effectiveness does not decrease when applied to most phages) does not decrease)

In addition, the method's accessibility and simplicity are equally important.

Currently developed methodologies for obtaining concentrated and ultrapure preparations are intended for implementation under laboratory conditions. To date, industrial-scale processes still actively utilize filtration employing bacterial filters or washing with chloroform [1, p. 5], the concentration of which is also strictly regulated. This method is common due to its simplicity and relative cost-effectiveness. Nonetheless, these approaches insufficiently account for the structural and external characteristics of each phage type. As previously mentioned, this subsequently impacts the quality of the preparation.

It is important to note that, irrespective of the substrate selected for cultivating the future preparation, bacteriophage production enterprises utilize pre-existing laboratory strains of pure phages. This results in the formation of purer lysates. Nevertheless, a subsequent purification stage remains necessary, which requires modernization to produce high-quality bacteriophage preparations on a large scale.

In the future, scaling up the production of pure strains in substantial quantities will help resolve the issue of the high cost associated with the application of bacteriophages across various fields. Particularly in food production, where its application is a promising and emerging direction. After all, while phages are actively being utilized in medicine and laboratory research, food enterprises are not yet ready to use them. Only when there is complete confidence that the utilized preparation not only addresses numerous issues related to product storage and raw material processing but is also precisely safe will bacteriophages be able to become an integral part of the food sector. What can be attained through the development of effective purification methods at an industrial scale.

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FACTORS AFFECTING THE GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF LACTOBACILLI

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Abstract. *This article considers the main factors influencing the growth and development of lactobacilli. Nutritional, physico-chemical, and biological conditions that determine the intensity of their cultivation are analyzed. Particular emphasis is placed on the composition of nutrient media, including the use of hydrolysates and unconventional raw materials, as well as the effects of temperature, pH, and inoculum dose on biomass accumulation. It has been demonstrated that optimizing cultivation conditions enhances the viability of lactobacilli and improves their efficiency in biotechnology and the food industry.*

Keywords: *lactobacilli, microbial growth, nutrient media, cultivation, probiotics, hydrolysates, temperature, pH, inoculum, biomass, biotechnology.*

With each passing day, lactobacilli are becoming an integral part of modern science due to their unique biological properties. They are widely utilized in the food industry and medicine and constitute the basis for the production of fermented dairy products and functional nutrition.

Lactobacilli are key representatives of the microbiota and play a significant role in maintaining the microbiological balance of the host organism. Consequently, they are emerging as one of the promising subjects of research. Lactobacilli are Gram-positive anaerobic bacteria that produce lactic acid and, therefore, are classified as lactic acid bacteria. They are widely applied in the food, pharmaceutical, and biotechnology industries [1]. These microorganisms are characterized by their ability to conduct lactic acid fermentation, during which they synthesize not only lactic acid but also other biologically active compounds that play a significant role in maintaining microbial balance [2].

Particular importance lies in the study of factors influencing the growth and development of lactobacilli. The effectiveness of utilizing these strains across various industries depends on their cultivability, the quality of nutrient media, and the influence of external factors. Disruption of this process may adversely impact the results. Consequently, the activity of the cultures and their probiotic efficacy may decline, leading to a deterioration in product quality.

Understanding the growth factors of lactobacilli holds significant practical value. They are utilized in the development and optimization of starter cultures for fermented dairy products, probiotic formulations, as well as in the cultivation of microorganisms under laboratory and industrial conditions.

Thus, it is important to investigate the main factors influencing the growth and development of lactobacilli for their promising applications in contemporary microbiology and biotechnology.

Lactobacilli are a group of Gram-positive microorganisms belonging to the genus *Lactobacillus*. They are among the most widespread and extensively studied representatives of lactic acid bacteria, playing a significant role both in nature and in human physiological functions. They constitute a part of the normal microflora of the gastrointestinal tract. A primary characteristic of lactobacilli is their ability to perform lactic acid fermentation, whereby carbohydrates are converted into lactic acid. This process results in a decrease in the pH of the medium, which inhibits the development of pathogenic microflora. Lactobacilli exhibit pronounced antagonistic activity against opportunistic and pathogenic microflora. This indicates that they create unfavorable conditions for the development of virulent microorganisms owing to their ability to synthesize organic acids that reduce the environmental pH [2]. Lactobacilli can synthesize bacteriocins, enzymes, vitamins, and other biologically active compounds.

Lactobacilli possess remarkable adaptive capability; however, they are sensitive to cultivation conditions. Primarily, representatives of these microorganisms are facultative anaerobes or microaerophiles. The growth characteristics of lactobacilli depend on the composition of the nutrient medium.

The nutrient medium is a crucial component of microbiological research. The nutrient medium is a mixture of substances in liquid, semi-solid, or solid form, comprising natural or synthetic compounds designed to support growth (with or without the inhibition of certain microorganisms), identification, or preservation of microorganism viability [3]. Each laboratory that prepares media for its own use is required to perform regular testing, as ensuring the standardization of nutrient medium preparation is highly challenging [3].

Nutrient media constitute substrates utilized for the cultivation of microorganisms (bacteria, yeasts, fungi, etc.) under laboratory conditions. A wide variety of nutrient media exists, designed for different microorganisms. These media are

categorized into several groups and classified based on composition, initial components, consistency, intended purpose, and other criteria. These classifications will be examined in further detail. Table 1 presents the differences between the substrates across various categories.

Table 1

Classification by composition	Simple media	<p>1) Meat-peptone broth (MPB) – the protein foundation of all media. Several methods exist for the preparation of MPB: a) using meat broth with the addition of commercially available peptone; b) using hydrolysates of the original raw materials obtained through enzymatic hydrolysis.</p> <p>2) Meat-peptone agar (MPA) is prepared by adding agar-agar (1.5–3%) to MPB. If MPA is distributed along the diagonal of a test tube or vial, this is slant agar. If the medium is distributed vertically in a test tube to a height of 5–7 cm, this is column agar. MPA solidified in Petri dishes as a slant is slant agar. If the medium has a vertical layer 2–3 cm high and a diagonal layer of the same size, this is half-slant agar.</p>
	Complex media	Prepared based on simple media with specific additives (carbohydrates, blood, bile, eggs, serum, milk, salts, growth factors, etc.)
Classification by source components	Natural products	<p>These are natural products of animal or plant origin. They can be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plant-based (source materials – soy, peas, potatoes, carrots, etc.). • Animal-based (source materials – meat, fish, eggs, milk, animal tissues, bile, blood serum, etc.). • Mixed (MPA, Levenstein-Jensen medium, etc.).
	Artificial	Contain processed natural products (meat broth, digest), substances obtained from these products (peptone, yeast and corn extracts), and various additives. This is the largest and compositionally most diverse group of media most frequently used. They are prepared according to defined formulations from various infusions or decoctions of animal or plant origin, with the addition of inorganic salts, carbohydrates, and nitrogenous compounds.
	Synthetic	Consist of chemically pure compounds in precisely established concentrations (including carbohydrates, salts, amino acids, vitamins, etc.). Semisynthetic media are obtained by supplementing these media with natural or artificial components.

Classification by Consistency	Liquid Media	Liquid media are predominantly used to study the physiological and biochemical properties of microorganisms, as well as for biomass and metabolite production. They are prepared without agar.
	Semi-liquid Media	Semi-liquid media are typically employed for culture preservation. Containing up to 1% agar
	Solid Media	Solid media are utilized for microorganism isolation, examination of colony morphology, diagnostic purposes, quantitative enumeration, assessment of antagonistic properties, and other applications. With agar concentration of 1.5–2.5%
Classification by intended purpose	Universal	Used for cultivating most microorganisms or employed as a base for preparing specialized media by supplementing with blood, sugar, milk, serum, and other ingredients required for growth of particular microorganism species. This group includes: MPB and MPA.
	Selective	<p>Intended for the isolation and selective cultivation of specific microorganism species that do not grow on simple media.</p> <p>1) Enrichment media – characterized by enhanced nutritional content with added carbohydrates and proteins. These include: blood agar and blood broth; whey broth and whey agar.</p> <p>2) Elective (selective) media – designed for the selective isolation and proliferation of microorganisms of a specific species from materials containing multiple microbial species. These include: selective media; bismuth sulfite agar; egg yolk-salt agar; bile broth; alkaline agar.</p> <p>3) Differential diagnostic media are used to differentiate one species of microorganisms from another based on their enzymatic activity profiles.</p> <p>4) Accumulation media that support rapid growth of specific species of microorganisms.</p> <p>5) Preservative (transport) media. Intended to preserve microorganisms during transportation to the site of analysis. These media contain additives that inhibit microbial proliferation and death, thereby promoting the maintenance of their viability. These include: Tige medium, phosphate-buffered mixture, Kari-Blair media, Amies medium (with and without activated charcoal), and Stuart medium.</p>

In order to select an appropriate nutrient medium for microorganisms, it is necessary to study their cultivation and nutritional characteristics. Due to the production of lactic acid by lactobacilli, selecting a suitable nutrient medium for their growth is challenging. The minimum temperature for the viability of mesophilic species is 10 °C. For thermophilic species, the optimal growth temperature ranges

from 38 to 45 °C, with the minimum being 20 to 22 °C. For their metabolic activity, substrates that serve as sources of energy, as well as compounds necessary for bacterial cell synthesis – such as nucleic acids, polysaccharides, aminosugars, and others – are required [4]. Consequently, the following media are used in the cultivation of lactobacilli:°°°

Table 2

№	Nutrient medium	Characteristics
1	Skimmed milk	Obtained by separating whole milk or by dissolving dry skimmed milk powder in warm water (100 g per 1 L)
2	Hydrolyzed milk	Skimmed milk is diluted with tap water (1 part milk to 2 parts water), then 1 g of dry pancreatin powder or 5 g of pancreas, minced in a meat grinder, is added to 1 L of the diluted milk preheated to 45 °C. A few minutes after the addition of pancreatin to the diluted milk, 5 ml of chloroform is added.
3	Agar with honey	This medium is used for the detection of lactic acid bacteria. Calcium carbonate is added to the nutrient agar at a concentration of 2–3%, after which the medium is sterilized.
4	Sabouraud medium	The basis of this medium is yeast water. To 1 liter of tap water, 20 g of dry yeast are added, boiled for 15 minutes, filtered through a paper filter, dispensed into flasks, and sterilized. To 100 ml of sterile yeast water, 1% peptone, 4% glucose, and 2% agar are added and sterilized.
5	MRS Medium	This medium appears yellow and can be prepared in either solid or liquid form. Media are classified based on agar concentration ranging from 0.075% to 10%. Used for the isolation of acidophilic and lactic acid bacteria.
6	Milk agar	Used to assess the proteolytic activity of microorganisms. 1 to 2 ml of sterile skimmed milk are added to a test tube containing melted sterile nutrient agar, mixed thoroughly, and poured into Petri dishes.
7	Ellinger medium	Used for the general cultivation of streptococci and lactobacilli. Can be either solid or liquid.
8	Trupticase yeast extract glucose medium	A multicomponent medium containing inorganic compounds, yeast extract, and casein hydrolysate.
9	Tomato juice agar	Liquid medium for the cultivation of lactic acid microorganisms. Composed of tomato juice, yeast extract, and casein hydrolysate.

T. A. Raskoshnaya, V. F. Semenikhina, I. V. Rozhkova, and A. V. Begunova, in their study ‘Development of a nutrient medium and cultivation regimes for

Lactobacillus reuteri to obtain a bacterial concentrate,' investigated the effect of technological cultivation parameters of L. reuteri (active acidity, pH 5.6–6.6; cultivation temperature, 32–41 °C; inoculum dose ranging from 3 to 8%) on cell accumulation in the medium. Analysis of the obtained data demonstrated that cultivation on hydrolysate derived from skimmed milk resulted in a higher cell count compared to hydrolysate obtained from whey [5].

The study investigated the effect of various substrates on the cultivation of L. reuteri. Figures 1 and 2 illustrate that increased sucrose content inhibits cell growth in the nutrient medium.

Figure 1 – Dependence of L. reuteri cell number on medium component concentrations at ‘Sucrose’ – 0%

Figure 2 – Dependence of L. reuteri cell count on the concentration of medium components with “Sucrose” at 5%

The optimal nutrient medium composition for cultivating *L. reuteri* was established as follows: hydrolysate 96.75%, yeast extract 3%, and inulin 0.25%. Optimal technological cultivation parameters for *L. reuteri* were determined to be: temperature 37 °C and active acidity (pH) 6.2 units. pH, inoculum dose of 6–7%, and cultivation duration of 6–8 hours. Under these conditions, the cell count reached 2×10^9 CFU/cm³. This study demonstrated that the highest cell count was achieved on a nutrient medium without sucrose.

The highest number of *Lactobacillus reuteri* cells was obtained using the developed nutrient medium composition, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 – Composition of the nutrient medium for optimal cultivation

The authors also conducted a study to determine the optimal temperature and acidity at pH 6.2. Also, under these conditions, a high concentration of cells was observed in the nutrient medium. Figure 4 shows that the optimal temperature for cultivation is 35 and 37 °C.

It was found that cell accumulation occurs within 8–10 hours, and the difference in cell numbers during the stationary growth phase when cultivated at different active acidity values was minimal, ranging from 7.5×10^8 to 1.75×10^9 CFU/cm³. However, the highest number of cells was achieved during cultivation at lower active acidity values within the pH range of 5.8 to 6.2 units. At an active acidity of 5.8 pH units, the highest cell number was 1.5×10^9 CFU/cm³; at 6.0 pH units, it was 1.75×10^9 CFU/cm³, and at 6.2 pH units, 1.4×10^9 CFU/cm³.

Figure 4 – Changes in the cell concentration of *L. reuteri* during cultivation at various temperatures at pH = 6.2 pH units

Figure 5 – Variation in cell concentration during cultivation at different active acidity levels

The highest accumulation of *Lactobacillus reuteri* cells was observed when cultivated in a nutrient medium based on milk hydrolysate, using the proteolytic enzyme Alcalase at a concentration of 3 % relative to the protein content. The optimal medium composition comprised 96.75 % milk hydrolysate, 3 % yeast extract, and 0.25 % inulin, which ensured intensive microbial growth and development. The study of the effects of temperature and active acidity (pH) of the medium established that the most favorable conditions for *L. reuteri* growth are a temperature of 37 °C and pH 6.2. Under these parameters, the cell concentration reached 1.4×10^9 CFU/cm³. Analysis of the effect of the amount of inoculum added on the reproduction process showed that the maximum accumulation of *L. reuteri* cells occurs after 6–8 hours of cultivation with the addition of 6–7 % inoculum, with the cell count reaching approximately 2×10^9 CFU/cm³. The highest concentration of *Lactobacillus reuteri* cells (up to 10^{11} CFU/cm³) was obtained by isolating biomass using ultracentrifugation, with the addition of 6 % inoculum.

The analysis conducted established that the growth and development of lactobacilli is determined by a combination of interrelated factors, including the composition of the culture medium, physico-chemical conditions, and the biological characteristics of the microorganisms themselves. It has been demonstrated that lactobacilli exhibit high requirements for nutrients, particularly carbohydrates, nitrogen-containing compounds, vitamins, and minerals, which necessitates the use of complete and balanced culture media.

Factors such as temperature and medium acidity are of particular importance. It has been established that optimal cultivation conditions (a temperature of approximately 37 °C and a mildly acidic medium) ensure maximal accumulation of cellular biomass and high metabolic activity. The inoculum dose and cultivation duration also play a critical role, as they influence the growth intensity of microorganisms.

It has been demonstrated that employing modern approaches, including the use of hydrolysates and unconventional raw material sources, significantly improves the efficiency of lactobacilli cultivation. Such media stimulate the growth and development of microorganisms, increase biomass yield, and broaden the potential for their practical application.

The study of lactobacilli growth factors holds significant practical importance. The obtained data are employed in the development of probiotic formulations, the creation of starters for the food industry, and the optimization of biotechnological processes. The correct selection of cultivation conditions enables enhanced bacterial viability, resilience, and biological activity.

Future research prospects are linked to the search for new highly efficient strains of lactobacilli, the investigation of their physiological characteristics, and the development of innovative nutrient media and cultivation technologies.

Special emphasis will be placed on utilizing alternative raw materials and creating functional products with targeted properties.

Therefore, the study of factors affecting the growth and development of lactobacilli represents an important area of modern microbiology and biotechnology, with both theoretical and practical significance.

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TOTAL WATER CONTENT OF ADOLESCENT STUDENTS OF A SPORTS UNIVERSITY DURING HIGH SOLAR ACTIVITY

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Abstract. *This article, based on data from the Tanita BC – 545N body composition analyzer and morphological data calculated using simple anthropometric measurements according to Watson P. E., presents findings on the total body water content in adolescent students enrolled at the Institute of Physical Culture of Tyumen State University. The study found that with increasing chronological age of the young men, the total body water content gradually and imperceptibly decreases, having practically no effect on the functioning of physiological systems or their health. During periods of high solar activity (geomagnetic storms – GMA), lasting from several hours to several days, the percentage of water content in the body does not change. 22.6% of the students reported experiencing certain discomfort. It was concluded that the percentage of water content in adolescent students remains stable, which indicates a well-planned training process with regular health monitoring.*

Keywords: *adolescent male athletes, high solar activity, total body water content.*

In contemporary sports, it is crucial to conduct proper medical supervision of the athlete's functional state at various stages of their training and competitive preparation. It is well established that water is contained in all biological fluids of the human body – in blood, lymph, cerebrospinal fluid, bile, gastric juice, synovial fluid of the joints, etc. d., as well as internal organs. Physical loads of varying duration and intensity uniquely influence both the functional state of the human body and its morphological state, including its body composition [Sattarov A. E. et al., 2015], in particular, water content. It should be especially noted that the study of human body composition has received significant and deserved attention from domestic researchers [Bashkirov P. N. et al., 1968; Martirosov E. G. et al., 2006; Nikolaev D. V. et al., 2009; Rudnev S. G. et al., 2014].

In the available medical and pedagogical literature, there are no scientific and practical studies elucidating the percentage of water content in adolescent sports university students during periods of high solar (geomagnetic) activity. It should be noted that in recent years, increasing attention has been given to the study of the nature of high solar activity, the frequency of geomagnetic storm influences on the Earth, and human responses to intense solar radiation [Efremova A. I. et al., 2025; Nikberg I. I., 2014; Parfenova A. A. et al., 2024].

Research objective: using measurements from the Tanita BC – 545N body composition analyzer and morphological data, to calculate the water content in the bodies of adolescent sports students during the peak of geomagnetic activity.

Materials and Methods

On a voluntary basis, 36 males aged 18 to 22 years (19.6 ± 0.8), students of the Institute of Physical Culture at Tyumen State University, were examined in October and November 2025. The male adolescents possessed the qualifications of Master of Sport (MS) of the Russian Federation, Candidate Master of Sport (CMS), and First Sports Category.

Total body water (TBW) in the male adolescents was examined, firstly, using the Tanita BC-545N body composition analyzer scales, and secondly, by the formula [Watson P. E., 1980]:

$$TBW = (0.09156 \times \text{Age (years)}) + (0.1074 \times \text{Height (cm)}) + (0.3362 \times \text{Weight (kg)}) - 2.447,$$

where: TBW – total body water; Age – years; Height – height (cm); Weight – body mass (kg).

Body length was measured using the stadiometer proposed by us (RF Patent for Utility Model No. 153076) with an accuracy of up to 0.5 centimeters. Body weight was measured using beam balance scales with an accuracy of up to 50 grams.

We learned about GMA from the mass media.

The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles outlined in the Helsinki Declaration and European Community Directives (8/609EC), with the verbal consent of the adolescent males.

Results and Discussion

The study results showed (Table 1) that the body length of 18-year-old adolescent males is 178.93 ± 1.02 cm, while body weight is 69.8 ± 0.92 kg. In 22-year-old males, these values were 178.43 ± 1.03 cm (a decrease of 0.42 cm) and 72.2 ± 1.01 kg (an increase of 2.4 kg), respectively.

Table 1. Body height and body mass of male athletes (M±m)

Age, years	Body height, cm	Body mass, kg
18	178.93±1.02	69.8±0.92*
19	178.78±1.04	70.2±0.94
20	178.66±0.96	70.7±1.01
21	178.57±0.98	71.5±1.04
22	178.43±1.03	72.2±1.01**

Note: * and ** indicate statistically significant differences at $p < 0.05$

It can be noted that an important indicator of physical development – body height – in the adolescent males we studied does not differ from the average height of their peers from other countries. Specifically, the average height (Fig. 1) of Chinese men is 170 cm; Spanish, 173 cm; French, 176 cm; Israeli, 177 cm; Russian, 177.2 cm; Dutch, 178.7 cm; German, 178.9 cm; Czech, 180.3 cm; Latvian, 181 cm; and Danish, 183 cm.

Fig. 1. Average height (body length) of men from various countries worldwide.

As for body mass in adolescent males, it increased during the period from 18 to 22 years but in absolute values remained lower than that of men (Fig. 2) from the USA (88 kg), Kuwait (86 kg), Croatia (86 kg), Austria (85 kg), the United Kingdom (84 kg), Germany (82 kg), Canada (80 kg), and Chile (77 kg), yet higher than that of men from Brazil (73 kg) and Yu. Korea (69 kg), Japan (61 kg), Vietnam (58 kg), Bangladesh (56 kg).

Fig. 2. Average body weight of men from various countries.

Based on the conducted study, it can be concluded that the calculated values of total body water in adolescent males during GMA increased slightly with age (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Calculated values of total body water in adolescent males during GMA.

Thus, from 18 to 22 years of age, the percentage of water content increased by 1.12%. Consequently, during the brief adolescent period, total body water content does not undergo significant changes.

As for the percentage of water relative to total body mass in male adolescents, measured by the Tanita BC – 545N body composition analyzer (Fig. 4), it remained stable during GMA and was dependent solely on chronological age.

Fig. 4. Percentage of water content in male adolescents measured by the Tanita BC – 545N analyzer.

Stable values of percentage water content, obtained by various methods, are considered by us to be a reliable indicator that, firstly, allows the training process to be carried out without compromising the athletes' health. Secondly, which we regard as particularly important, is the well-structured, long-term planning of the training process before entering university, which contributes to maintaining the stability of the internal environment of the adolescent organism.

Based on the study conducted, the following conclusions can be made:

1. During the training process, to determine the water content in an athlete's body, in addition to the use of equipment, a calculation method can be applied, enabling prompt and fairly accurate monitoring of water content as a component of the body's composition at the time of examination.

2. The percentage of water content in adolescent students remains consistently stable, indicating a carefully designed training regimen with regular monitoring of health status.

3. A high level of solar activity in the form of GMA, firstly, does not influence the total body water content in students of adolescent age. Secondly, throughout the entire adolescent age period, the total body water content remains practically unchanged.

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ORAL HYGIENE FOR PATIENTS USING ALIGNERS

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Abstract. *The prevalence of individuals with malocclusion utilizing aligners increases annually. Numerous researchers underscore the significance of oral hygiene. The prevalence of individuals with malocclusion utilizing aligners increases annually. Numerous researchers underscore the significance of oral hygiene. When using aligners, comprehensive oral hygiene management is necessary. It is recommended to use various mouth rinses intended for the treatment and prevention of dental caries and periodontal diseases. Currently, the literature indicates*

that disinfection in dentistry involves the use of mechanical, physical, chemical, and biological agents. It has been established that an optimal combination of active ingredients in the formulation can create a disinfectant that exhibits all actions corresponding to the majority of the specified requirements.

Keywords: *aligners, oral hygiene, periodontitis, diseases of the oral mucosa.*

In modern times, oral hygiene undeniably plays an essential role in the prevention of various diseases affecting periodontal tissues and teeth. Mechanical cleaning of the dental rows exerts a beneficial effect by removing soft dental deposits, food debris, microorganisms, desquamated epithelial cells, and by providing gingival massage. The use of toothpastes containing biologically active components facilitates a therapeutic and preventive effect in the care of the oral cavity. However, oral hygiene in individuals using aligners is fundamentally different [5].

The prevalence of individuals with malocclusion utilizing aligners increases annually. Numerous researchers underscore the significance of oral hygiene. Thus, there are numerous studies confirming the necessity of proper care for aligners, as well as addressing their bacterial contamination. Accumulation of dental plaque is observed, located in the most difficult-to-clean retentive areas, along with inflammatory processes of the soft periodontal tissues – these are complications associated with aligners. This adverse factor may also affect the condition of the oral mucosa [1].

However, the authors' opinions diverge regarding the significance of hygienic care for aligners. Some researchers suggest that inflammation of the oral mucosa in people using aligners may result from poor hygiene in their care. This is because 'food debris, under poor oral hygiene, does not remain an inert mass but transforms into a nutrient medium for numerous microbes that cause pathological conditions of the mucous membrane' [7].

According to V. Yu. In many instances, stomatitis in Courland is caused by intolerance to plastics ('acrylic stomatitis'), where the periodontal tissues beneath dentures become chronically inflamed due to the adverse effect of the microflora contained in the plastic of removable dentures on the mucous membrane. This effect may also be observed during wearing aligners. When using aligners, comprehensive oral hygiene management is necessary. It is recommended to use various mouth rinses intended for the treatment and prevention of dental caries and periodontal tissue diseases [2].

Numerous authors have studied the microflora on removable prostheses fabricated from various polymers: acrylic, vinyl, piacryl, tarmopont, and dentomid. The authors observed a high abundance of diverse microflora on the prosthesis surfaces; therefore, thorough cleaning and disinfection are necessary. Certain bacterial species in the experiment produced an unpleasant odor in the oil, which can partly explain halitosis in some individuals wearing removable prostheses. Literature sources indicate that poor and inadequate oral hygiene involving teeth

and aligners significantly deteriorates the condition of periodontal tissues. Thus, among individuals who maintain regular oral hygiene, visible changes in the soft periodontal tissues were observed in 79.0% of cases, while in the group without such care, these changes were noted in 92.0% [2].

Inadequate oral hygiene and care of prosthetic devices play a significant role in altering the composition of microbial communities, as routine hygienic care of the oral cavity is insufficient to eliminate microorganisms residing on the denture base; therefore, special disinfectant solutions must be used. The primary causes of both systemic and local deterioration in patients using aligners are non-compliance with oral and aligner hygiene protocols and the mistaken belief that dental plaque does not accumulate on the aligners. Clinical observations by researchers have established that dental plaque is resistant to removal by saliva and mouth rinses due to its upper layer being covered with a mucous semi-permeable mucoid gel [8].

Implementing hygiene practices for patients using aligners is necessary, and it is crucial to understand the various types of these procedures. Few patients are aware of the existence of professional hygiene care for orthodontic appliances, which comprises several stages: assessment of the aligner's hygienic condition, motivating the patient to maintain hygiene, removal of deposits and disinfection of the aligner, assistance in selecting hygiene products, and training in hygiene techniques [4].

Patients using aligners should know that there is a wide range of products for prosthesis care, including gels, pastes, liquids, specialized powders for their cleaning and disinfection, as well as storage cases. An essential aspect of aligner hygiene is the adherence to the sequence and comprehensiveness of hygienic procedures. The most optimal and appropriate agents for patients with aligner prostheses are mouth rinses possessing anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and deodorizing properties [3].

Thus, a relationship can be observed between the level of aligner hygiene, oral cavity hygiene, and the formation of dental diseases. To maintain aligners in an appropriate hygienic condition, the use of specialized cleaning agents is required.

At present, various literature sources indicate that disinfection in dentistry is performed by mechanical, physical, chemical, and biological means. Disinfection is a process that reduces the quantity of pathogenic microorganisms, spores, bacteria, and toxins on inanimate objects to a level that does not pose a risk to health. The main requirement for disinfectants and disinfection methods is a high level of virucidal, bactericidal, and fungicidal activity. During the disinfection of dental materials and instruments, no adverse effects should occur, primarily including corrosion of metal instruments or alteration and degradation of the surfaces of dental prosthetic materials [6].

Mechanical disinfection is a method for removing microflora from a prosthesis using mechanical methods. This method is often applied as the initial stage of prosthesis cleaning, removing contaminants from both the internal and external surfaces.

The physical method of disinfection refers to the elimination of microorganisms through the antimicrobial effect of physical disinfecting agents. This method includes the use of ultraviolet radiation, ultrasound, microwave radiation, and similar technologies. Disinfection using microwave radiation is characterized by its antimicrobial activity against both conditionally pathogenic and pathogenic flora inhabiting prostheses. The disinfection effect depends on the power of microwave radiation and the duration of exposure. Numerous experimental studies demonstrate that microwave disinfection does not affect the surface, hardness, or other properties of acrylic plastics and soft lining materials. Vibrational cleaning of dentures is performed using devices whose containers are filled with specialized solutions. The denture is placed into the container, and the vibration mode with a specified frequency is initiated. Vibration causes the detachment of colonies of pathogenic microflora and soft dental plaque. Clinical practice demonstrates that vibrational, ultraviolet cleaning, and disinfection in the microwave field have not gained widespread use among patients due to the lack of appropriate equipment and high cost [4].

Chemical disinfection is the most accessible disinfection method, performed using antiseptic solutions. The effectiveness of such disinfection is ensured by the active ingredients. Particular attention should be paid to the application regimen of the agent, the concentration of the active substance, and the duration of the disinfection effect. The disinfectants employed must possess a broad spectrum of antimicrobial activity, namely to induce the eradication of gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria, yeast-like fungi of the genus *Candida*, etc. Additionally, specific guidelines have been established for such agents: they must not exhibit toxicity to humans or the environment; microbiological activity, encompassing a broad spectrum of bactericidal, virucidal, and fungicidal effects; absence of carcinogenic, teratogenic, and corrosive properties; economic accessibility [6].

Unfortunately, not all agents used in clinical practice possess such properties. However, it has been demonstrated that, with an optimal combination of active ingredients in the formulation, it is possible to develop a disinfectant exhibiting all the actions that meet most of the aforementioned requirements.

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**AGE-RELATED FEATURES OF THE SYSTEMIC INFLAMMATORY
RESPONSE DURING RENAL REPLACEMENT THERAPY
FOR RENAL FAILURE IN CHILDREN**

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Abstract. *Greater instability in the functional activity of thermoregulation centers (a trend toward increased mesora CR, increased amplitude of circadian fluctuations in body temperature) is primarily due to the lower sensitivity threshold of sympathetic nervous system receptors at an early age. A more pronounced effectiveness of intensive complex therapy was identified in children older than 7 years, which we primarily associate with their anatomophysiological maturity, resulting in a more successful restoration of urinary system function in the older age group. The method of assessing Cys C serves as an indicator of the severity of the inflammatory response. This method is more sensitive than the temperature response and directly correlates with the degree of renal and hepatic insufficiency, predominantly in children of early age.*

Keywords: *systemic inflammatory response, hemodialysis period, renal failure, children*

Relevance. Progress in intensive care medicine, enhanced equipment in intensive care units, the introduction into clinical practice of increasingly effective antibacterial agents, as well as novel approaches to hemodynamic, rheocorrective, antioxidant therapy, and respiratory support have led to an increased number of patients surviving ARF. Therefore, the prospects for temporary replacement of lost renal function are highly encouraging. Beginning with primitive methods of removing exo- and endotoxins from the body (phlebotomy, the use of laxatives and

diuretics), efferent medicine has become the most effective approach within the comprehensive treatment of the syndrome of exo- and endogenous intoxication. Renal oliguria is characterized by parenchymal renal failure and may develop due to damage to the kidney parenchyma by various injurious factors. However, in the majority of cases, ARF with oligoanuria is caused by two conditions: acute tubular necrosis and acute interstitial nephritis. Acute tubular necrosis (ATN) is induced by a wide range of factors, including ischemia, sepsis, surgical interventions, pharmaceuticals, plant and animal toxins, and pigments (e.g., myoglobin). Acute interstitial nephritis (AIN) is attributed to a hypersensitivity reaction occurring in the kidneys secondary to exposure to medications. ARF with oliguria in patients admitted to intensive care units typically indicates systemic damage to the organism (sepsis, multiple organ failure, toxic effects of medications, dyes). Renal replacement therapy (RRT) is a set of procedures heterogeneous in structure and fundamental principles, performed to sustain the life of a patient who has lost intrinsic kidney function. Each of these functions can be partially substituted by using dialysis methods. Additionally, the kidney secretes hormones that stimulate hematopoiesis, activates vitamin B12, and regulates blood pressure: these functions can be partially or completely substituted by supplementary pharmacological therapy, whereas the inactivation of excess hormones can only be performed by a normally functioning kidney. Hemodynamic overload, venous congestion, activation of neurohumoral systems, natriuretic peptides, inflammation, endothelial dysfunction, oxidative stress and its influence on cardiac and vascular remodeling, as well as mechanisms of cellular maladaptation, are currently regarded as the primary factors in the pathogenesis of ESRF. Sympathetic stimulation leads to an increase in cardiac contractility through the activation of beta-adrenergic receptors of the heart and an increase in peripheral vascular resistance through the activation of alpha-adrenergic receptors of the blood vessels. Additional vasoconstrictive effects may also be mediated by neurohormonal activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system, in which angiotensin II and vasopressin induce direct vasoconstriction of blood vessels. Direct endothelial dysfunction can also profoundly alter vascular reactivity by activating endothelial oxidative stress, whereby cytokine release generates reactive oxygen species that directly contribute to the scavenging of nitric oxide (NO), thereby limiting vasodilation capacity. These effects are systemic, affecting both arterial and venous vessels, and promote increased mobilization of central blood volume. This mechanism aligns with the current pathophysiological understanding of hemodynamic disturbances, wherein an increase in pulmonary artery pressure may be detected several days to weeks prior to an episode of ESRF. **Cystatin C (Cys C)** – a reliable laboratory marker for the early diagnosis of renal function impairment and for assessing glomerular filtration rate (GFR). Unlike creatinine, the blood level of cystatin C is less influenced by age, sex, muscle mass,

and diet, making it a more sensitive marker for early renal failure [1–7]. Given the lack of sufficient data, we undertook an investigation to study and evaluate the age-related characteristics of the systemic inflammatory response during renal replacement therapy in children with renal failure.

Aim of the study. To study and evaluate age-related characteristics of the systemic inflammatory response during renal replacement therapy in children with renal failure.

Materials and methods. Monitoring data of body temperature, hemodynamics, and respiratory system were analyzed in 14 children with diseases complicated by renal failure during the oligoanuric phase. Comprehensive intensive therapy included, alongside etiopathogenetic treatment, prosthetic support of the respiratory and urinary systems' functions.

Table 1. Characteristics of the patients.

Groups	Age, years	Number of HD sessions	ICU treatment duration, days
1 (4 months – 2 years 6 months)	0.8±0.4	11.0±7.0	14.2±12.2
2 (7–18 years)	13.9±3.2	6.0±1.7	9.0±2.8

Continuous hourly monitoring was conducted in two age groups. Group 1 included children aged 0.8±0.4 years, comprising 3 boys and 3 girls. In group 2, patient examination data were studied for individuals aged 13.9±3.2 years, including 1 boy and 7 girls. In group 1, all children were diagnosed with pneumonia: focal – 2 cases, polysegmental – 1 case, bilateral pneumonia complicated by sepsis, MODS, acute kidney injury in the oligo-anuric stage – 3 cases, hemolytic-uremic syndrome – 1 case, toxic-metabolic encephalopathy – 3 cases, and acute respiratory failure grades 2–3 – 5 cases. Medical background in 4 children: polycystic kidney disease, congenital nephrotic syndrome, nephromegaly, acute renal failure (ARF) in the convalescence stage. In group 2 – systemic lupus erythematosus – 3, pneumonia – 6, sepsis – 3, rhabdomyolysis complicated by ARF – 1, acute nephritis – 1, chronic renal failure (CRF) in the exacerbation stage – 6, multiple organ dysfunction syndrome (MODS) – 2, congenital anomaly – solitary kidney – 1. All patients underwent Extracorporeal Blood Purification (ECP). The age-related difference was evident in the duration of comprehensive intensive therapy: patients in Group 1 remained in the ICU for an average of 14.2±12.2 days, which was 43% longer than in Group 2 (Table 1). Patients in Group 1 underwent 11±7 sessions, whereas Group 2 had 6±1.7 sessions, representing 45% fewer. In all patients, the CYSC parameter was assessed within the first 2 days.

Results and Discussion. The observed differences in the duration of intensive therapy, trajectory of condition severity, and clinical-functional examination data

indicated comparatively more effective comprehensive intensive therapy in Group 2, which we attribute primarily to anatomical and physiological maturity that facilitated more successful restoration of urinary system function in older children.

Fig. 1. Dynamics of mesora CR body temperature in degrees Celsius.

Changes in mesora CR body temperature were characterized by fluctuations, with the fluctuation level 0.15–0.3° higher in Group 1 than in Group 2 over the course of 20 days. The observed fluctuation within the subfebrile range of the temperature response indicated insufficient effectiveness of anti-inflammatory therapy in Group 1 (Fig. 1).

Table 2. Mean values of the amplitude-phase structure of circadian rhythm (CR) of body temperature.

	Mesor	At the acrophase	At the bathyphase	Amplitude	Daily fluctuations
Group 1, 10 days	36.9±0.1	37.3±0.2*	36.7±0.1	0.4±0.1	0.6±0.2
Group 2, 10 days	36.8±0.1	37.0±0.1	36.6±0.1	0.2±0.1	0.4±0.2
Group 1 (11–37 days)	36.8±0.1	37.2±0.2*	36.6±0.1	0.3±0.1	0.6±0.2
Group 2 (11–13 days)	36.7±0.1	37.0±0.2	36.5±0.03	0.3±0.1	0.5±0.2

* – difference is statistically significant relative to the mesor value

A statistically significant difference in body temperature during the acrophase was observed within the first 10 days and throughout 37 days in children of Group 1 by 0.4 °C ($p < 0.05$). In contrast, in older patients, the difference in the acrophase parameter showed a tendency to increase by 0.2 °C ($p > 0.05$) (Table 2). The amplitude of diurnal fluctuations was most pronounced during the first 10 days in group 1, amounting to 0.4±0.1 °C.

Fig. 2. Circadian rhythm of temperature (first 10 days).

Fig. 3. Circadian rhythm of temperature (days 11–37).

The mean values of diurnal temperature fluctuations during the first 10 days were 36.9 ± 0.1 °C in group 1 and 36.8 ± 0.03 °C in group 2 (Fig. 2), while during days 11 to 37 they were 36.8 ± 0.03 °C in group 1 and 36.7 ± 0.1 °C in group 2 (Fig. 3). The acrophase projection was shifted in group 1 by 10 hours counterclockwise, whereas in group 2, the acrophase was observed at 19 hours during the first 10 days.

Fig.4. Amplitudes of the circadian rhythm of body temperature.

Fig.5. Daily range of temperature fluctuations

A comparatively more pronounced tendency toward increased amplitude of the circadian rhythm of body temperature in group 1 reflects greater instability in the

functional activity of thermoregulation centers, primarily attributable to a lower sensitivity threshold in early age (Fig.4). The daily fluctuations in body temperature were also more marked in group 1 (Fig.5). Consequently, alongside the selection of more effective etiotropic antibacterial therapy, the heightened sensitivity, functional lability, exhaustion, and vulnerability characteristic of young children should be taken into consideration. Alongside comprehensive anti-inflammatory therapy, the appropriateness of sedative stress-protective correction is established, up to and including initiation of invasive mechanical ventilation (IMV) or non-invasive ventilation (NIV). Management of this patient population is complicated by the presence of chronic infection and systemic inflammatory response in the majority of children, who had previously undergone repeated and prolonged courses of antibacterial and anti-inflammatory therapy. Due to insufficient efficacy, this led to the chronification of inadequately controlled acute disease.

Fig. 6. Correlation of CysC with blood elements.

Fig. 7. Correlation of CysC with plasma biochemical parameters

Significant age-related differences in correlation patterns of CysC were identified between groups 1 and 2. In group 1, a direct correlation of CysC was found with leukocyte count (0.82), band neutrophils (0.9), segmented neutrophils (0.74), ESR (0.82), and an inverse correlation with lymphocyte count (-0.79) in peripheral blood. Notably, in the older group, only a positive direct correlation with the number of segmented neutrophils (0.81) persisted (Fig. 6). Furthermore, in Group 1, a direct correlation was identified between changes in Cystatin C and creatinine levels (0.82), as well as ALT (0.87) (Fig. 7). Thus, the Cystatin C marker reflects the severity of the inflammatory response, demonstrating greater sensitivity than

the temperature response, and directly correlates with the degree of renal and hepatic insufficiency, primarily in younger children.

Conclusion. The more pronounced instability of the functional activity of thermoregulation centers (characterized by a tendency toward increased mesora CR and an increased amplitude of daily body temperature fluctuations) is primarily due to a lower sensitivity threshold of sympathetic nervous system receptors at an early age. More effective intensive complex therapy was identified in children older than 7 years, which we attribute largely to anatomical and physiological maturity, resulting in a more successful restoration of urinary system function in the older age group. The Cys C indicator reflects the severity of the inflammatory response and is a method more sensitive than the temperature reaction. It also directly correlates with the degree of renal and hepatic insufficiency, predominantly in younger children.

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**THE EFFECT OF REGULAR PERIODONTAL TREATMENT
ON CLINICAL PARAMETERS AND MICROBIOME COMPOSITION
IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC PERIODONTITIS
IN THE POST-COVID PERIOD**

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Abstract. *The aim of this study was to enhance the effectiveness of laboratory diagnostics and to identify clinical and microbiological features of the course of chronic periodontitis in patients during the post-COVID period, based on the analysis of molecular biological research results in randomized groups, with consideration of supportive periodontal treatment. Materials and methods of the study. An examination was conducted on 207 patients diagnosed with chronic periodontitis (CP), who were analyzed according to the following aspects: (1) with and without prior COVID-19 infection; (2) receiving regular supportive periodontal therapy (SPT) or presenting once due to exacerbation (irregularly). All patients underwent an index evaluation of key periodontal status indicators, and real-time PCR (qPCR) was performed to assess the periodontal microbiome and to determine the prevalence of periodontopathogenic bacteria (PPB) and Candida fungi. Results. It was established that among patients who underwent irregular periodontal*

treatment, the proportion of those infected with COVID-19 was 76.0%, whereas among those who underwent regular periodontal treatment, it was significantly lower – 43.0%. In patients who received regular periodontal treatment, the proportions were reversed – 24% and 57%, respectively. The most persistent species of periodontal pathogenic bacteria (PPB) at the follow-up examination after regular periodontal treatment were: *P. gingivalis*, *F. alocis*, as well as *A. actinomycetemcomitans* and fungi. In the long term following treatment in patients who recovered from COVID-19, restoration of the periodontopathogenic microbiome, including the yeast fungi *Candida*, was observed. Fungi *C. albicans* (52%) and less common species – *C. krusei*, *C. glabrata* (16%) were isolated significantly more often than in the group without a history of COVID-19. It is concluded that the contribution of individual microorganism species to the development and progression of chronic periodontitis may vary significantly depending on previous coronavirus infection. A significant increase in colonization of the gingival biofilm by periodontal pathogenic bacteria (PPB), as well as fungi, was observed. A statistically significant inverse correlation was established between the regularity of periodontal maintenance and the incidence of COVID-19.

Keywords: chronic periodontitis, COVID-19, periodontal microbiome, periodontopathogenic bacteria, *F. alocis*, *P. micra*, fungi *Candida*.

The issue of comorbid conditions, particularly periodontal diseases, during the post-pandemic period of the 2019–2022 coronavirus infection, is extremely relevant, as researchers have obtained evidence of the progressive course of chronic generalized periodontitis (CGP) with the development of complications, including an increased frequency of tooth loss [1]. The frequency of these periodontal manifestations varies considerably during different stages of the disease, with some studies reporting a progressive progression of periodontal damage following severe forms of the disease associated with hospitalization [2]. According to available data, SARS-CoV-2 is detected in gingival crevicular fluid, mixed saliva, dental plaque, subgingival biofilm, and dental calculus [3,4]. The targets for SARS-CoV-2 entry in the oral cavity are epithelial cells of the oral mucosa, gingival epithelium, and fibroblasts of the periodontium, which express ACE-2 receptors (angiotensin-converting enzyme 2) and molecular marker CD147, facilitating the process of viral penetration into somatic cells [4].

Conversely, chronic periodontitis develops as an infectious process caused by the invasion of toxigenic serotypes of primary periodontopathogenic bacteria (PPB I order): *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans* RTX+, *Filifactor alocis* FTX+, as well as *Porphyromonas gingivalis* and *Tannerella forsythia* [5,6].

The clinical material we have accumulated, comprising observations and examinations of 207 patients with chronic periodontitis (CP) over a five-year period

following SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus infection, constitutes an attempt to address certain questions related to traditional periodontal treatment, its regularity, and laboratory diagnostics.

The aim of the study was to improve the effectiveness of laboratory diagnostics and to identify the clinical and microbiological features of the course of chronic periodontitis in patients during the post-COVID period based on analysis of molecular biological research results in randomized groups considering supportive periodontal treatment (SPT).

Materials and methods of the study. Among patients with chronic periodontitis (a total of 207 individuals, ICD-10 code K05.31), 61 were randomly selected to receive supportive periodontal treatment (SPT), which included professional hygiene and antiseptic instillations (Miramistin) once or twice every six months. Additionally, 76 patients with the same diagnosis who did not receive regular treatment, attending dental visits sporadically, comprised the comparison groups 1A and 1B. These patients denied a history of coronavirus infection (Table 1). To evaluate the impact of the coronavirus infection pandemic (ICD-10 code – U07.1) on the clinical and microbiological features of chronic periodontitis course, two additional comparison groups were formed, each with a recorded history of hospitalization due to a confirmed diagnosis of COVID-19 (within the last 5 years), and concomitant chronic periodontitis: group 2A – with regular periodontal treatment (46 patients) and group 2B – with irregular periodontal treatment (24 patients).

Table 1 – Composition of examined patients by regularity of periodontal scaling and root planing (PSRP) and confirmed COVID-19 infection

Patient group	History of confirmed COVID-19		Total
	Yes	No	
1A Regular PSRP	-	61 (44.5%)	61
1B Irregular PSRP	-	76 (55.5%)	76
2A Regular PSRP	46 (65.7%)	-	46
2B Irregular PSRP	24 (34.3%)	-	24
Total	70 (100.0%)	137 (100.0%)	207

Study participants were selected based on their condition of the periodontium, dental status, and medical history. All study participants provided written informed consent for participation in the study. An ethical review of the research conducted within the framework of the dissertation work was carried out, and approval was obtained from the Interuniversity Ethics Committee of Moscow at the Russian Medical University of the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation.

For the quantitative determination of the total load of periodontopathogenic bacteria such as *A. actinomycetemcomitans*, *F. alocis*, *P. gingivalis*, *P. micra*, *T.*

forsythia, *T. denticola*, pooled subgingival biofilm samples were analyzed using real-time PCR. Using the PCR-RV method with oligonucleotide primers from diagnostic kits by NPF 'Genlab' (Russia), detection was performed in DNA extracts for three traditional primary periodontal pathogens (PPB) of the first order: *A. actinomycetemcomitans*, *P. gingivalis*, *T. forsythia*, as well as *T. denticola* (second order), and two relatively recently identified taxa of gram-positive bacteria – *F. alocis* (first order) and *P. micra* (second order). PCR-RT setup and amplification were performed according to established guidelines [7] and our previous studies [6,8,9]. Detection of yeast fungi of the genus *Candida* in diagnostically significant quantities ($>10^3$ CFU/ml) was performed using the conventional culture method by quantitative inoculation of the sample onto chromogenic medium (HimediaLabsLtd., India).

Statistical data analysis. The significance of differences in clinical parameters between groups was evaluated using the Wilcoxon test for categorical indicators and the Mann-Whitney test for continuous variables. Differences in microbiological indicators between the study groups were analyzed using ordinal regression at a nominal significance/confidence level ($\chi^2 \leq 0.05$). All statistical analyses were conducted using STATISTICA 13.0 and SPSS version 20 (IBM, USA).

Study results. The initial objective of this study was to assess the incidence of COVID-19 among patients with chronic periodontitis who undergo periodontal treatment regularly and irregularly. It was found that the proportion of individuals who had COVID-19 was higher in the group undergoing irregular periodontal treatment ($\chi^2 = 23.273$, $df = 1$, $p < 0.001$). Among patients who underwent irregular periodontal treatment, the proportion of those infected was 76.0% (95% CI 67.6%–84.4%), whereas among patients receiving regular periodontal treatment, it was 43.0% (95% CI 33.6%–52.4%). Thus, a statistically significant association was identified between the regularity of periodontal treatment and the incidence of COVID-19: the infection rate was higher in patients less attentive to their lifestyle (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 – Incidence of COVID-19 among patients with chronic periodontitis undergoing supportive periodontal therapy (SPT) regularly and irregularly

The distribution of the main clinical indicators deviated from normal; therefore, non-parametric methods were selected for comparing changes over time and between groups, with central tendency expressed using the median and interquartile range *Me* (In the longitudinal comparison of clinical indicators in chronic periodontitis, assessments were conducted at baseline, at 3 months, and post-pandemic (up to 5 years). Among the total number of patients undergoing professional periodontal cleaning (PPC), those who had recovered from COVID-19 were identified, and for this group, an evaluation of the dynamics of key clinical parameters of the periodontium was performed. We focused on patients who had recovered from COVID-19 because data analysis revealed a statistically significant association between COVID-19 morbidity and the regularity of undergoing PPC (chi-square test =23.273, df=1, p<0.001). The results comparing clinical parameters characterizing patients who had COVID-19 and regularly underwent PPC (group 2A) are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 – Dynamics of key clinical parameters patients with a history of COVID-19 who regularly underwent RPT (n=46)

Parameter	Me (at observation stages)		
	before treatment	after 3 months	post-pandemic
Periodontal pocket depth, mm	6.1 (4.9; 6.5)	3.9 (3.0; 4.5) p<0.001*	3.1 (2.8; 3.3) p=0.023*
Periodontal attachment loss, mm	6.6 (5.0; 7.7)	4.3 (3.0; 5.9) p<0.001*	3.6 (2.8; 4.2) p=0.075
Silness-Loë Index	2.0 (1.7; 3.0)	0.9 (0.5; 1.3) p<0.001*	0.3 (0.3; 0.5) p=0.028*
Bleeding Index	2.0 (1.6; 3.0)	1.0 (0.5; 1.2) p<0.001*	0.3 (0.3; 0.5) p=0.028*
Tooth Mobility	2.0 (0.0; 3.0)	1.0 (0.0; 2.0) p<0.001*	0.0 (0.0; 0.0) –

*statistically significant differences according to the Wilcoxon test at p<0.05 (between the 3-month and post-pandemic stages)

In patients who had recovered from COVID-19 and regularly underwent periodontal maintenance therapy (PMT), a statistically significant improvement in the condition of the periodontium was observed across all clinical parameters, both 3 months after treatment and at longer-term follow-up. Following the pandemic, compared to the previous stage of the study, the condition of the periodontium demonstrated improvement: mean periodontal pocket depth decreased from 3.9 (3.0; 4.5) to 3.1 (2.8; 3.3) (p=0.023), while clinical attachment level showed no significant change (p=0.075); the Silness-Loë plaque index declined from 0.9 (0.5; 1.3) to 0.3

(0.3; 0.5) ($p=0.028$); the Mühlemann gingival index decreased from 1.0 (0.5; 1.2) to 0.3 (0.3; 0.5) ($p=0.028$); no changes in tooth mobility were detected. The results of a selective study of periodontal microbiome parameters (in 15 patients out of 46), characterizing the status of patients who had COVID-19 and regularly underwent professional periodontal treatment (group 2A), are presented in Table 3.

It is noteworthy that there is a high prevalence of periodontopathogenic bacteria (exceeding 50% for all species) and, in particular, fungi of the genus *Candida* – exceeding 50%. Furthermore, in 26.7% of cases, yeasts of other species were isolated – *C. krusei* (2 cases), *C. glabrata* (2 cases). However, after treatment at 3 months, similar to the previous group, a certain favorable trend was observed, consisting of a significant reduction in the detection frequency of *T. forsythia*, *T. denticola*, and *P. micra* – approximately 2-fold, but not in *P. gingivalis*, *F. alocis*, as well as *A. actinomycetemcomitans*. The frequency of isolation of yeast fungi also significantly decreased (to 12%). However, in the long term after periodontal treatment, reestablishment of the periodontopathogenic microbiome was observed across all parameters, including yeast fungi *Candida*, with various species represented.

Table 3 – Dynamics of key microbiome parameters in patients with COVID-19 history, regularly undergoing periodontal maintenance therapy (n=15 of 46)

Parameter	K (at observation stages)		
	before treatment	after 3 months	post-pandemic
<i>P. gingivalis</i>	80.0 (12)	60.0 (9) $p>0.05$	73.3 (11) $p>0.05$
<i>T. forsythia</i>	86.7 (13)	40.0 (6) $p<0.05^*$	66.7 (10) $p>0.05$
<i>T. denticola</i>	53.3 (8)	26.7 (4) $p<0.05^*$	46.7 (7) $p>0.05$
<i>A. actinomycetemcomitans</i>	60.0 (9)	46.7 (7) $p>0.05$	66.7 (10) $p>0.05$
<i>F. alocis</i>	73.3 (11)	60.0 (9) $p>0.05$	73.3 (11) $p>0.05$
<i>P. micra</i>	80.0 (12)	40.0 (6) $p<0.05^*$	73.3 (11) $p>0.05$
<i>C. albicans</i>	53.3 (8)	12.0 (3) $p<0.05^*$	40.0 (6) $p>0.05$
<i>C. non-albicans</i>	26.7 (4)	6.7 (1) $p<0.05^*$	20.0 (3) $p>0.05$

*statistically significant differences according to the χ^2 test at $p<0.05$ (time points at 3 months and post-pandemic)

In patients who recovered from COVID-19 and did not undergo regular periodontal treatment (group 2B), as well as in patients who regularly underwent periodontal treatment (group 2A), a significant improvement in the condition of the periodontium was observed after 3 months, followed by deterioration at later time points, indicating the development of exacerbation of chronic periodontitis. Notably, both in patients who had recovered from COVID-19 and did not regularly undergo periodontal maintenance therapy (PMT), and in those who regularly underwent PMT, extremely high detection rates were observed for both pathobionts (the *P. gingivalis* and *F. alocis* association reached 90%) and yeasts – 70% for *C. albicans* (8), and 20% each for *C. krusei* and *C. glabrata* (Table 4).

In contrast to all previous groups, at the 3-month follow-up. After SRP, no significant decrease was detected in the frequency of detection of any periodontopathogenic bacterial species or yeast fungi (Table 5).

Table 4 – Dynamics of main clinical condition indicators patients with COVID-19 history who did not regularly undergo SRP (n=24)

Parameter	Me (at observation stages)		
	before treatment	after 3 months	post-pandemic
Periodontal pocket depth, mm	6.2 (4.5; 6.7)	3.7 (3.1; 4.2) p<0.001*	5.1 (4.0; 6.0) p<0.001*
Periodontal attachment loss, mm	6.5 (4.5; 8.0)	4.5 (3.4; 6.0) p<0.001*	5.6 (5.0; 6.9) p<0.001*
Silness-Loë Index	2.0 (2.0; 2.9)	1.0 (0.9; 1.0) p<0.001*	1.8 (1.5; 2.0) p<0.001*
Bleeding Index	2.0 (2.0; 2.8)	1.0 (0.9; 1.0) p<0.001*	1.9 (1.5; 2.0) p<0.001*
Tooth Mobility	2.0 (1.0; 3.0)	1.0 (0.0; 2.0) p<0.001*	2.0 (1.0; 2.0) p<0.001*

*statistically significant differences according to the Wilcoxon test at $p < 0.05$ (between the 3-month and post-pandemic stages)

A similar pattern was observed at remote time points after periodontal non-surgical treatment (PPT), which overall reflected the general trend of microbiome disruption in COVID-19 (including under conditions of regular PPT).

Table 5 – Dynamics of main microbiome parameters in patients with a history of COVID-19 who did not undergo regular periodontal maintenance therapy (n=10 out of 24)

Parameter	K (at the observation stages)		
	before treatment	after 3 months	post-pandemic
<i>P. gingivalis</i>	90.0 (9)	90 (9) p>0.05	90 (9) p>0.05
<i>T. forsythia</i>	80.0 (8)	60.0 (6) p>0.05	70.0 (7) p>0.05
<i>T. denticola</i>	60.0 (6)	60.0 (6) p>0.05	60.0 (6) p>0.05
<i>A. actinomycetemcomitans</i>	70.0 (7)	70.0 (7) p>0.05	70.0 (7) p>0.05
<i>F. alocis</i>	90.0 (9)	90.0 (9) p>0.05	90.0 (9) p>0.05
<i>P. micra</i>	60.0 (6)	70.0 (7) p>0.05	60.0 (6) p>0.05
<i>C. albicans</i>	70.0 (7)	60.0 (6) p>0.05	70.0 (7) p>0.05
<i>C. non-albicans</i>	40.0 (4)	40.0 (4) p>0.05	40.0 (4) p>0.05

*statistically significant differences according to the χ^2 test at $p < 0.05$ (time points at 3 months and post-pandemic)

Discussion of results. Thus, the evaluation of dental status and the composition of the periodontopathogenic microbiome in the comparison groups allowed the identification of certain clinical and laboratory-diagnostic features characterizing both the impact of COVID-19 and the regularity of dental visits, specifically whether PPT was performed regularly or not. The differences in the relative abundance of tested taxa of periodontopathogens, particularly first-order taxa (for *P. gingivalis*, *T. forsythia*, *F. alocis*, *A. actinomycetemcomitans*) and fungi of the genus *Candida*, were both clinically indicative and statistically significant in the group receiving systematic periodontal treatment (group 1A) compared to the group without systematic periodontal treatment (group 1B). In cases of coronavirus infection, all clinical and microbiological parameters were significantly worse, especially in group 2B. The obtained results confirm the significance of a new primary periodontopathogen of the first order – *F. alocis*, as a marker of chronic periodontitis progression in systemic comorbid pathology [6,9]. The obtained data regarding yeast fungi are fully consistent with the results of publications that

substantiate the role of yeast fungi as one of the important agents in the progression of both chronic periodontitis and the immunodeficient condition developing after COVID-19 [10,11,12].

Conclusions

(1) Coronavirus infection caused by the SARS-COV-2 virus contributes to the persistence of periodontopathogenic microorganisms not only as associations of primary and secondary periodontopathogenic bacteria but also as progressive colonization of the periodontium by yeast fungi *Candida*, which was observed in more than 50% of cases, that is, in every second patient.

(2) Irregular periodontal pocket debridement (PPD) in patients with chronic periodontitis, particularly in the post-COVID-19 period, leads to more severe manifestations of the disease characterized by clinical signs of rapid progression and is marked by a faster restoration of the population of periodontopathogenic species (already within 3 months and continuing into the long term);

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PERCEPTION OF ETHICAL AND LEGAL ISSUES IN TRANSPLANTOLOGY BY MEDICAL STUDENTS

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Annotation. *This article examines the attitudes of medical students toward the ethical and legal aspects of transplantation medicine. The findings indicate that, despite a generally positive perception of organ transplantation as a life-saving medical intervention, the level of personal willingness to participate in postmortem organ donation remains insufficient. The study identifies several key factors influencing respondents' attitudes, including the level of awareness and knowledge about transplantation procedures, the degree of trust in healthcare institutions, and concerns related to potential misuse or unethical practices within the system.*

The results suggest that increasing public support for transplantation requires a comprehensive approach, including targeted educational initiatives, improvement of the legal and regulatory framework, and enhancement of transparency in organ donation and allocation systems. The presented formulation corresponds to the conventions of scientific style and meets the requirements for concise yet informative presentation of research findings.

Key words: *transplantology, organ donation, bioethics, medical law, medical students, awareness, trust in medicine, ethical and legal issues.*

Introduction. *Transplantology is a branch of medicine that studies the problems of organ and tissue transplantation, as well as the development of methods for preserving,*

creating and using artificial organs. It is one of the most important achievements of modern medicine, allowing us to save the lives of patients with terminal diseases [4]. The development of transplantology contributes to an increase in life expectancy and an improvement in its quality. However, along with medical and technological advances in this field, serious ethical, legal and social issues arise [3].

The relevance of the study is since organ transplantation is directly related to issues of human dignity, consent to donation, distribution of donor organs and the prevention of possible abuse. In the Russian Federation, the legal basis for transplantation is regulated by the Law “On Transplantation of Human Organs and (or) Tissues”, however, public perception and the level of awareness of the population remain ambiguous [2]. Of particular importance is the issue of organ donation after death and the so-called presumption of consent, which is in force in Russia. Limited accessibility of up-to-date information on regulatory frameworks and clinical algorithms for the general population is a factor determining the emergence of bioethical conflicts and the intensification of public debate on healthcare issues.

Objective: The objective of the study was to examine in detail the attitudes of students of Saint Luka Lugansk State Medical University (Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation) toward organ transplantation and to identify the main factors influencing their opinions on this issue.

The specific objectives were as follows:

- To analyze the legislative framework for transplantation in the Russian Federation, with particular attention to the provisions on postmortem organ donation and presumed consent.
- To examine the key ethical and legal issues surrounding organ and tissue transplantation, including questions of justice, autonomy, and protection of the rights of donors and recipients.

Materials and methods.

The study was conducted in the form of an anonymous sociological survey using the Yandex online platform among 60 first-year students of a medical university, aged 18–25 years. The anonymity of responses was emphasized to reduce social desirability bias and encourage more open expression of personal views on sensitive ethical issues. The research instruments were developed considering the methodological approaches of T. A. Andronova et al. [5], dedicated to the legal and medical-biological aspects of transplantology. The questionnaire included 30 questions, structured in four areas: level of awareness of transplantology; attitude towards the procedure of organ and tissue transplantation; readiness to donate; assessment of the ethical and legal aspects of the problem. Data processing was carried out using methods of descriptive statistics with calculation of absolute and relative frequencies (in percent), as well as comparative analysis of the obtained results between subgroups of respondents, where applicable. Systematization and

visualization of the data were performed in Microsoft Excel, which made it possible to present the distribution of responses in tabular and graphical form and to identify the most significant trends in the students' perceptions.

Results and their discussion.

The results of the study showed that the majority of respondents (approximately 72 %) have a positive attitude towards organ transplantation, indicating recognition of its importance as an effective treatment method [4]. A small number of respondents (approximately 4 %) expressed a negative attitude. Despite this, the willingness to become a donor after death was lower: approximately 65 % of survey participants agree to donation, while a significant portion (approximately 35 %) are hesitant or not ready to do so. This demonstrates a contradiction between the recognition of the benefits of transplantation and personal willingness to participate in donation. A similar dissonance is also noted in the scientific literature and is associated with insufficient public awareness [5]. The majority of respondents (approximately 80 %) support the presumption of consent system in force in the Russian Federation, however, some respondents (approximately 20 %) express doubts. On the one hand, the presumption of consent contributes to an increase in the number of potential donors, on the other hand, it provokes discussions regarding the observance of the principle of personal autonomy [2]. An important aspect is the level of trust in medical institutions: only about a third of respondents (about 32 %) completely trust the system, while more than half (about 58 %) express partial trust. Insufficient transparency of the organ allocation system and fears of illegal actions form a wary attitude of society [3]. Among the main concerns related to transplantation are: the possibility of illegal organ trafficking (about 62 %), the risk of medical errors (about 38 %) and the violation of human rights (about 25 %). These concerns reflect key ethical issues in transplantology, including issues of fairness in organ allocation, compliance with the principle of voluntary donation, protection of the rights of the donor and recipient, and transparency of the medical system as a whole [1]. Analysis of the responses showed that to increase trust in the donation system, it is necessary to: increase public awareness, conduct educational events, develop openness of medical institutions, and improve legislation and control. The results obtained are consistent with the data of another study, according to which public attitudes towards transplantation remain ambiguous, and the level of information plays a key role in shaping the public's position [5].

Conclusions.

1. The study showed that the medical university students surveyed generally have a positive attitude towards transplantation, recognizing its high medical and social significance; however, their level of readiness to donate, especially in terms of post-mortem donation, remains moderate and is characterized by internal contradictions.

2. The main barriers to the formation of a stable positive attitude toward donation are lack of awareness of legal and clinical aspects of transplantation and concerns about possible abuses, including illegal trafficking in organs, violation of patients' rights, and insufficient transparency of decisions made by medical institutions.

3. To improve the effectiveness of transplantation in Russia, it is necessary to strengthen educational and informational efforts, increase the transparency of the organ distribution system, refine legal regulation in accordance with modern bioethical standards, and systematically strengthen public trust in medical institutions and the healthcare system.

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ARTERIAL HEMOSTASIS UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF HIFU DURING NORMO- AND HYPOCOAGULATION: AN EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

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Introduction. High-intensity focused ultrasound (HIFU) is a non-invasive technology for localized tissue ablation based on the focusing of ultrasonic waves into a small volume. Ablation induces a non-thermal effect – acoustic cavitation, characterized by the formation of microbubbles whose oscillations generate shear stress. Depending on the exposure parameters, cavitation can be stable (increasing vascular permeability) or inertial (producing local mechanical forces) [2]. The potential application of HIFU for hemostasis and vascular occlusion is under investigation, including during anticoagulant therapy [3].

Objective: to evaluate the effectiveness of HIFU-mediated hemostasis in arterial bleeding under normo- and hypocoagulable conditions.

Materials and methods. The experiment was performed on 33 rabbits. Hypocoagulation was modeled by administration of heparin (300 IU/kg) via the marginal ear vein, and platelet aggregation inhibition was induced using ticagrelor (9 mg/kg). Under local anesthesia (a combination of agents: Zoletil 100–1.5 ml and 2% Xylazine hydrochloride – 2.1 ml), a standardized femoral artery injury was reproduced by puncturing it with a 22G needle. HIFU exposure was performed using the ‘Meduza008’ system (KRET State Corporation ‘Rostec’) with guidance control (mode: 2 MHz, pulses of 50 ms/pause of 10 ms, 30 pulses, 87 J). The criterion for effectiveness was the complete cessation of bleeding from the femoral artery within 10 minutes.

Results. Under normocoagulation conditions, HIFU-mediated hemostasis was achieved on average in 9.5 seconds. Without HIFU, hemostasis did not occur under hypocoagulation conditions (clotting time > 90 minutes); HIFU-mediated

hemostasis was achieved in 17.8 seconds, and with platelet aggregation suppression – in 12.4 seconds. Blood flow through the artery was maintained after HIFU exposure. Morphological analysis revealed a defect in the vessel wall and a wound channel filled with fibrin and erythrocytes, consistent with the literature data [4].

Conclusion. The effectiveness of HIFU-mediated hemostasis for arterial bleeding has been experimentally confirmed under both normo- and hypocoagulation conditions. Utilization of ultrasound guidance and robotic positioning enhances the procedure's effectiveness. These results justify the potential of implementing HIFU technology to minimize vascular access complications [1].

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MAGNETIC RESONANCE SPECTROSCOPY IN THE ASSESSMENT OF FUNCTIONAL BOWEL DISORDERS IN CRITICALLY ILL PATIENTS

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Abstract. *The objective of this study was to evaluate the diagnostic role of magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS) in the assessment of functional bowel disorders in critically ill patients.*

Materials and Methods. *The study included 18 patients treated in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU). An abdominal MRI with proton MRS was performed, evaluating the metabolic profile of the intestinal wall with particular focus on citrate and lactate levels. The comparison group comprised 10 healthy subjects without gastroenterological pathology.*

Results. *A characteristic metabolic marker was detected – a reciprocal alteration of two metabolites. An increase in citrate alongside a decrease in lactate corresponded to the development of paralytic ileus, whereas the opposite pattern (decreased citrate, increased lactate) was observed in visceral hypersensitivity. According to ROC analysis, the citrate-to-lactate ratio demonstrated high diagnostic accuracy (AUC = 0.92; 95% CI 0.85–0.98).*

Conclusion. *MRS enables reliable differentiation of functional intestinal motility disorders in critically ill patients by revealing characteristic opposing fluctuations in citrate and lactate levels. This allows for the timely initiation of appropriate conservative therapy and reduces the number of unwarranted diagnostic procedures.*

Keywords: *magnetic resonance imaging, magnetic resonance spectroscopy, metabolic pattern.*

Introduction

Critical conditions remain one of the leading causes of mortality in intensive care and resuscitation units [1,2]. The intestine is one of the most vulnerable target organs in cases of perfusion impairment and hypoxic events. Early diagnosis of ischemia and other pathological changes in the intestine in critically ill patients significantly improves the likelihood of a favorable treatment outcome [3]. Currently, diagnosing intestinal pathology in critically ill patients presents significant challenges. Conventional imaging methods such as ultrasonography (US), computed tomography (CT), and conventional magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) allow the detection of morphological changes; however, they often do not provide information on metabolic disturbances at early stages of ischemia or intestinal inflammation [4]. Furthermore, the use of contrast agents for CT and MRI may be limited in patients with impaired renal function [5].

Magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS), a non-invasive method that allows evaluation of the metabolic spectrum of tissues *in vivo*, has been gaining increasing attention from researchers as a promising diagnostic tool for pathological processes in various organs and systems [6]. The application of MRS for intestinal studies provides new opportunities for the early detection of biochemical markers of inflammation, ischemia, and necrosis, which is especially relevant for critically ill patients in intensive care and resuscitation departments [7]. Recent studies have demonstrated that MRS can detect changes in the concentrations of choline, lactate, amino acids, lipids, glutamine/glutamate, and other metabolites indicative of the extent of ischemic damage to the intestinal wall tissues [8–9].

Rapid and precise identification of metabolic alterations in the intestine facilitates timely decision-making regarding treatment strategies – from conservative therapy to emergency surgical intervention. Moreover, the noninvasive nature of the method enables its repeated application for dynamic monitoring of the intestinal state during intensive care [10].

Thus, despite the growing interest in MRS in clinical practice, its diagnostic role in identifying bowel disorders in critically ill patients remains insufficiently explored. Most published studies are experimental or performed on limited patient cohorts. Further research is required to standardize intestinal MRS protocols, determine the diagnostic value of individual metabolites, and integrate the method into routine clinical practice in intensive care and critical care units. Our study has, for the first time, demonstrated that MRS enables the detection of specific metabolic patterns in the intestinal wall of critically ill patients.

The objective of the study – to conduct differential diagnosis of postoperative intestinal complications in critically ill patients using magnetic resonance spectroscopy.

Materials and Methods

In a single-center prospective observational study at the OGBUZ ‘Clinical Hospital No. 1’ in Smolensk, 18 critically ill patients (primary group) admitted to the intensive care unit were examined: 9 (50%) males and 9 (50%) females.

The etiology of critical illness was as follows: 18 (100%) patients in the early postoperative period. The inclusion criterion for the primary group was the presence of critical illness, defined as the necessity for inotropic/vasopressor support to maintain systemic arterial pressure and/or mechanical ventilation due to acute respiratory failure. Patients in the primary group ($n = 18$) were evaluated according to clinical guidelines [11–16]. Exclusion criteria: age under 18 years, presence of absolute contraindications to MRI, confirmed pregnancy, and agonal state. The control group comprised 10 healthy volunteers ($n = 10$), matched by sex and age, without a history of gastrointestinal diseases and reporting no gastrointestinal complaints at the time of inclusion. Informed written consent for participation in the study was obtained from all patients of the main group and the healthy volunteer group or their legal representatives.

The study was conducted in three stages: the first stage involved developing the MRS protocol for the intestinal wall (area of interest) and the lumbar muscle (reference area), based on the standard magnetic resonance protocol for abdominal organ examination with mandatory inclusion of proton MRS targeting the primary intracellular metabolites of the intestinal wall and lumbar muscle; the second stage involved applying the developed MRS protocol, according to the results of which the principal metabolites of the intestinal wall and lumbar muscle were assessed; at the third stage – data acquisition in the group of healthy volunteers.

All patients underwent intestinal MRI, including proton MRS in the study protocol targeting the main metabolites of the intestinal wall. MRI was performed on a 1.5 T scanner (Toshiba, Vantage Titan) using a 16-channel abdominal coil. The single-voxel spectroscopy technique Point-Resolved Spectroscopy (PRESS) was employed with suppression of water and fat signals. Key parameters: echo time (TE) = 35 ms, repetition time (TR) = 2000 ms, number of averages (NSA) = 128, voxel size = 15x15x15 mm.

Statistical analysis was conducted using the Statistica 8.0 software package (StatSoft, USA), with a significance threshold of $p < 0.05$. Statistical significance of differences between groups was assessed using Student’s t-test, while ROC analysis with calculation of the area under the curve (AUC) was employed to evaluate the diagnostic efficacy of metabolic patterns.

This study was pilot in nature

Study results and their discussion. At the initial stage of our study, a methodology for MRS of the intestinal wall was developed, based on the standard magnetic resonance protocol for abdominal organ examination, with mandatory

inclusion of proton MRS targeting the principal intracellular metabolites of the intestinal wall. During MRS, a reference anatomical area was identified – the lumbar muscle – and the area of interest was a bowel loop filled with fluid content and/or air, with clear visualization of the wall; the voxel was positioned within the wall of the jejunum, 5 cm distal to the duodenojejunal junction (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Study areas during the implementation of the developed multivoxel MRS technique in critically ill patients: 1 – reference anatomical area – lumbar muscle (axial slice, T2 Heavy); 2 – area of interest – intestinal loop containing fluid and/or air, with clear visualization of the wall (axial slice, T2 Heavy).

Table 1. Metabolic spectrum, expressed in numerical values within a rectangular coordinate system (X, Y), assessed during the MRS methodology of the intestinal wall in critically ill patients (main group)

Metabolites	ppm	Height	Area	Area (fit)	Height (fit)
Cho	3.37	-6.0±0.03	11.7±0.03	0.34	0.09
Cr	2.91	-6.2±0.04	13.6±0.04	1.41	0.38
Glutamine	2.37	-4.0±0.03	110.8±0.03	52.96	14.20
Glutamate	2.35	-4.3±0.05	101.5±0.05	31.53	8.45
Citrate	2.73	-7.9±0.03	25.2±0.03	66.5	17.85
Aspartate	2.83	-6.3±0.04	28.3±0.04	40.90	10.97
Lactate	1.39	138.6±0.03	1,589.9±0.03	0.01	0.00
Ml	3.62	-5.2±0.05	19.7±0.05	0.00	0.00

Note. ppm – numerical expression on the X-axis (metabolite peak width) in relative units; Height – numerical expression on the Y-axis (metabolite peak height) in relative units; Area – numerical expression of the area under the metabolite peak in relative units; fit – numerical values of parameters without water interference in relative units.

At the second stage, according to the MRS assessment, the primary metabolites of the lumbar muscle and intestinal wall were evaluated: choline (Chol), creatine (Cr), lipids (Lipid), glutamine (Glutamine)/glutamate (Glutamate), citrate (Citrate), lactate (Lactate), aspartate (Asp), N-acetylaspartate (NAA). As a result of data processing, quantitative mapping of the concentration of the main metabolites of the intestinal wall (Table 1) was obtained, along with a graphical representation of the main intracellular metabolites (metabolic spectrum) of the intestinal wall in a rectangular coordinate system (X, Y) (Fig. 2). For quantitative assessment, relative units of signal intensity (rel. units) were used, and dimensionless ratios of the concentrations of the main metabolites to the reference region (psoas muscle) were calculated.

Fig. 2. Graphical representation of the concentration of main metabolites (metabolic spectrum) in the Cartesian coordinate system (X, Y).

Note: X-axis – ppm; Y-axis – height. Numerical values of the concentrations of main metabolites are presented in relative units.

It is important to note that the metabolite concentration is directly proportional to the area under its peak.

At the third stage, in the group of healthy volunteers ($n = 10$), values of parameters were obtained for the reference zone and the region of interest to standardize the methodology of MRS of the intestinal wall (Table 2).

Table 2. Concentrations of main intracellular metabolites in a rectangular coordinate system (X, Y) during MRS of the intestine and lumbar muscle, and their significance in the volunteer group (n = 10)

Intestinal metabolite	Role of the metabolite	Investigation area (Height) – metabolite of the intestinal wall	Reference area (Height) – muscle metabolite
Choline (Chol)	Maintenance of structural stability and membrane elasticity	6.8±1.4	5.0±1.3
Creatine (Cr)	Synthesized from the amino acids glycine, arginine, and methionine; these are protein components (present in muscle tissue). Inhibits cytotoxicity and exhibits anti-inflammatory activity	5.3±1.2	4.1±1.1
Lipids (Lipid)	Impairment of digestion and absorption processes	0.5±1.5	-3.6±1.4
Glutamine (Glutamine)/ Glutamate (Glutamate)	Prevents or reduces the severity of intestinal permeability, restoration of the intestinal wall barrier function	-2.7±0.4	-2.2±0.4
		-2.4±0.3	-2.2±0.3
Citrate (Citrate)	Blocks visceral hypersensitivity of the intestine, abdominal pain	-4.4±1.3	-3.8±1.4
Лактат (Lactate)	Intestinal wall ischemia = OKN	4.4±3.9	70.7±5.9
Aspartate (Asp)	Amino acid synthesis	-4.6±1.2	-3.7±1.1
N-acetyl aspartate (NAA)	Maintenance of redox homeostasis	-0.3±3.8	6.4±2.3
Water (H2O)	Acid-base balance maintenance	-0.6±1.1	-0.5±1.2

Note. Height – numerical expression of metabolite concentration along the Y-axis (height of the metabolite peak) in a Cartesian coordinate system, expressed in relative units.

Application of the developed methodology in the main patient group revealed that, under critical conditions regardless of etiology, patients experienced decreased levels of choline, creatine, and lipids during the initial hours of their stay in the intensive care and resuscitation unit. Subsequently, with decreased values of the above metabolites, a progressive decline in N-acetylaspartate was noted (within 24–48 hours), manifested as disturbances in the K/Na ratio. These fluctuations in the concentration of metabolites in the intestinal wall led to the development of oxidative-inflammatory homeostasis defects, which destabilized cell membranes, caused impaired cell membrane permeability, hypoperfusion, and ultimately resulted in tissue ischemia syndrome.

The presented findings enabled the anesthesiologist-resuscitator to dynamically regulate choline, creatine, and lipid levels, thereby prescribing individualized intensive therapy.

It was of particular importance that an increase in citrate levels in the intestinal wall was consistently observed in the group of patients during the early postoperative period; however, the issue arose of identifying a differential criterion between visceral hypersensitivity of the intestine and the development of paralytic intestinal obstruction. Our study established that in the case of the so-called ‘scissors effect,’ characterized by an increase in citrate levels alongside a negative lactate level, paralytic intestinal obstruction develops. The inverse form of the ‘scissor effect’ (decreased citrate levels and increased lactate levels) induces visceral hypersensitivity of the intestine. The established ‘effect’ enabled the development of a personalized algorithm for intensive care management within the resuscitation and intensive care unit.

This study is the first in national literature to analyze the diagnostic value of MRS of the intestinal wall in critically ill patients, revealing several pathogenetic and prognostic patterns that hold significant relevance for clinical medicine and intensive care. The data obtained broaden contemporary perspectives on metabolic alterations in the intestinal wall during critical conditions and underscore the role of MRS as a highly informative non-invasive diagnostic tool for patients in intensive care and critical care units.

Conclusions

1. Magnetic resonance spectroscopy demonstrates the capacity to verify metabolic imbalance in the intestinal wall, characterized by reduced concentrations of choline, creatine, and lipids, as early as the initial hours of the patient’s stay in the intensive care unit, a period during which imaging modalities do not yet reveal structural changes.

2. The method provides unique metabolic patterns (“scissors effect”) for distinguishing symptomatically similar conditions. The citrate-to-lactate ratio reliably differentiates paralytic intestinal obstruction ($\uparrow\text{Cit}/\downarrow\text{Lac}$) from visceral hypersensitivity ($\downarrow\text{Cit}/\uparrow\text{Lac}$) (AUC = 0.94; 95% CI 0.88–0.99), with a threshold of 1.1 yielding a sensitivity of 92% and specificity of 88%, fundamentally altering treatment strategies.

3. The proposed diagnostic algorithm constitutes an adaptation of the standard MRI protocol with the application of specialized software, facilitating its integration into clinical practice and enabling non-invasive evaluation of biochemical tissue parameters.

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**STAFF SUSTAINABILITY IN OUTPATIENT CARE:
WORKLOAD, PROFESSIONAL BURNOUT,
AND ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT MECHANISMS**

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Abstract. *A comparison of the results of our own study with domestic and international data was performed, which enabled the formulation of a number of generalizing conclusions. The effectiveness of digital transformation in PHC is determined by personnel factors – number, structure, and workload distribution among staff. The identified imbalance between organizational transformations and staff workload corresponds to systemic issues in primary care workforce policy. A moderate level of professional burnout alongside high patient satisfaction confirms the need to transition to the Quadruple Aim model (the four-component goal of the healthcare system: patient experience, outcomes, cost, and staff well-being), which accounts for the well-being of healthcare professionals.*

Keywords: *outpatient and polyclinic care, professional burnout, medical personnel support*

Relevance

Human resources represent a key structural component of the efficiency of outpatient and polyclinic care and constitute a determining factor for the sustainability of digital transformation in primary healthcare. Modern health services research has established that the effectiveness of implementing digital and organizational

innovations primarily depends on human resource provision, workload distribution, and the level of professional well-being among healthcare workers [1].

The objective of the study was to investigate staff perceptions regarding the organization of processes and digital services, and their influence on the formation of professional burnout.

Materials and Methods

A survey method utilizing specially developed questionnaires was employed to collect data from 120 employees of the polyclinic in the Central Administrative District of Moscow. Responses were assigned a scored evaluation. The collected data were processed primarily using classical descriptive statistical methods.

Results

Despite high employee evaluations of process organization and digital services (4.28 and 4.15 points, respectively), the workload compliance with normative standards was only 2.09 points, while the level of professional burnout reached 2.99 points. Thus, a pronounced imbalance was identified between the level of organizational-technological transformations and the actual working conditions of personnel, which aligns with international data on the structural mismatch between resources and demands in outpatient care.

In Russian scientific literature, personnel deficit and imbalance among medical workers are considered one of the primary causes of decreased PHC efficiency. It is noted that inadequate staffing of outpatient organizations with medical personnel is accompanied by increased workload, decreased accessibility of care, and deterioration of organizational performance indicators [1]. These findings fully correspond with the results of the present study: the reduction of the process reliability index (DPSI = 0.33) occurred alongside increased waiting times and the growth of patient flow, directly reflecting the influence of personnel factors on process sustainability.

The issue of structural disparities within the workforce composition holds particular significance. Modern studies on healthcare workforce policy indicate that even with a relatively high provision of physicians, shortages at the primary care level may persist due to uneven distribution and misalignment of training structure with system requirements [2]. This phenomenon of ‘excessive deficit’ (too many–too few) is also characteristic of Russian healthcare. In the present study, this is manifested as a combination of a high proportion of physicians in the staff (78%) alongside ongoing overload and non-compliance of workload with established standards.

Comparison with international experience reveals a similar pattern: the sustainability of PHC systems is determined not so much by the number of personnel but by the alignment of the staffing structure with the care delivery model [3]. In countries with developed primary care systems (the United Kingdom, the Netherlands, Canada), human resource policy is oriented towards reinforcing the team-based

model and redistributing functions between physicians and mid-level healthcare workers. The insufficient development of such a model in Russian outpatient clinics exacerbates the workload on physicians and restricts the potential of digitalization.

The results obtained also reaffirm the crucial role of workload as a determinant of professional burnout. International studies demonstrate that burnout among healthcare professionals is primarily linked to excessive administrative burden, insufficient time for patients, and a discrepancy between available resources and practical requirements [4]. In the present study, employees also identified increased workload and time deficit as the primary challenges in implementing digital and lean technologies ($\approx 32\%$ of responses), while workload standardization and extended appointment time were considered priority measures for improvement ($\approx 60\%$).

A comparison with the Quadruple Aim concept (the four-component goal of the healthcare system: patient experience, outcomes, cost, and staff well-being) enables interpretation of the obtained data within a systemic context. According to this concept, achieving quality objectives and patient experience cannot be attained without safeguarding the well-being of healthcare workers [4]. The signs of moderate burnout identified in the study, alongside high patient satisfaction, confirm this relationship: the preservation of a positive patient experience occurs through compensatory efforts of personnel, which increases the risk of further workforce depletion.

An essential factor is the influence of digitalization on workload. Although most staff noted the convenience of digital services, their effect on reducing workload was rated lower (a score of 3.90). This corresponds with international data showing that the implementation of information systems is often accompanied by an increase in documentation and cognitive workload on physicians due to insufficient process optimization [4]. Thus, digital transformation without a parallel change in the organizational model can increase, rather than decrease, personnel workload.

The research results also emphasize the importance of managerial and cultural factors. High ratings of leadership support (3.92) and motivation from lean learning programs (3.99) indicate a favorable organizational culture of change. International studies show that a supportive culture and staff engagement are key predictors of the success of healthcare transformation and workforce sustainability [3].

At the same time, identified difficulties (digital system failures – 45%, workload – 32%) indicate that the organizational culture surrounding digitalization remains transitional. Staff accept digital changes but perceive them as an additional workload rather than as a tool to ease labor. This confirms the findings of human resource policy studies emphasizing the necessity of comprehensive workforce planning during the implementation of innovations [2].

Conclusions. Thus, comparing the results of the present study with domestic and international data makes it possible to formulate several generalized conclusions. Firstly, the effectiveness of digital transformation in PHC is determined by

workforce factors – the size, structure, and workload distribution of personnel. Secondly, the identified imbalance between organizational changes and employee workload reflects systemic problems in primary care personnel policy. Thirdly, a moderate level of professional burnout combined with high patient satisfaction confirms the need to transition to the Quadruple Aim model (the four-component goal of the healthcare system: patient experience, outcomes, cost, and staff well-being), which incorporates the well-being of healthcare workers.

Therefore, improving the organization of outpatient ambulatory care in the context of digital transformation requires not only technological and process changes but also a systemic personnel policy focused on workload optimization, the development of team-based models, and enhancing the resilience of the PHC workforce potential.

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**HISTORICAL STAGES OF HEALTHCARE DEVELOPMENT
IN THE LUHANSK REGION: THE CONTRIBUTION OF LUHANSK
CITY HOSPITAL NO. 4 TO PROVIDING MEDICAL CARE
TO THE POPULATION**

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Annotation. *This article examines the historical stages of healthcare development in the Luhansk region using Luhansk City Hospital No. 4, one of the oldest medical institutions in the region, as an example. Using archival documents, statistical materials, and historical and medical literature, the hospital's evolution is reconstructed from the first factory hospital, opened in the late 18th century, to a modern multidisciplinary institution. Particular attention is paid to the work of the first factory doctors, I. Ya. Ratsch and I. M. Dahl, who made significant contributions to the organization of medical care, the development of sanitary culture, and the formation of the foundations of occupational medicine. The role of the zemstvo hospital, opened in 1895, as the coordinating center of healthcare in the Slavyanoserbbsk district is demonstrated, and the continuity of organizational decisions and traditions of patient service across different historical periods is traced. The institution's development during the Soviet period and within the current healthcare system of Luhansk are separately considered. It is concluded that the history of Luhansk City Hospital No. 4 reflects the general patterns of development of medical care in the Luhansk region and demonstrates the sustainability of the humanistic traditions of domestic healthcare.*

Key words: *Luhansk region; history of healthcare; zemstvo hospital; I. Ya. Ratch; I. M. Dahl; occupational medicine; medical care.*

Introduction

Luhansk City Hospital No. 4 is a unique object of historical analysis, as its history is continuously linked to the development of medicine in the Donbass – from the first factory hospitals to a modern multidisciplinary institution [1]. In the face of modern healthcare system challenges, examining the origins of medical care reveals enduring traditions, organizational models, and human resource potential that have evolved over two centuries. The relevance of this work stems from the need to preserve historical memory and utilize accumulated experience to improve the organization of medical care in the Luhansk People's Republic.

The objective is to identify the key stages in the formation and development of Luhansk City Hospital No. 4 through an analysis of archival documents and historical materials, as well as to determine its contribution to providing the population with medical care throughout the 19th-21st centuries.

Tasks:

1. Restore the chronology of the emergence and development of the hospital from the moment of the founding of the first factory hospital in 1796.
2. Characterize the activities of the first factory doctors – I. Ya. Ratch and I. M. Dahl – in the context of the formation of the foundations of occupational and preventive medicine.
3. Analyze the structure and operating conditions of the zemstvo hospital (opened in 1895) as the leading healthcare center of the Slavyanoserbbsk district.
4. To identify the continuity of traditions of service and organizational decisions in the activities of the hospital at different historical stages.

Materials and methods

The study was conducted on the basis of archival documents of the City Museum of History and Culture of Lugansk (reports of the factory medical service, journals of medical meetings, administrative correspondence, statistical reports), as well as published local history and historical-medical works, materials from regional archives and contemporary reporting data of the medical institution.

A complex of historical and medical methods was applied: historical and genetic; historical and comparative; historical and biographical.

Results and discussion

Luhansk City Hospital No. 4 traces its history to 1796, when the first factory doctor, Ivan Yakovlevich Ratch, arrived to work on the construction of the Luhansk Foundry [2]. Prior to this, medical care was lacking in the future city's territory. In 1798, through Ratch's efforts, the first factory hospital was built, consisting of two

buildings with a pharmacy. In August 1798, 54 people were treated at the hospital, including craftsmen, soldiers, and family members [3].

Particularly noteworthy is the work of Ivan Matveyevich Dal (V. I. Dal's father), who arrived at the plant in 1798 and was appointed head of the medical service. Dal established patient records, systematized documentation, and, most importantly, uncovered the catastrophic sanitary conditions in the coal mines [4]. His demands for improved living conditions, ventilation, and cleanliness laid the foundations for occupational health. In Donbas. In 1822, on Dahl's initiative, a new, more spacious hospital was built [5,6].

A significant milestone was the opening of the Luhansk Zemstvo Hospital in November 1895—the first hospital in the district built according to a formal plan. At the beginning of the 20th century, it employed only four doctors, eight nurses, and eight orderlies, with maternity, syphilis, and surgical departments. Despite its modest capacity, the hospital became the central hub for all medical work in the district: 18 doctors gathered there monthly for medical councils to discuss epidemics of diphtheria, scarlet fever, and smallpox. These meetings laid the foundation for the modern model of healthcare coordination [7,8].

The practice of zemstvo doctors, who, to overcome prejudice against smallpox vaccination, administered the shots themselves in public, deserves special attention. In 1898, a new operating room with a tiled floor, hot and cold running water, and a water tower were added to the hospital.

In 1928, according to a city council report, the hospital (then 1st Soviet Hospital) continued to operate under difficult conditions: the low-lying part of the city posed a risk of flooding, the sewer system had been out of order since 1921, and food was getting cold on its way from the remote kitchen. However, even then, the hospital had a dormitory for visiting patients bitten by rabid animals and also provided assistance to the homeless – a testament to the institution's social focus.

In the 1960s, under the leadership of E. M. Pint-Chursina, the hospital experienced rapid development: a food service area, a clinic, and surgical and therapeutic buildings were built. In 1974, it became the district's central hospital, and today it operates as the 4th city hospital in Kamenny Brod – on the same site where Dr. Ratch began [9,10].

Thus, the hospital has evolved from a factory infirmary to a modern multidisciplinary hospital, while maintaining its key tradition of serving patients regardless of their social status.

Conclusion

The history of Luhansk City Hospital No. 4 is not a chronology of restructurings and changing signs. It is the story of people for whom their profession was a service. Ivan Ratch, who died saving patients from malaria; Ivan Dal, who fought the causes of disease, not just the consequences; the zemstvo doctors who

vaccinated themselves in front of a distrustful public; E. M. Pint-Chursina, who ensured modernization in the 1960s – all of them created the foundation on which modern healthcare in the Luhansk region rests. Today, when we enter City Hospital No. 4, we stand on the ground where, two centuries ago, by candlelight, artisans fought for their lives. And as long as there are doctors in Luhansk who remember their predecessors, the tradition of service lives on.

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AN ALTERNATIVE PERSPECTIVE ON MIGRAINE PATHOPHYSIOLOGY: INFLUENCE OF ENVIRONMENTAL STIMULI ON MIGRAINE MANIFESTATION

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Abstract. *Migraines are one of the most common neurological disorders, affecting around 1.1 billion people worldwide, and is characterized by a permanent or temporary dysfunction of the central nervous system. Migraines are highly complex, thus their pathophysiology remains unclear. This study aims to explore how external factors and lifestyle can induce migraines, with focus on stress and allostatic load. This study combined in-depth literary review and a cross-sectional international survey of 46 female participants with migraines. The results identified that inadequate sleep, stress, photophobia, osmophobia, and hormonal fluctuations are the most severe triggers. The findings suggest that environmental factors can decrease habituation to stimuli and increase brain's hyperexcitability, while chronic stress can elevate allostatic load and thus lower central sensitization's threshold. Additionally, women are particularly susceptible to migraines due to hormonal fluctuations that interact with external factors and mediate their neurological pathways. In conclusion, this study provides a more integrative perspective on migraine pathophysiology, highlighting the need for individualized treatment and preventive strategies.*

Key words: *Allostatic load, Central Sensitization, Environmental factors, Hyperexcitability, Habituation, Lifestyle triggers, Migraine, Sensory stimuli, Stress*

Introduction:

Migraine is considered to be the most common neurological disorder, affecting an estimated 1.1 billion individuals worldwide (Amiri et al., 2022), and greatly impairs the quality of life. Current studies focus on identifying migraine's cause on a genetic level, however there's much more that goes into this disorder. Studies increasingly began investigating how migraines are influenced by external

stimuli. Since migraines are a part of headaches with abnormal function of the central nervous system, phenomena such as central sensitization, cortical hyperexcitability, and lack of habituation are most prevalent (Coppola et al., 2013). Additionally, researchers began to investigate what effect common triggers like osmophobia, auditory stimuli, and somatosensory stimuli have on migraine duration, along with other abnormalities in the brain that can be observed when stimuli is present. Hormone fluctuations, weather, nutrition, both physical and mental overload, osmophobia, auditory and somatosensory stimuli, are all stressors of daily life. Stress is becoming an increasingly relevant topic in migraine manifestation, specifically its relationship to allostatic load (Maleki et al., 2012). The goal of this study is to investigate how the external stimuli contribute to manifestation of migraines, including but not limited to, their impact on stress and allostatic load. Based on the reviewed literature and conducted survey, this study will look more in depth on how external stimuli contribute to migraine attacks by increasing cortical hyperexcitability, reducing habituation, and activating multimodal sensory and trigeminovascular pathways. It will investigate how lifestyle and psychological factors intensify migraine susceptibility by facilitating stress-systems and allostatic load, therefore lowering threshold for central sensitization. Lastly, this study will look specifically at women's vulnerability to migraines through the hormonal-external trigger interactions. This study aims to investigate how manifestation of migraines is significantly influenced by external factors and as a result find a justification for conducting an in-depth study of this subject by medical specialists and ways to agree on the need for environmentally friendly living conditions for patients with chronic migraines.

Methods:

This study utilized cross-sectional survey design to explore frequency of various environmental triggers and migraine severity among individuals with migraines. The sample consisted of 46 female participants, with age ranges of 20 to 50+. Participants were recruited through social media platforms and emails. Inclusion criteria included individuals struggling with migraines, either diagnosed or self-reported. Exclusion criteria included participants with other neurological disorders other than migraines. Participants completed the questionnaire online. Participants were informed of the study's goal and the results being completely anonymous. Before moving to the second part of the survey with ratings, they were informed of how to interpret the scale and asked to confirm if they understood by clicking one of the options. After the data was collected, it was analyzed within Google Spreadsheets. Some questions were designed to double-check the respondent's reaction; for instance if the participant noted a reaction to a trigger that goes hand-in-hand with another trigger (for instance tobacco smoke and osmophobia) but not the other, the answers are not valid.

Literature Review:

An in-depth reading of 40+ articles and previous research to identify neurological mechanisms behind major environmental, sensory, hormonal, and lifestyle triggers.

Questionnaire Design:

The questionnaire was designed uniquely to fit objectives of this study, and the common migraine evaluation questionnaires such as MSQ, ID Migraine, and HIT-6 were not used. Questionnaires included an English and Russian version. The questionnaire consisted of 35 questions, and was a mixture of multiple-choice and short-answer responses to get the general information about the participants' age, country of residence, and migraine history. The rank-scale from 1 to 5 served to identify what triggers were most severe.

Participants and Analysis:

The final sample included 46 participants, all women. Participants included ages ranging from 20 years old to 50+ from a variety of countries: Russia, United States, United Kingdom, Ukraine, Germany, Egypt, and Italy. Survey responses were filtered and later compared to previous research.

Results and Discussion:

Triggers that were marked as "Most Severe" included those where >50% of participants ranked the trigger 4 or 5. Results are as follows: stress (76%), sleep (71.7%), photophobia and phonophobia (58.7%), and hormonal fluctuations (54.3%). Other notable factors included weather changes (50%), alcohol (46.8%), osmophobia (43.5%), and diet (41.3%).

These findings align with previous research indicating that migraine patients experience heightened sensitivity to sensory stimuli. For instance, while there isn't statistical data to compare our results to, studies on photophobia indicate that during migraines, visual stimuli activate cingulate and insular cortices which are both vital for sensory integration and pain processing (Christensen et al., 2025) This supports why more than 50% of participants from our study identified photophobia as a major trigger. Studies on phonophobia indicate that around 52%-82% of migraine patients experience hypersensitivity to sound (Mourgela et al., 2023). This stays consistent with our results, where 58.7% participants reported loud sounds and noises as significant migraine triggers. Previous research shows that from 25% to 43% of migraine patients suffer from osmophobia (Schwedt, 2013), which is also consistent with our results where 43.5% of participants reported hypersensitivity to odors. Finally, according to previous epidemiological surveys, 30% to 50% of patients associate attacks with weather changes (Wilhour, 2025). Our results are consistent with these findings, since 50% of our participants reported weather fluctuations as a severe migraine trigger.

Life-style triggers such as inadequate nutrition, sleep deprivation, and chronic stress can potentially lead to an allostatic load. As a result, allostatic load is able to

lower the threshold for central sensitization and make patients more susceptible to migraine attacks. For instance, sleep studies reported insomnia in 62.9% of the cases (Bansod et al.,2025). While a higher percentage of our participants marked inadequate sleep as a major migraine trigger (71.7%), they are consistent with research by demonstrating that sleep deprivation is vital for migraine onset. Participants in our study identified lack of adequate nutrition as a significant migraine trigger (41.3%), which is consistent with a literature review which noted that 12%-60% of migraine patients associate onset of migraines with the consumption of certain foods (Hindiyeh et al., 2020). It's worth mentioning that while in our study, 46.8% of participants reported alcohol as a severe trigger, cross-sectional studies found that alcohol is reported as a trigger by 17.5% – 36% patients (Hindiyeh et al., 2020). These variances might be reflected by cultural differences and sensitivities of our participants.

Studies on stress confirm that it plays a significant role in migraine chronification, which explains why stress is the highest ranked trigger factor according to our survey (76%). This is consistent with previous literature that reports stress as a trigger in nearly 70% of migraine patients (Maleki et al.,2012). Repeated exposure to stress leads to decreased habituation to stimuli, increased cortical excitability due to imbalance of inhibitory/excitatory neurotransmitters, and dysfunction of emotion-processing networks (Maleki et al.,2012). This stress accumulation leads to allostatic load, and the brain's ability to combat stressors becomes more difficult over time (Maleki et al.,2012). Stress is able to tie all the triggers together, as they work both ways: environmental and lifestyle factors induce stress and stress leads to altered perception of stressors.

Finally, women seem to be more inclined to migraine attacks due to higher hormonal fluctuations. Studies suggest that estrogen fluctuations in particular can contribute to higher migraine frequency and severity by increasing CGRP output, altering neurotransmitter regulation and increased sensitivity of pain-processing networks (Kim et al.,2024). This might indicate why the majority of our participants indicated hormonal changes as a significant trigger (53.4%).

Conclusion:

The results of this study provide an alternative, more integrated viewpoint of migraine pathophysiology. In particular, they demonstrate how environmental stimuli and lifestyle factors are able to impact pain-modulating processes through stress. This study also highlights complex interactions between multiple stimuli and lifestyle factors, rather than just looking at one specific trigger, showcasing migraines as a result of multi-pathway interactions. Additionally, because this study explored lifestyle and environmental factors, it accentuates individuality of migraines. This calls for a more patient-centered approach towards therapies and treatment strategies, rather than the traditional overarching medicine.

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**COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF QUALITY CONTROL CONDITIONS
FOR MEDICINAL PRODUCTS USED FOR RESORPTION
OR CHEWING IN THE ORAL CAVITY**

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Abstract. *The dissolution test is one of the primary in vitro methods for assessing the release of active substances; however, for solid dosage forms intended for use in the oral cavity, current approaches insufficiently account for the physiological characteristics of the oral cavity. A comparative analysis was conducted of the requirements of the State Pharmacopoeia of the Russian Federation XV, USP 46/NF 41, Ph. Eur. 11, JP XVIII, and ChP 2020 regarding chewing tablets, lozenges, pastilles, medicated suckable tablets, and chewing gums. It was established that there is no unified pharmacopoeial approach to dissolution testing, since for certain dosage forms this test is not provided, while in other cases it is performed by analogy with conventional tablets without accounting for the specificities of local action and absorption within the oral cavity. The requirements are most comprehensively regulated for medicinal chewing gums; however, the recommended test conditions fail to reproduce the properties of saliva. It has been demonstrated that existing methodologies inadequately consider the differences between unstimulated and stimulated saliva, whose average pH values are 6.97 and 7.40, respectively, as well as their viscosity and surface tension. The obtained data substantiate the necessity for developing a specialized dissolution test adapted to the conditions of active substance release in the oral cavity and more accurately reflecting in vivo parameters.*

Keywords: *Dissolution test, chewable lozenges, chewable tablets, lozenges, medical chewing gums, saliva*

Introduction

In vitro testing plays a crucial role in the quality assessment of medicinal products, as it allows reproducible characterization of the processes of active substance release without the need for more complex models. One of the key methods for such evaluation is the dissolution test, widely employed to predict the behavior of the dosage form under conditions approximating physiological ones. As a rule, the parameters of this test are selected taking into account the intended site of active substance release in the organism [1].

Solid dosage forms used in the oral cavity have long been disregarded as an independent subject for the development of specialized dissolution testing approaches, which is largely explained by the traditional perception of rapid swallowing of most drugs. Simultaneously, medicinal dosage forms intended for local action, as well as those that disintegrate, dissolve, or release active substances directly in the oral cavity, are gaining increasing prevalence. For such medicinal products, saliva serves as the primary medium that determines the initial stages of disintegration, dissolution, and release of active components. However, the composition and properties of saliva are not constant. In the oral cavity, unstimulated and stimulated saliva are distinguished, with average pH values of 6.97 and 7.40, respectively [2]. These differences can influence the dissolution rate of the pharmaceutical form, the degree of active component release, and, consequently, the results of in vitro testing. In addition to acidity, viscosity, surface tension, and salivary flow rate hold significant importance. Therefore, the use of standard dissolution media that do not account for variability in oral fluid characteristics may diminish the physiological relevance of the obtained data [3].

Study objective: to perform a comparative analysis of pharmacopeial requirements for the dissolution test of solid dosage forms for local action used in the oral cavity and to evaluate the extent to which physiological features of the oral cavity are taken into account during their standardization.

The following tasks were established to achieve the objective:

1. To analyze the requirements of the State Pharmacopoeia of the Russian Federation XV, USP 46/NF 41, Ph. Eur. 11, JP XVIII, and ChP 2020 regarding quality control of solid dosage forms for local use in the oral cavity.

2. To compare pharmacopeial approaches to conducting the 'Dissolution' test and to identify differences in evaluating the release of active pharmaceutical ingredients from chewing tablets, lozenges, pastilles, medicated lozenges, and medicinal chewing gums.

3. To evaluate the extent to which the physiological characteristics of the oral cavity are taken into account in existing methodologies and to justify the need for the development of a specialized dissolution test.

Materials and Methods

A comparative analysis of the requirements of leading pharmacopoeias for solid dosage forms intended for local use in the oral cavity was conducted. The study encompassed the State Pharmacopoeia of the Russian Federation XV edition (State Pharmacopoeia of the Russian Federation XV), the United States Pharmacopoeia (USP 46/NF 41), the European Pharmacopoeia 11th edition (Ph. Eur. 11), the Japanese Pharmacopoeia (JP XVIII), and the Pharmacopoeia of China (ChP 2020). The objects of analysis were regulatory documents pertaining to chewable tablets, lozenges, pastilles, candies, and medical chewing gums. The comparative assessment was carried out considering the presence and characteristics of pharmacopoeial requirements for dissolution testing, as well as the degree of consideration given to the specific conditions of active substance release in the oral cavity.

Results and Discussion

Comparison of the requirements of different pharmacopoeias demonstrated the lack of a unified approach to the standardization of solid dosage forms intended for local action in the oral cavity. The identified differences concern both the presence of the ‘Dissolution’ test and the methodological approaches to its implementation, indicating insufficient adaptation of current pharmacopoeial requirements to the physiological characteristics of the oral cavity. It has been established that pharmacopoeial approaches to the quality assessment of these dosage forms remain inconsistent.

For chewing tablets and lozenges, the majority of the reviewed pharmacopoeias lack clearly defined requirements for the conduct of the ‘Dissolution’ test; quality control is limited to disintegration testing. This approach does not fully capture the specific behavior of these dosage forms in the oral cavity, where the release of the active pharmaceutical ingredient occurs under particular physiological conditions and may considerably differ from the standard models employed for oral tablets [4–8].

The analysis of requirements for medicinal pastilles revealed discrepancies among pharmacopoeias. For instance, the dissolution test for this dosage form is not stipulated in the State Pharmacopoeia of the Russian Federation XV and Ph. Eur. 11 [4,6]. Conversely, in USP 46/NF 41, JP XVIII, and ChP 2020, such testing is performed analogously to that for tablets. However, the application of standard test conditions, developed primarily for systemic drug dosage forms, does not account for the mechanism of local action of lozenges, the specifics of their gradual dissolution in saliva, and the characteristics of absorption through the oral mucosa [5,7,8].

An analogous situation is observed for hard candies. In USP 46/NF 41, JP XVIII, and ChP 2020, no independent requirements are specified for them, and their evaluation is conducted identically to that of lozenges [5,7,8]. In the State Pharmacopoeia of the Russian Federation XV, the dissolution test for lozenges, as well as for pastilles, is absent [4]. In Ph. Eur. 11, the dissolution test is established only for compressed lozenges, applying requirements analogous to those for tablet

dosage forms [6]. This indicates insufficient differentiation within pharmacopeial approaches depending on the type of dosage form and the mechanism of active substance release.

Among the examined dosage forms, the dissolution test is most thoroughly regulated for medicinal chewing gums. In many pharmacopoeias, with the exception of the Chinese Pharmacopoeia 2020, a separate general pharmacopeial article regulates the testing of the release of active substances from chewing gums. This article is harmonized between the State Pharmacopoeia of the Russian Federation XV, USP 46/NF 41, and JP XVIII, which indicates a high level of consistency in approaches. The methodology involves simulating the chewing process using specialized devices and enables a more accurate assessment of release kinetics. Nonetheless, even in this case, limitations persist: phosphate buffer at pH 6.0 is recommended as the dissolution medium, which only partially simulates the conditions of the oral cavity and fails to account for the variability in the composition and properties of saliva [4–8].

The obtained data indicate that current pharmacopeial requirements for solid dosage forms designed to disintegrate or release active substances in the oral cavity either do not mandate dissolution testing or rely on methodological approaches that do not consider the specific conditions of their application. Such factors include the pH of saliva, its viscosity, surface tension, as well as differences between stimulated and unstimulated salivation. Neglecting these factors may reduce the extent to which in vitro results correspond to the actual conditions of active substance release and local action manifestation in the oral cavity.

Accordingly, the development of a specialized dissolution test for solid pharmaceutical forms intended for local action in the oral cavity is justified. Such a test needs to be adapted to the physiological parameters of saliva and consider the specific characteristics of disintegration, dissolution, and release of active substances under conditions closely approximating in vivo. The proposed approach may provide a foundation for enhancing pharmacopeial standardization and improving the adequacy of quality assessment for this group of medicinal products.

Conclusion

The analysis performed demonstrated the lack of a unified pharmacopeial approach to dissolution testing for solid dosage forms intended for administration in the oral cavity. Current methodologies insufficiently account for the physiological characteristics of the oral cavity, including the differences in pH between unstimulated and stimulated saliva (6.97 and 7.40, respectively), as well as its viscosity and surface tension. This substantiates the need for the development of a specialized dissolution test that more accurately replicates the conditions of active substance release in vivo.

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THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE USE OF POTASSIUM-MINERAL SLUDGE, A BY-PRODUCT OF THE PRODUCTION OF POTASSIUM CHLORIDE, IN POTATO CULTIVATION TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract. *This paper presents the results of research on the effectiveness of using potassium-mineral sludge (PMS), a by-product of potassium production, in combination with increasing doses of poultry manure as a potassium fertilizer and chemical ameliorant on sod-podzolic soils within a potato agrocenosis, considering both residual effects and repeated application. An increase in potato yield was observed both when using sludge in its pure form and in combination with poultry manure. An increase in potato tuber yield of 39–47% was achieved using PMS in its pure form at 150 kg K₂O/ha, as well as in combination at 60 kg K₂O/ha with 15 t/ha of poultry manure. The marketable fraction yield of potato tubers ranged from 84 to 88%.*

Keywords: *ameliorant, potassium-containing fertilizer, potassium-mineral sludge, soil fertility, potato, yield*

One of the main sources of potassium for plants is potassium fertilizers, which are used both in basal applications and as top-dressings for all crops. Currently, in domestic agriculture, potassium is mainly applied in the form of complex fertilizers, which do not always ensure balanced potassium nutrition for plants, and therefore do not guarantee a sustainable increase in yield and product quality (1).

Potassium chloride is also a widely used potassium fertilizer. It is obtained from mineral raw material – sylvinite, which represents a mechanical mixture of potassium and sodium chlorides. The main by-product of potassium fertilizer production is PMS, with a specific yield of 0.6 m³ per 1 t of finished product. The use of PMS as a mineral potassium fertilizer is recommended [2–3].

At present, none of the developed methods for the utilization of GMS has been implemented at an industrial scale. One of the obstacles is its high moisture content (70–80%) and fine particle size. However, if PMS is subjected to dehydration, its composition will approximate that of marls (4).

Research methodology: The field experiment with PMS was established at the experimental site of the Perm Research Institute of Agriculture on potatoes (2023). The soil is sod-podzolic, weakly podzolized, heavy loam, humus content 2.6%, pH_{KCl} 5.4, available phosphorus and potassium contents are 172 and 152 mg/kg, respectively, the sum of exchangeable bases – 21 meq/kg of soil.

The aim of the research was the agroecological assessment and determination of the biological effectiveness of the application of PMS as potassium nutrition for potatoes, taking into account soil and climatic conditions (5–6). The experimental design included 15 treatments:

1. Control (without fertilizers)
2. PMS 60 kg K₂O/ha (0.7 t/ha in actual weight)
3. PMS 90 kg K₂O/ha (1.0 t/ha in actual weight)
4. PMS 120 kg K₂O/ha (1.4 t/ha in actual weight)
5. PMS 150 kg K₂O/ha (1.7 t/ha in physical weight)
6. Poultry manure 90 kg N/ha (7 t/ha in physical weight) – Background 1
7. Background 1 + PMS 60 kg K₂O/ha
8. Background 1 + PMS 90 kg K₂O/ha
9. Background 1 + PMS 120 kg K₂O/ha
10. Background 1 + PMS 150 kg K₂O/ha
11. Poultry manure 180 kg N/ha (15 t/ha in physical weight) – Background 2
12. Background 2 + PMS 60 kg K₂O/ha
13. Background 2 + PMS 90 kg K₂O/ha
14. Background 2 + PMS 120 kg K₂O/ha
15. Background 2 + PMS 150 kg K₂O/ha

The experiment used poultry manure, the accumulation of which increases the level of environmental hazard, which is significantly relevant for addressing the

region's ecological issues. The calculation of PMS doses was based on potassium content, while doses of poultry manure were calculated based on nitrogen content. PMS and poultry manure were applied in the fall before plowing, to a depth of 22 cm. The object of the study was the Gala potato variety. The plots were arranged sequentially. The total plot area is 48 m².

PMS contains 8–12 % potassium, 5–7 % sodium, up to 25 % calcium and can be applied as a potassium fertilizer with a ameliorative effect (Table 1).

Table 1 – Analysis results of PMS (moisture content 20%)

pH (water)	Organic matter sub- stance	Total nitrogen	Phos- phorus total	Potassi- um total	Avail- able phos- phorus,	N-NH ₄	N-NO ₃	Sodium exchange- able cations	CaCO ₃ + MgCO ₃
6.9	5.9	0.35	0.7	8.7	0.4	16.3	63.1	8.8	23.0

Soil sample analyses were performed using the following methods: determination of salt pH – by potentiometric method (GOST 26483–85); hydrolytic acidity by Kappen method – potentiometric method (GOST 26212–84); sum of exchangeable bases by Kappen-Gilkowitz method – titrimetric method (GOST 27821–88); exchangeable calcium and magnesium by TsINAO method (GOST 26487–85); mobile phosphorus and mobile potassium by Kirsanov method modified by TsINAO (GOST 26207–91); humus content by Tyurin method modified by TsINAO (GOST 26213–91); exchangeable ammonium by TsINAO method (GOST 26489–85); nitrates by ionometric method (GOST 26951–86); exchangeable sodium (GOST 26950–86).

Discussion of results

The research results demonstrated that under the arid conditions of 2023 a statistically significant increase in potato yield of 39–47% was achieved using PMS at a dose of 150 kg K₂O/ha (treatment variant 5) and with the application of PMS at 60 kg K₂O/ha combined with poultry manure at 15 t/ha (treatment variant 12). The yield of the marketable tuber fraction in these treatments was 84–88% compared to 68% in the control treatment (Table 2).

Table 2 – Effect of PMS on the yield of Gala potato variety

Treatment	Yield, t/ha	+/- compared to control	+/- compared to background
Control (without fertilizers)	14.5	-	-
PMS 60 kg K ₂ O/ha	16.7	2.2	-

PMS 90 kg K ₂ O/ha	18.7	4.2	-
PMS 120 kg K ₂ O/ha	19.5	5.0	-
PMS 150 kg K ₂ O/ha	21.3	6.8	-
Poultry manure 90 kg N/ha (7 t/ha in physical weight) – Background 1	16.8	2.3	-
Background 1 + PMS 60 kg K ₂ O/ ha	18.6	4.1	1.8
Background 1 + PMS 90 kg K ₂ O/ ha	19.6	5.1	2.8
Background 1 + PMS 120 kg K ₂ O/ ha	19.4	4.9	2.6
Background 1 + PMS 150 kg K ₂ O/ ha	23.1	8.6	6.3
Poultry manure 180 kg N/ha (15 t/ha in physical weight) – Back- ground 2	18.5	4.0	-
Background 2 + PMS 60 kg K ₂ O/ ha	25.8	11.3	7.3
Background 2 + PMS 90 kg K ₂ O/ ha	22.1	7.6	3.6
Background 2 + PMS 120 kg K ₂ O/ ha	23.5	9.0	5.0
Background 2 + PMS 150 kg K ₂ O/ ha	26.1	11.6	7.6
NSP ₀₅	-	6.5	

The tuber yield of potatoes in the PMS treatment at a rate of 150 kg K₂O/ha was 21.3 t/ha, representing an increase of 6.8 t/ha, or 47%. The yield in the treatment “background 2 + PMS 60 kg K₂O/ha” amounted to 25.8 t/ha, an increase over the background of 7.3 t/ha, or 39%. The maximum tuber yields, 25.8 and 26.1 t/ha, were recorded in the treatments “background 2 + PMS 60 kg K₂O/ha” and “background 2 + PMS 150 kg K₂O/ha”, respectively. The use of poultry manure alone under the year’s dry conditions was ineffective, with the obtained tuber yield increases of 2.3–4.0 t/ha being statistically insignificant.

The increase in potato yield in variants 5 and 12 was attributable to an increase in tuber mass per bush and per tuber, as well as to the number of tubers per bush (Table 3).

Table 3 – Effect of PMS on the structure of potato yield

Treatment	Tuber mass, g/ bush	Number of tubers, pcs/bush	Average tuber weight, g	Marketable fraction, %
Control (without fertilizers)	437	10.0	42	68
PMS 60 kg K ₂ O/ha	547	9.1	59	83
PMS 90 kg K ₂ O/ha	561	7.9	71	86
PMS 120 kg K ₂ O/ha	533	10.8	48	75
PMS 150 kg K ₂ O/ha	672	12.0	56	84
Poultry manure 90 kg N/ha – Background 1	494	8.5	58	86
Background 1 + PMS 60 kg K ₂ O/ha	571	11.6	50	80
Background 1 + PMS 90 kg K ₂ O/ha	597	10.6	56	86
Background 1 + PMS 120 kg K ₂ O/ha	463	9.9	47	77
Background 1 + PMS 150 kg K ₂ O/ha	657	10.9	63	90
Poultry manure 180 kg N/ha – Background 2	427	7.5	57	74
Background 2 + PMS 60 kg K ₂ O/ha	790	12.6	62	88
Background 2 + PMS 90 kg K ₂ O/ha	639	12.2	51	76
Background 2+PMS 120 kg K ₂ O/ha	594	9.5	62	88
Background 2+PMS 150 kg K ₂ O/ha	783	11.2	70	94
NSP ₀₅	177	2.6	11	7

The yield of the marketable tuber fraction was 84% in variant 5 and 88% in variant 12. The highest yield – 94% – was obtained in variant 15. ‘Background 2 + PMS 150 kg K₂O/ha.’

Quality assessment of the produce showed that the maximum content of dry matter and starch in potato tubers was recorded in the control variant – 23.8% and 16.6%, respectively (Table 4). When all types of fertilizers were used in the experiment, the parameters decreased.

Table 4 – Influence of PMS on the quality of tubers of the Gala potato variety

Treatment	Content in tubers		
	dry matter, %	starch, %	nitrate, mg/kg
Control (without fertilizers)	23.8	16.6	392
PMS 60 kg K ₂ O/ha	18.8	15.6	560
PMS 90 kg K ₂ O/ha	21.0	13.7	304
PMS 120 kg K ₂ O/ha	20.6	14.6	329
PMS 150 kg K ₂ O/ha	20.6	13.7	402

Treatment	Content in tubers		
	dry matter, %	starch, %	nitrates, mg/kg
Poultry manure 90 kg N/ha (7 t/ha in physical weight) – Background 1	20.9	14.7	461
Background 1 + PMS 60 kg K ₂ O/ha	20.0	12.9	864
Background 1 + PMS 90 kg K ₂ O/ha	19.1	12.7	658
Background 1 + PMS 120 kg K ₂ O/ha	21.3	14.3	632
Background 1 + PMS 150 kg K ₂ O/ha	19.0	12.7	621
Poultry manure 180 kg N/ha (15 t/ha in physical weight) – Background 2	21.3	13.3	566
Background 2 + PMS 60 kg K ₂ O/ha	18.1	12.4	1370
Background 2 + PMS 90 kg K ₂ O/ha	20.5	13.8	663
Background 2 + PMS 120 kg K ₂ O/ha	19.4	14.1	701
Background 2 + PMS 150 kg K ₂ O/ha	19.1	12.3	652
NSP ₀₅	2.3	1.8	612

The application of PMS contributed to an improvement in the pH_{KCL} indicator and a significant increase in the content of available potassium in the soil in the 0–20 cm layer (Table 5).

Table 5 – Effect of PMS on the agrochemical properties of sod-podzolic soil (0–20 cm)

Treatment	pH _{KCL}	N-NH ₄	N-NO ₃	N _{min}	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	Total salinity, mS/cm
		mg/kg					
1	5.3	9.0	15.3	24.2	206	169	0.07
2	5.6	8.5	24.0	32.4	231	175	0.07
3	5.6	7.6	25.3	32.9	186	177	0.09
4	5.6	9.3	25.8	35.1	234	185	0.08
5	5.6	12.7	23.6	36.3	243	340	0.10
6	5.4	8.3	22.1	30.4	198	192	0.09
7	5.6	7.0	41.3	48.3	221	179	0.11
8	5.6	22.3	76.7	99.0	185	228	0.19
9	5.7	38.8	34.8	73.5	230	206	0.15
10	5.6	11.8	59.1	70.9	303	255	0.16
11	5.4	40.6	74.8	115.4	195	232	0.18
12	5.6	10.4	66.4	76.8	202	171	0.14
13	5.6	5.1	60.1	65.2	202	172	0.15
14	5.6	40.5	58.1	98.5	223	223	0.17
15	5.6	43.5	105.9	149.4	414	280	0.23
NSP ₀₅	0.1	23.2	18.9	34.5	80	72	0.04

Application of poultry manure at a dose of 15 t/ha (variant 11) resulted in a significant increase in soil mineral nitrogen (by 4.9 times), including both ammonium and nitrate forms. Accumulation of mineral nitrogen was observed with the use of PMS at doses of 90–150 kg K₂O/ha under background treatment 1 (variants 8–10) and at a dose of 150 kg K₂O/ha under background treatment 2 (variant 15). The content of available phosphorus in the soil also increased when PMS was applied at a dose of 150 kg K₂O/ha under background treatments 1 and 2 (variants 10 and 15). The content of available potassium in the soil increased significantly with the application of PMS at a dose of 150 kg K₂O/ha from 169 mg/kg (control) to 340 mg/kg (2-fold).

Under repeated application and residual effects of PMS, no further significant changes were observed in soil pH_{KCl}, hydrolytic acidity, total exchangeable bases, or in the content of exchangeable calcium, magnesium, and mobile phosphorus compounds. An increase in soil content of mobile potassium compounds was recorded (averaged across factor B) upon application of PMS at a dose of 150 kg K₂O/ha, from 178 to 320 mg/kg (Tables 6–7).

Table 6 – Effect of PMS on soil acidity (2024)

Factor A	Factor B* Residual effect	Factor C		Mean per factor	
		Repeated application	A	B	
Control (without fertilizers)	0	5.61	5.70	5.73	5.66
	60	5.80	5.82		5.74
	90	5.74	5.75		5.76
	120	5.71	5.73		5.76
	150	5.67	5.72		5.74
Poultry manure 90 kg N/ha (7.5 t/ha in physical weight)	0	5.72	5.64	5.70	-
	60	5.62	5.68		-
	90	5.68	5.70		-
	120	5.75	5.82		-
	150	5.72	5.72		-
Poultry manure 180 kg N/ha (15 t/ha in physical weight)	0	5.69	5.61	5.77	-
	60	5.76	5.73		-
	90	5.84	5.86		-
	120	5.70	5.85		-
	150	5.83	5.81		-
Average for factor C		5.72	5.74	-	-
NSP ₀₅					
Factor and interaction		A	Fφ<Fτ		
B and AB		Fφ<Fτ			
C and AC, BC, ABC		Fφ<Fτ			

Factor A	Factor B* Residual effect	Factor C		Mean per factor	
		Repeated application	A	B	
For individual medium plots II order III order	I order	0.34			
		0.24			
		0.11			

* – doses of GMS recalculated as K₂O, kg/ha

Table 7 – Influence of PMS on the content of available potassium, mg/kg, 0–20 cm (2024)

Factor A	Factor B* Residual effect	Factor C		Mean per factor	
		Repeated application	A	B	
Control (without fertilizers)	0	160	146	209	178
	60	166	176		189
	90	162	148		161
	120	177	195		189
	150	347	416		320
Poultry manure 90 kg N/ha (7.5 t/ha in physical weight)	0	159	172	212	-
	60	192	207		-
	90	156	222		-
	120	190	197		-
	150	319	309		-
Poultry manure 180 kg N/ha (15 t/ha in physical weight)	0	221	212	201	-
	60	186	211		-
	90	147	135		-
	120	176	199		-
	150	256	272		-
Average for factor C		201	214	-	-
NSP ₀₅					
Factor and interaction B and AB C AC, BC, ABC	A	F ϕ <F _T			
		23			
		16			
		F ϕ <F _T			
For individual medium plots II order III order	I order	63			
		57			
		60			

* – doses of PMS recalculated as K₂O, kg/ha

Application of poultry manure at doses of 7.5 and 15 t/ha (factor A) contributed to an increase in soil mineral nitrogen content from 10.2 to 12.9–17.2 mg/kg, respectively (Table 8).

Table 8 – Effect of PMS on mineral nitrogen content, mg/kg, 0–20 cm (2024)

Factor A	Factor B* Residual effect of PMS	Factor C		Mean per factor	
		Repeated application of PMS	A	B	
Control (without fertilizers)	0	12.5	12.5	10.2	14.6
	60	13.0	8.2	14.8	
	90	7.9	5.7	11.7	
	120	9.1	5.5	10.9	
	150	13.1	14.8	15.3	
Poultry manure 90 kg N/ha (7.5 t/ha in physical weight)	0	14.5	13.7	12.9	-
	60	12.7	16.2	-	
	90	10.2	13.8	-	
	120	9.2	12.5	-	
	150	10.5	15.5	-	
Poultry manure 180 kg N/ha (15 t/ha in physical weight)	0	17.2	17.2	17.2	-
	60	18.6	20.1	-	
	90	15.6	16.8	-	
	120	14.0	15.1	-	
	150	16.0	21.7	-	
Mean for factor C		12.9	14.0	-	-
NSP ₀₅					
Factor and interaction	A		2.3		
	B		2.1		
	AB		F ϕ <F τ		
	C, AC, BC		0.8		
	ABC		F ϕ <F τ		
For private subsidiary plots	I order		7.4		
	II order		5.2		
	III order		2.9		

* – doses of PMS recalculated as K₂O, kg/ha

The application of PMS contributed to an increase in exchangeable sodium in the soil (Table 9).

Table 9 – Influence of PMS on exchangeable sodium content, mg/kg, 0–20 cm

Factor A	Factor B* Residual effect of PMS	Factor C		Mean per factor	
		Repeated application of PMS	A	B	
Control (without fertilizers)	0	41	43	80	40
	60	37	90	67	
	90	40	87	67	
	120	55	122	87	
	150	132	160	117	
Poultry manure 90 kg N/ha (7.5 t/ha in physical weight)	0	42	46	78	-
	60	47	117	-	
	90	47	98	-	
	120	58	125	-	
	150	109	91	-	
Poultry manure 180 kg N/ha (15 t/ha in physical weight)	0	34	36	69	-
	60	40	73	-	
	90	54	78	-	
	120	60	100	-	
	150	74	139	-	
Mean for factor C		58	94	-	-
NSP ₀₅					
Factor and interaction	A		F ϕ <F τ		
	B and AB		20		
	C and AC, BC, ABC		5		
For individual medi- um plots	I order		42		
	II order		50		
	III order		18		

* – doses of PMS recalculated as K₂O, kg/ha

Under conditions of residual effect, an increase was observed in the variant «PMS 150 kg K₂O/ha» when applied in pure form and with a background application of poultry manure at 7.5 t/ha by 2.6–3.2 times (by 67–91 mg/kg). Upon re-application, an increase in exchangeable sodium compounds was observed with all doses of PMS, ranging from 2.0 to 3.9 times (an increase of 37–116 mg/kg). An increase in soil sodium content according to factor BC was observed with PMS application at doses of 60–150 kg K₂O/ha, increasing from 40 to 67–117 mg/kg.

A trend toward a decrease in sodium content was observed when PMS was applied in combination with poultry manure.

No significant effect of PMS on chloride content in the soil was observed. The total soil salinity indicator varied within the range of 0.06–0.15 mS/cm.

Thus, applying PMS at a dose of 150 kg K₂O/ha and 60 kg K₂O/ha combined with poultry manure at 15 t/ha resulted in a potato tuber yield increase of 39–47%. The commercial fraction yield of potato tubers was 84–88% (control variant – 68%). The yield increase when using PMS at 150 kg K₂O/ha combined with 15 t/ha poultry manure amounted to 41%, with the commercial fraction yield of potato tubers reaching 94%. The increase in potato yield was achieved due to the increase in tuber mass per bush, individual tuber mass, and the number of tubers per bush.

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THE EFFECTIVENESS OF NATURAL SYNNYRITES AS A POTASH FERTILIZER AND CHEMICAL MELIORANT IN THE POTATO AGROCENOSIS

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Abstract. *The article presents the results of agroecological field studies on sod-podzolic soils concerning the effectiveness of natural synnyrites as potash fertilizers and chemical ameliorants in the potato agrocenosis. A positive influence of synnyrites on the formation of potato tuber yield and their quality was demonstrated. A statistically significant yield increase of 17.0–29.7% in potato was obtained with the application of synnyrites at doses of 90–120 kg K₂O/ha, respectively. The yield of marketable potato tuber fractions reached 83–88% (compared to 68% in the control). The application of synnyrites contributed to an increase in soil pH (measured in KCl) and to higher contents of available potassium in the 0–20 cm soil layer.*

Keywords: *synnyrites, potash fertilizers, ameliorant, yield, soil fertility, soil acidity, potato*

Natural potassium polymineral salts (sylvinite, sylvine, carnallite, kainite, langbeinite, polyhalite, synnyrite) serve as raw materials for the production of

potash fertilizers and contain, in addition to potassium, a range of micronutrients essential for plant growth.

The application of potassium fertilizers, as a mandatory agrotechnical practice to enhance soil fertility and increase agricultural crop yields, promotes improved plant growth and development, enhances the quality of crop production, and increases crop resistance to adverse anthropogenic factors 2–4. The application of nitrogen and phosphorus fertilizers alone, without compensating for potassium removal, results in a reduction of exchangeable and non-exchangeable potassium compounds in the topsoil layer (0–20 cm), thereby diminishing soil fertility 5–6.

Potato is among the most responsive crops to potassium fertilization and represents one of the primary food, fodder, and industrial crops in Russia and globally, ranking fourth after wheat, rice, and maize. A majority of scientific studies [7–9] have documented the positive impact of potassium fertilizers on increasing potato yields and enhancing the quality parameters of tubers.

At present, the development of advanced cultivation technologies that consider the optimization of mineral nutrition, including potassium, remains a relevant research focus. One of the promising representatives of potassium fertilizers is a chloride-free potassium fertilizer produced from natural synnyrite minerals. To address the stated objective, long-term comprehensive studies were conducted on the effectiveness of synnyrites applied in increasing doses as potassium fertilizers within the potato agrocenosis.

Synnyrites are a hololeucocratic dense rock composed of (wt.%): potassium feldspar – 55–85, calcsilicate – up to 35, nepheline – up to 10, and biotite – 1–2. The mineral contains ultrapotassic syenites and synnyrites, which can serve as raw materials for the production of chloride-free potassium fertilizers and chemical ameliorants.

Synnyrites are characterized by a high silicon content, an essential biogenic macronutrient involved in the formation of plant productivity and structural components. Silicon contributes to stem strengthening and the optimization of morphometric parameters, actively participates in metabolic processes including energy metabolism, and enhances plant resistance to biotic and abiotic stresses as well as pathogenic phytopathogens.

The relevance of the studies conducted, which are aimed at developing effective methods for increasing soil fertility, improving the potassium regime of sod-podzolic soils, and enhancing potato yields through the use of unconventional natural sources of mineral nutrition – ground synnyrites – is indisputable. These studies gain particular significance under the current complex economic conditions, import substitution policies, and extreme situations induced by ecological stresses.

Research methodology: The objective of the research was to conduct a comparative evaluation of the effectiveness of various types of potash fertilizers in

potato cultivation technology depending on fertilizer rates. The research tasks included studying the effects of ground synnyrites on the agrochemical properties of sod-podzolic soils, as well as on the yield and quality of potato tubers.

The scientific novelty of the conducted research consists in the experimental substantiation of the feasibility of using synnyrites to increase the potassium level in soils. The availability of available forms of silicon in sod-podzolic soil was evaluated, and the influence of this factor on the formation of potato tuber quality was identified. The application of potassium-silicon-containing fertilizers derived from natural synnyrite ore allows a novel approach to improving both the potassium status of sod-podzolic soils and the supply of available silicon to enhance the yield and quality of potato tubers.

Experimental design:

1. Control (without fertilizers)
2. N60P60 – background fertilization
3. N60P60+ K90 (KCl)
4. N60P60 + K90 (synnyrites)
5. N60P60+ K120 (KCl)
6. N60P60 + K₁₂₀ (synnyrites)

Dosage calculations of synnyrites were performed based on their potassium content. Synnyrites and potassium chloride were applied in autumn before plowing (to a depth of 22 cm). Plots were arranged sequentially. The study object was the Gala potato variety. Planting pattern – 30×70 cm. Soil treatment followed standard practices for the Moscow region. The total plot area is 50 m².

The soil of the plot is sod-podzolic, medium loamy, with medium humus content (2.2%), slightly acidic reaction (pH_{KCl} 5.1), medium mobile phosphorus content (152 mg/kg), and low mobile potassium content (95 mg/kg).

Discussion of results:

According to quantitative chemical analysis, the mass fraction of total potassium oxide K₂O in synnyrite was 17.82% (Table 1). The main elements of the ore are silicon Si, aluminum Al, potassium K, calcium Ca, and iron Fe, associated with the principal rock-forming minerals: microcline, kalsilite, and biotite.

Table 1 – Quantitative chemical composition of the original ore

K ₂ O	Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	P ₂ O ₅	Fe ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	ZnO	TiO ₂	S _{TOTAL}	MnO
17.82	21.3	1.05	0.23	0.026	1.97	56.9	0.005	0.13	0.015	0.047

Potassium in synnyrite is present in a water-insoluble form, which prevents its leaching from the arable layer. The content of available potassium ranges from 16.5 to 20%. The use of dry ore milling is necessitated by the requirement to preserve soluble potassium oxide K₂O in the final product.

Application of synnyrites at doses of 90 and 120 kg K₂O/ha (treatments 4 and 6) resulted in a statistically significant increase in potato tuber yield (Table 2).

Table 2 – Effect of synnyrites on potato yield (2025)

Treatment		Yield, t/ha	Total, t/ha	
1.	Control (without fertilizers)	18.4	-	%, relative to the background
2.	N60P60 – background fertilization	22.9	4.5	-
3.	N60P60+ K90 (KCl)	26.1	7.7	14.0
4.	N60P60 + K90 (synnyrites)	26.8	8.4	17.0
5.	N60P60+ K120 (KCl)	28.8	10.4	25.8
6.	N60P60 + K120 (synnyrites)	29.7	14.3	29.7
	LSD 0.05	3.2		

The potato tuber yield in the treatment variant with the application of 90 kg K₂O/ha in the form of synnyrites amounted to 26.8 t/ha, representing a total increase of 8.4 t/ha, which corresponds to 17.0% relative to the background. The yield in the treatment with the same dose of potassium applied as potassium chloride was 26.1 t/ha, representing an increase of 7.7 t/ha, which corresponds to 14.0% above the control.

With increasing doses of potash fertilizers, potato yield increased; however, the advantage of synnyrites was preserved. In the treatment with the application of 120 kg K₂O/ha as synnyrites, tuber yield reached 29.7 t/ha, with a total increase of 14.3 t/ha, corresponding to 29.7% above the control. The yield in the variant with the same potassium dose applied as potassium chloride was 28.8 t/ha, representing an increase of 10.4 t/ha, or 25.8% relative to the control.

The use of synnyrites was highly effective; their impact on potato yield formation surpassed that of potassium chloride. The increase in potato yield observed in treatments 4 and 6 was achieved due to increases in tuber mass per plant, individual tuber mass, and the number of tubers per plant (Table 3).

Table 3 – Effect of various forms of potash fertilizers on the structure of potato yield

Treatment	Mass		Number of tubers, pcs per bush	Marketable fraction, %
	of tubers, g per bush	of tuber, g		
Control (no fertilizers)	570	51	11.2	63
N ₉₀ P ₉₀	737	60	13.0	81
N ₉₀ P ₉₀ + K ₉₀ (KCl)	758	65	14.2	78
N ₉₀ P ₉₀ + K ₉₀ (synnyrites)	793	70	14.6	84

Treatment	Mass		Number of tubers, pcs per bush	Marketable fraction, %
	of tubers, g per bush	of tuber, g		
$N_{90}P_{90}+K_{120}$ (KCl)	896	74	13.9	85
$N_{90}P_{90}+K_{120}$ (synnyrites)	906	77	14.6	88
LSD 0.05	102	12	2.9	8

The marketable fraction yield of potato tubers amounted to 78% in variant 3 and 84% in variant 4 with the application of synnyrites. The maximum yield of the marketable fraction, 88%, was obtained in treatment 6 “background + synnyrites 120 kg K_2O /ha.”

The highest contents of dry matter and starch in potato tubers were observed in the control treatment (without fertilizers) – 20.8% and 15.4%, respectively (Table 4).

Table 4 – Effect of potassium fertilizers on the quality of potato tubers

Treatment	Dry matter, %	Starch, %	Nitrates, mg/kg
Control (no fertilizers)	20.1	15.1	161
$N_{90}P_{90}$	20.6	14.3	204
$N_{90}P_{90}+K_{90}$ (KCl)	21.2	14.0	215
$N_{90}P_{90}+K_{90}$ (synnyrites)	21.5	14.5	196
$N_{90}P_{90}+K_{120}$ (KCl)	21.8	13.5	243
$N_{90}P_{90}+K_{120}$ (synnyrites)	22.2	14.5	209
LSD 0.05	2.2	1.4	33
MAC	-	-	250

In tubers from variants where synnyrites were applied, a reduction in nitrate content was noted compared to analogous variants treated with potassium chloride. However, no variant exhibited levels exceeding the MAC.

The use of synnyrites contributed to the improvement of the soil acid-base balance, with a statistically significant increase in the pH_{KCl} value from 5.1 units (variant 1, control) to 5.7 units. (dose of synnyrites 120 kg K_2O /ha). The increase in the pH_{KCl} value shifted towards a near-neutral range with increasing doses of synnyrites.

The content of mobile potassium in the soil significantly increased following the application of potash fertilizers. However, when using synnyrites at both 90 kg K_2O /ha and 120 kg K_2O /ha doses, the pH_{KCl} value did not exceed those observed with potassium chloride applied at the same doses. However, unlike treatments with potassium chloride application, a further improvement in the soil potassium regime is expected due to the prolonged effect of natural synnyrites.

Conclusion

The research results demonstrated that the application of potash fertilizer derived from natural synnyrites resulted in a significant increase in potato yield of 17–29.7%. The marketable fraction of potato tuber yield in these treatments was 83–88% (control variant – 68%). The increase in potato yield was due to an increase in the mass of tubers per bush, the mass of a single tuber, and the number of tubers per bush. The application of synnyrites contributed to the improvement of the pH_{KCL} value and to the increase in the content of available potassium in the soil (0–20 cm layer).

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JUSTIFICATION FOR THE USE OF ACTIVE PRECHAMBER FOR A MODER GAS PISTON ENGINE

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An overview and analysis of modern ignition methods for gaseous fuels used in moder gas piston engines is provided. As active prechamber has been developed for gas piston engine GPD-185. The first results of combustion simulation tests of developed prechamber are presented.

Keywords: *prechamber, active prechamber, gas piston engine, ignition system, combustion simulation tests.*

In the modern world, gas-piston engines represent one of the key directions in the development of engine engineering. This technology is of particular importance for distributed power generation, railway transport, and heavy-duty machinery, where gas-piston engines successfully replace diesel engines, providing fuel savings and reducing harmful emissions.

In the context of increasingly stringent environmental regulations and the transition to low-carbon energy, the use of natural gas as a motor fuel is becoming especially relevant. This is обусловлено a lower level of CO, CO₂, NO_x, and particulate matter (PM) emissions compared to conventional gasoline and diesel engines.

The development of the modern gas-piston engine GPD-185 is being carried out by LLC “UDMZ” in collaboration with the Advanced Engineering School “Heart of the Urals.” One of the key areas of this project is the creation of a reliable ignition system, as it directly determines operational stability, fuel efficiency, and environmental performance of the engine. Unlike diesel engines, where combustion occurs due to auto-ignition of the fuel, gas engines require a reliable

external ignition source. This issue becomes particularly critical when operating on ultra-lean mixtures with an excess air ratio $\alpha > 1.6$, which are used to improve efficiency and reduce emissions [1, 2].

In this regard, recent years have seen an active search for effective methods of combustion initiation in large-bore gas engines. Study [3] demonstrated that for engines with a cylinder diameter exceeding 150 mm, pre-chamber jet ignition is the most promising approach. This method ensures higher values of brake mean effective pressure (BMEP) compared to other concepts (Fig. 1), including spark ignition in an open chamber with a stoichiometric mixture, spark ignition in an open chamber with a lean mixture, and the gas-diesel process. As shown in the figure, the application of pre-chamber jet ignition significantly expands the stable combustion range and improves the efficiency of the working process.

Fig. 1. Efficiency of modern four-stroke gas-fueled engines as a function of cylinder diameter [3]

To systematize existing solutions and identify the most promising option, a comparative assessment of various ignition systems was carried out. Based on the analysis of studies [4–10], Table 1 was compiled, presenting a comparison between a spark plug with an active pre-chamber and spark ignition, laser ignition, corona ignition, and passive pre-chamber jet ignition systems.

The table shows that laser and corona ignition systems, despite achieving high combustion pressure (above 10 MPa), have several limitations for implementation in an engine of the GPD-185: restrictions on cylinder diameter (up to 170 mm) and the lack of implementation using commercially available components. This makes their application in a production engine economically impractical and technologically challenging, despite their evident potential.

In contrast, conventional spark ignition and passive pre-chamber systems are readily available but do not provide the required lean mixture ignition limit (α not exceeding 1.8). Only the active pre-chamber combines three key advantages: high combustion pressure (up to 10 MPa), a wide ignition range ($\alpha = 2.5$), and suitability for cylinder diameters exceeding 170 mm.

It should be noted that the selection of an ignition system must consider a combination of factors, including thermodynamic process parameters, design constraints, and technological feasibility. Thus, the conducted comparative analysis demonstrates that the active pre-chamber is the most preferable solution for the GPD-185 gas-piston engine in terms of ensuring reliable ignition of lean mixtures and practical implementability of the design.

Table 1. Comparative characteristics of ignition systems of various types

Ignition system	Combustion pressure at ignition timing, MPa	Energy input to the mixture, mJ	Lower ignition limit (by α)	Cylinder diameter, mm	Implementation using available components
Spark plug	up to 4	<4	1,6	up to 170	+
Laser ignition system	> 10	20	2,0	up to 170	-
Corona ignition system	> 10	200	2,0	up to 170	-
Spark plug with passive pre-chamber	up to 10	-	1,8	up to 170	+
Spark plug with active pre-chamber	up to 10	-	2,5	>170	+

Thus, the conducted analysis made it possible to formulate the key requirements for the ignition system of the engine under development, which served as the basis for proceeding to the design of an active pre-chamber. Based on the engine's geometric parameters and the requirements for the combustion process, an active pre-chamber design was developed. The design of the developed pre-chamber includes the following components (Fig. 2):

Fig. 2. Active pre-chamber for the GPD-185 gas-piston engine

1. Pre-chamber sleeve – required for installation of the pre-chamber inside the engine and for sealing the entire system.
2. Pre-chamber housing – required for forming the internal volume and assembling all pre-chamber components.
3. Pre-chamber nozzle – required for the formation of jet flames.
4. Gas valve – required for purging the pre-chamber from exhaust gases and filling it with natural gas.
5. Pressure sensor – required for measuring pressure inside the pre-chamber.
6. Spark plug – required for generating a spark to ignite the working mixture inside the pre-chamber.

All structural elements are interconnected and ensure the implementation of a stable ignition process over a wide range of engine operating conditions. During operation, the gas valve supplies natural gas into the internal volume of the pre-chamber, displacing exhaust gases, after which the spark plug initiates ignition of the enriched mixture. The resulting jet flames are discharged through the nozzle orifices into the main combustion chamber, ensuring reliable and volumetric ignition of the lean working mixture. The sleeve provides secure mounting and sealing of the assembly, while the pressure sensor enables real-time monitoring of process stability.

To validate the operability of the developed active pre-chamber and to evaluate the ignition characteristics of lean gas-air mixtures, non-engine experimental studies were carried out using the unique research facility “Vprysk” [11–13], which is equipped with a constant volume combustion chamber and high-speed imaging, as well as instrumentation for recording pressure variations in the chamber.

During the experiments, key parameters of the ignition and combustion process were recorded using high-speed imaging (up to 1000 frames per second), including flame front propagation velocity, combustion pressure dynamics both in the pre-chamber and in the main chamber, and exhaust gas composition. Pressure was measured using piezoelectric pressure sensors installed in both the pre-chamber and the main chamber.

To determine the effect of mixture composition on these parameters, a series of experiments was conducted at different excess air ratio values α using both the active pre-chamber and a conventional spark plug.

Fig. 3. Results of natural gas combustion studies in a constant volume combustion chamber with pre-chamber jet ignition and spark ignition at an initial gas pressure of 0.45 bar and mixture pressure of 4 bar (A), and at an initial gas pressure of 0.45 bar and mixture pressure of 5 bar (B)

The results of the study showed that, for identical mixture compositions, the maximum combustion pressure in pre-chamber jet ignition is reached more than twice as fast as in conventional spark ignition (Fig. 3). This is explained by the formation of multiple ignition sites and an increase in the total flame front area, which leads to an accelerated combustion process.

Thus, pre-chamber jet ignition ensures a more intensive development of the lean gas-air mixture combustion process, which is manifested in an earlier attainment of peak pressure compared to spark ignition.

Conclusion. Based on the results of the analysis of existing methods for ignition and combustion of lean gas-air mixtures in gas-piston engines, the following conclusions have been drawn for application in the domestic GPD-185 gas-piston engine:

1. It has been established that the active pre-chamber provides the best combination of characteristics, ensuring ignition of lean mixtures at excess air ratios up to $\alpha \leq 2.5$, as well as operability at combustion pressures up to 10 MPa, making it preferable for large-bore engines (cylinder diameter > 170 mm).

2. Based on the formulated requirements, an active pre-chamber design for the GPD-185 gas-piston engine has been developed. The design ensures the formation of stable jet flames, efficient ignition of the working mixture, and the possibility of integration into the existing engine configuration.

3. It has been shown that the developed pre-chamber can be installed in the cylinder head in place of a standard diesel injector when converting the engine to gaseous fuel, enabling the implementation of pre-chamber jet ignition with minimal design modifications.

4. The results of non-engine experimental studies of natural gas combustion in a constant volume combustion chamber with pre-chamber jet ignition have confirmed the operability of the proposed solution. The use of an active pre-chamber ensures a more intensive combustion process, and the time to reach peak pressure is reduced by more than two times compared to spark ignition, indicating improved ignition efficiency of lean mixtures.

5. An active pre-chamber of this design can be applied in other large gas-piston engines during the development and modernization of power units operating on natural or associated gas.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF SNAKEHEAD IN THE FOOD INDUSTRY AND ITS USE

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Abstract. *This work considers the significance of Snakehead (genus Channa) as a promising species for aquaculture and the food industry. An analysis of global and regional production was conducted, including a comparative evaluation of the nutritional value of snakehead fish relative to catfish, tilapia, and eel, as well as a study of processing methods and potential applications in the food industry.*

Keywords: *statistics, fish nutritional value, fillet, semi-finished product.*

In the context of global population growth and the rising demand for protein products, the development of aquaculture has gained significant importance. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization, global fish production reached 223.2 million tons, of which more than 135 million tons is accounted for by aquaculture [1]. The relevance of the topic is due to the increase in global demand for high-quality animal protein.

Table 1 – Global fish production (million tons)

Year	2000	2010	2020	2022
Total volume	130	178	214	223
Aquaculture	32	60	110	135
Capture	98	118	104	93

Table 1 demonstrates that aquaculture has become the dominant source of fish.

Traditional species (catfish, tilapia) have reached a high degree of market saturation, necessitating the search for new species.

A promising aquaculture species is the Snakehead (genus *Channa*), distinguished by rapid growth rate, tolerance to unfavorable environmental conditions, and high nutritional value.

The objective of this study is to evaluate the significance of snakehead in the food industry and to analyze the prospects for its utilization.

A comparative analysis of the production volumes and market positions of various fish species demonstrates that representatives of the genus *Tilapia* (*Tilapia*) – approximately 6.3 million tons per year – and the family *Siluridae* – approximately 6.13 million tons per year – hold a dominant position as mass aquaculture species, whereas representatives of the genus *Anguilla* (*Anguilla*) – approximately 0.47 million tons per year – are classified as delicacy products with limited production volumes; At the same time, snakehead (*Channidae*) is characterized by relatively smaller production volumes (0.3–0.4 million tons per year; snakehead is included in the group ‘other freshwater fish’ with a total of approximately 6.04 million tons) [2]. Nevertheless, it is regarded as a promising species with high growth potential within the industry and occupies a significant niche in regional aquaculture [3].

According to the National Statistics Bureau of the Republic of Kazakhstan, in 2025, the volume of fisheries and aquaculture production in the country amounted to 37.13 million tenge, while the total catch of fish and other aquatic animals reached 49.5 thousand units. tons, with production of marketable fish amounting to 22.9 thousand tons.

Table 2 – Volume of products (services) in fisheries and aquaculture in the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2024–2025.

Product volume, tons	2024	2025
Republic of Kazakhstan	27,802,092.2	37,130,184.40
Abai	175,221.7	1,025,456.10
Akmola	554,473.1	623,477.10
Aktobe	1,162,260.1	1,189,649.10

Product volume, tons	2024	2025
Almaty	4,553,339.7	4,715,227.20
Atyrau	1,976,122.8	2,963,322.50
West Kazakhstan	125,330.4	123,387.20
Zhambyl	1,978,197.9	1,675,241.10
Zhetysu	118,565.1	249,566.90
Karaganda	628,508.7	502,672.10
Kostanay	608,809.3	552,017.00
Kyzylorda Region	3,836,330.0	3,557,976.40
Mangystau Region	1,524,648.7	2,483,118.10
Pavlodar Region	1,661,523.3	1,322,702.10
North Kazakhstan Region	555,081.4	1,347,622.00
Turkestan Region	3 536 1012	7,918,280.00
Ulytau	4,921.4	8,492.80
East Kazakhstan	4,571,116.3	6,459,776.8
the city of Almaty	300.0	-
the city of Shymkent	222,241.0	412,200.0

The statistics presented above demonstrate that aquaculture in Kazakhstan is developing and the total catch has been increasing over many years [4].

The common Snakehead (*Channa argus*) is a freshwater ray-finned fish belonging to the family Snakehead. The natural distribution area includes rivers along the western coast of the Sea of Japan. This is a very large fish, capable of reaching up to 85 cm in length and a mass of approximately 10 kg. Snakehead fish is named for its distinctive flattened head with large scales resembling the cephalic plates of snakes [5].

Figure 1 – Common Snakehead. External appearance

The Snakehead (genus *Channa*) is characterized by higher growth rates compared to members of the genus *Tilapia* and comparable parameters to fish of the family *Siluridae*, which is largely attributed to its predatory feeding behavior that promotes the development of muscle tissue with enhanced nutritional and biological value.

The key advantages of this species include rapid growth (up to 1–1.5 kg per year), high survival rate, valuable meat, and tolerance to adverse environmental conditions, whereas its limitations mainly pertain to a limited export market [6]. Aquaculture in the Republic of Kazakhstan is currently in a developing phase. The primary cultured species are carp, trout, and catfish. Snakehead is predominantly distributed in the southern regions of the country and demonstrates potential for commercial cultivation [7, 8].

In the Zhambyl Region, the Mynaral Fish Factory is capable of producing at least 1,500 tons of fish products annually. These are cleaned and processed Balhash Lake fish including pike-perch, common carp, bream, snakehead, asp, and vobla. In addition to fish fillets, the enterprise performs deep processing of raw materials, producing fish bone meal and fish mince. More recently, it has begun exporting fish chipsters and cutlets [9].

Information on the chemical composition of fish for 2025 is provided in recent scientific publications, VNIRO materials, and specialized reference books.

Table 3 – Chemical composition of fish

Product	Water, g	Proteins, g	Fats, g	Ash, g	Mineral substances, mg						Vitamins, mg					Energy value, kcal
					Na	K	Ca	Mg	P	Fe	A	B1	B2	PP	C	
Crucian carp	78.9	17.7	1.8	1.6	100	280	70	25	220	0.87	-	-	-	-	-	87
Carp	77.4	16	5.3	1.3	55	265	35	25	210	0.8	0.02	0.14	0.13	1.5	1.8	112
Bream	77.1	17.1	4.1	1.1	70	265	25	30	220	0.3	0.03	0.12	0.1	2	-	105
Common Carp	78	18.2	2.7	1.1	55	280	35	25	220	0.63	-	-	-	-	-	97
Zander	79.2	18.4	1.1	1.3	35	280	35	25	230	0.5	0.01	0.08	0.11	1	3	84
Catfish	76.7	17.2	5.1	1	50	240	50	20	210	1	0.01	0.19	0.12	0.9	1.2	115
European Perch	79.2	18.5	0.9	1.4	100	280	50	75	270	0.7	-	-	-	-	-	82
Eel	64.0	14.5	30.5	1.0	70	230	20	30	220	0.38	0.8	0.10	0.15	3.2	-	333
Sole	83.2	10.3	5.2	1.3	130	300	30	60	150	0.90	0.02	0.02	0.05	2.9	2.3	88

The fundamental data by I. M. Skurikhina continue to serve as a basis in recent editions [10].

Table 4 – Nutritional value of fish

Parameter	Tilapia	Catfish	Eel	Snakehead
Protein, g	18–20	16–18	14–16	18–20
Fats, g	2–3	5–8	20–30	2–4
Caloric value, kcal	90–100	120–140	250–300	90–110

The analysis shows that the snakehead possesses an optimal balance of protein and fat, characterizing it as a high-protein and low-calorie product.

Snakehead is a promising species for the food industry due to its combination of high nutritional value, biological efficiency, and technological suitability for processing.

Russian scientists investigated the chemical composition of the studied fish species; the data are presented in Table 5.

Table 5 – Chemical composition of muscle tissue of the studied specimens

Fish species	Content, %					
	Water	Dry matter	Protein	Fats	Mineral matter	Carbohydrates
Striped snakehead	77.1 ± 0.09	22.8 ± 0.09	18.4 ± 0.50	1.07 ± 0.11	1.31 ± 0.04	2.11 ± 0.10
Dwarf snakehead	70.8 ± 0.24	29.2 ± 0.24	22.9 ± 0.44	2.21 ± 0.27	1.56 ± 0.12	2.56 ± 0.05
Nile tilapia	78.0 ± 0.19	22.0 ± 0.19	16.5 ± 0.90	2.56 ± 0.51	1.30 ± 0.05	1.56 ± 0.07
Catfish hybrid	70.3 ± 0.18	29.9 ± 0.29	22.7 ± 0.45	2.67 ± 0.43	1.65 ± 0.04	2.87 ± 0.13

Comparative analysis of the obtained data revealed that the highest contents of lipids, mineral substances, and carbohydrates were found in the muscles of the hybrid *Clarias gariepinus* + *Clarias macrocephalus*, whereas the highest protein content was observed in *Channa gachua*. According to lipid content, the examined specimens belong to fish with low lipid levels; *Channa striata* is classified as a lean fish species. The high physiological condition index observed in *Oreochromis niloticus* is related to its elevated water content [11].

The advantage of Snakehead over tilapia lies in the denser structure of the muscle tissue and a more balanced amino acid composition, which enhances its technological and dietary value. Furthermore, compared to tilapia and catfish, Snakehead possesses higher protein quality, and compared to eel, lower fat content, rendering it particularly appealing for dietary and functional nutrition.

At the Educational and Scientific Center for Meat (Fish) Processing and the Public Catering Production Center of Almaty Technological University, experiments on the production of Snakehead products were conducted. During experimental studies on the processing of Snakehead (*Channa argus*), the dynamics of muscle tissue yield depending on the fishing period were investigated. In February, during the processing of an experimental batch weighing 10 kg, the fillet yield amounted to 70%, while the proportion of technological waste did not exceed 30%. During the spring period (March–April), a decrease in the yield of the edible portion to 60.0–65.0% was observed, accompanied by a corresponding increase in the mass of secondary raw materials to 3.5–4.0 kg per 10 kg of initial raw material.

The technological potential of snakehead (*Channa argus*) lies in its high organoleptic and morphological characteristics. The dense consistency of the muscle tissue combined with a low content of intermuscular bones substantially enhances the efficiency of both mechanized and manual processing.

The primary avenues for utilizing this raw material include the production of fillets, stabilized mince, sterilized canned products, and a broad spectrum of molded semi-finished products. Predictive analysis of the products' consumer properties revealed a high commercial appeal of the nugget segment due to dynamic demand, as well as an advantage for cutlet-type products characterized by high juiciness levels. Meanwhile, the development of fish sausage formulations is regarded as a promising niche with high profit margins. Owing to its superior quality characteristics compared to tilapia, greater economic efficiency in comparison with river eel, and competitiveness relative to catfish species, snakehead is a strategically significant species for diversifying aquaculture in the Republic of Kazakhstan and for the introduction of innovative food products with high nutritional value.

For the Republic of Kazakhstan, the development of Snakehead aquaculture may become one of the directions for diversifying the fish industry, enabling an expansion of the raw material base of the fish sector and improving food security.

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USE OF SATELLITE MONITORING TO IMPROVE WEATHER FORECASTING FOR THE SAFETY OF NAVIGATION

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Abstract. Growing trade volumes, intense shipping traffic, and the optimization of fuel consumption and sea voyage times require accurate weather forecasting throughout the route. The use of space sensing to improve weather forecasts is an integrated field of research that lies at the intersection of meteorology, oceanology, atmospheric physics, space technology and information technology [1].

Space sensing methods and technologies allow for more accurate planning of transit routes and minimizing the impact on marine ecosystems by reducing harmful emissions.

Keywords: Artificial Earth satellites, weather monitoring, scatterometers, altimeters, radiometers, routing, tropical cyclones.

Remote sensing of the Earth (system types, see Table 1, [2]) from space has revolutionized the monitoring of the ocean-atmosphere system, providing unique opportunities for global observations. This is intensively used in marine meteorology and oceanography to improve the safety of navigation.

Active and passive sensors (scatterometers, altimeters, radiometers) provide a comprehensive understanding of the ocean-atmosphere system:

1. Satellite coverage of the hard-to-reach areas to study global processes (El Niño or climate change).
2. Microwave technologies provide all-weather observations to monitor extreme weather events;

3. Satellites measure many parameters simultaneously, allowing for a comprehensive study of the ocean-atmosphere system;
4. The integration of data into numerical models has improved the accuracy of weather forecasts, which is especially important for navigation;
5. Satellites help monitor long-term climate changes such as rising sea levels and shrinking sea ice;

Table 1 – Satellite measurement products

Devices	Types of maps	Measured and studied parameters
Scatterometers	Wind maps	Wind speed and direction
IR and microwave radiometers	Ocean Surface Temperature maps, global salinity distribution maps	Ocean surface temperature, global monitoring with an accuracy of 0.5 °C, study of temperature fronts and upwellings, ocean surface salinity)
Altimeters	Sea surface height maps, sea current maps, sea ice thickness maps	Sea surface height, wave and current directions, ice thickness
Microwave radiometers and SAR	Cloud cover and precipitation maps. Sea ice concentration maps.	Water vapor content in the atmosphere, monitoring of tropical cyclones. Sea ice concentration, ice type, ice movement; monitoring of seasonal changes in the ice cover

In navigation, the products are used to improve safety, route planning and monitoring of wind, waves, tropical cyclones (see Figures 1, 2 [3]), and ice conditions.

Figure 1 – Map of Tropical Cyclones (TC) occurrence sites (“Planeta” Research Center)

Figure 2 –Installation of space images of TC («Planeta» Research Center)

Using microwave sounding data at different frequencies allows us to estimate the vertical structure of a hurricane, including the distribution of water vapor and liquid water in the clouds.

Let’s consider an example of using satellite sensing data in navigation to diverge from the storm zone (see Table 2, Figures 4–7). Hurricane Milton, which formed in the Atlantic Ocean in early October 2024, posed a serious threat to maritime navigation. As of October 9, 2024, the hurricane has reached category 4 on the Saffir-Simpson scale, with a maximum wind speed of about 120 knots (62 m/s) and a minimum pressure in the center of 950 mbar.

Table 2 – Hurricane Milton Size Characteristics

Parameter	North-east Quadrant	South-east Quadrant	South-west Quadrant	North-west Quadrant	Average value
Radius of maximum wind speed (km)	35	28	30	32	31
Radius of hurricane force winds (>64 knots) (km)	120	95	90	110	104
Radius of gale force winds (>34 knots) (km)	300	260	250	280	273
Radius of the last closed isobar (km)	450	420	400	430	425
Radius of heavy precipitation (>10 mm/h) (km)	180	150	140	160	158
Radius of the cloud system (km)	550	520	500	530	525

Figure 3 – Hurricane Milton Rainfall Intensity Map

Figure 4 – Wind speed profile from the hurricane center to the periphery

Figure 5 – Process of forecasting the movement of a hurricane

Figure 6 – Hurricane Milton trajectory, wind speed, km/h

Figure 7 – Hurricane Milton Evasion Maneuver

1. Evasive maneuver: *Evasive maneuver: The vessel correctly steered to port to allow the cyclone to pass. This is a standard evasive maneuver in the Northern Hemisphere, positioning the vessel in the less dangerous left hemisphere of the hurricane.*

2. Speed comparison: *Hurricane Milton:*

25 m/s ≈ 48.6 knots; ship speed: 15 knots.

The hurricane was moving significantly faster than the ship (≥ 3 times), making it impossible to escape the cyclone in a straight line (Table 3).

3. Minimize the time spent in the cyclone's influence zone.

4. Potentially reduce vessel speed loss due to headwinds and rough seas.

Table 3 – Calculation of the maneuver to avoid Hurricane Milton

Hurricane velocity 10.8 knots	Hurricane velocity 25 knots
The time it takes for a hurricane to reach a ship ($V_{hurricane}$ 10.8 knots):	If conditions worsen (wind speed increases to 25 knots), the vessel's speed must be reduced to 5.6 knots. The Hurricane will cover the same distance in 20.4 hours.
Calculate the minimum evasion distance the vessel will travel:	The vessel will travel only:
It turns out that if a ship deviates 236 miles from the center of the hurricane, it will avoid encountering the TC zone, remaining at a safe distance from the storm.	In this case, the vessel must move to a safer distance in advance to avoid the risk of getting caught in the hurricane wind zone.

It turns out that if a ship deviates 236 (the critical minimum is 114 miles) from the center of the hurricane, it will avoid encountering the TC zone, remaining at a safe distance from the storm. It is important to consider that the cyclone velocity of 10.8–13.5 knots is comparable to the actual speed of the vessel under normal conditions, which makes route selection critical to ensure safety. It is recommended to deviate from the hurricane's path in advance by at least 150–200 nautical miles to minimize the risk of being caught in the zone of influence of strong winds and waves.

Conclusion: The calculations confirmed the need to use modern remote sensing technologies and forecasting methods to ensure the safety of maritime navigation during tropical cyclones. When used properly, remote sensing data can significantly improve the safety of maritime transportation of cargoes in conditions of extreme weather conditions.

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**INTERNATIONAL TECHNOLOGY TRADE: THE IRANIAN
CASE AND THE FUTURE OF SCIENTIFIC COOPERATION –
SANCTIONS AND NEW CHALLENGES FOR THE RUSSIAN
SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY**

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Abstract. *In the context of global digital transformation and accelerating technological progress, international technology trade has become one of the key drivers of economic growth, innovation development, and geopolitical competition, compelling the world to view anew the ongoing processes of digitalization and the associated changes in international economic relations (IER) and international division of labor (IDL). This article explores the theoretical foundations, institutional frameworks, structure, and dynamics of international technology trade, while identifying systemic barriers and emerging challenges posed by technological nationalism and the concomitant fragmentation of the GCSS (Global Cyber-Scientific Space) alongside alter-globalization shifts affecting interactions among states, scientific schools, and research collectives. The authors propose to evaluate the relevance of the current comprehensive model for assessing the technological openness of countries, explore opportunities for the effective utilization of producers driving the ongoing scientific and technological revolution (STR), determine their contribution to shaping the dynamics of international trade, and provide forecasts on the specialization of the innovative economy across various industries and regions worldwide.*

Keywords: *international technology trade, digitalization, technological export/import, intellectual property (IP), technological openness, technological nationalism, innovative economy, fragmentation, GCSS, AI, Big Data, clusters, MRI, IET, Russia, China, USA.*

1. Introduction

Modern technologies of the knowledge economy, as scarce and rapidly perishable commodities in international trade, represent not only physical products but also intangible assets: patents, licenses, know-how, software, manufacturing technologies, digital platforms, and data subject to AI-driven neuro-algorithmic processing through various versions of LLMs (large language models), machine vision, and deep learning. Unlike traditional trade in physical goods, technology trade and exchange are characterized by a high degree of information asymmetry, a significant role of intellectual property, and a complex regulatory environment aimed at defending national technological sovereignty, which embodies the contradictions and diversity of ideas within the technocratic society of behavioral economics. In recent years, this sector has undergone profound structural transformations driven by digitalization, geopolitical tensions, and the pursuit by several nations of their own national technological sovereignty – capable of securing their position in the contemporary world and enabling domestic institutions to address critical vulnerabilities in digital infrastructures for actors operating at the meso- and micro-levels.

The aim of this article is to propose and develop a hypothesis concerning the growing uncertainty in markets for high-technology products (ICT, military-industrial complex, space, robotics, e-commerce, financial services), to theoretically substantiate and empirically analyze contemporary trends in international technology trade, identify key barriers, and offer scientifically grounded methodologies for evaluating and forecasting the technological openness of countries in their innovation development and in their existential pursuit to secure a rightful place within the emerging robot-humanoid paradigm of the ongoing energy transition.

2. Structure and Dynamics of International Technology Trade

According to data from the World Trade Organization (WTO) and the World Bank, the volume of international technology trade (including royalties, license fees, software transfers, and know-how) exceeded 2.5 trillion US dollars in 2023, accounting for approximately 7% of the total global trade in services.

Today, the global leaders in technology exports remain highly developed countries: the United States, Germany, Japan, South Korea, and China (driven in part by the growth of digital technology exports, electric vehicles, hybrid solutions, as well as breakthroughs in machine tool manufacturing and robotics). Leaders in imports are developing countries of Asia, Latin America, as well as EU countries with low technological and industrially obsolete bases, which have become dependent on technology transfer since the 1990s, following the loss of their own scientific and technological schools and the collapse of international cooperation that had been guaranteed to Comecon and Warsaw Pact countries during their socialist orientation.

The key sectors of implemented technical solutions that could potentially serve as drivers of growth in the high-tech product market today might be considered

those small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and transnational corporations (TNCs) of expansion that have bet on ICT technologies, biotechnology, renewable energy sources (RES), semiconductors, AI platforms, proprietary components, microelectronics and RES, space technology, and digital infrastructure solutions.

3. Institutional and geopolitical barriers

A) Export controls (e.g., Wassenaar Arrangement, documents on restrictions and reprisals from the 20th EU sanctions package against the Russian Federation).

B) Patent wars and litigation (Apple vs. Samsung, Huawei vs.

Qualcomm), disputes before the WTO Dispute Settlement Body involving the enforcement of Anglo-Saxon positions and the corporatocratic structures of the ‘collective West’;

C) Technological nationalism – the policy of ‘technological sovereignty’ in the EU, USA, and China;

C) Digital fragmentation – diverse approaches to data regulation (GDPR, PIPL, CLOUD Act);

D) Sanction regimes – restrictions on access to technologies for specific countries and companies;

E) Formation of military-technological alliances for ‘insiders’: AUKUS (for the Anglo-Saxons), clusters in the EU focused on creating an alternative European army instead of NATO, as well as proprietary GCSS chains regionally established by type of armament: in aviation, one of the potential partners for India, as a BRICS and SCO country, may be a European scientific and industrial consortium comprising the United Kingdom, Italy, and Japan, or another consortium involving Germany and France; in space, based on cooperation among NASA, ESA, and JAXA, a Lunar program will be developed and competition will be established in launch vehicles and astronaut delivery systems previously dominated by Russia and China, particularly in programs for access to Mars and Venus.

4. International scientific and technological cooperation as a factor of sustainability and inclusive technological development

Despite the growing trend towards technological nationalism and the fragmentation of GCSS value chains, international scientific and technological cooperation remains a vital mechanism for overcoming technological barriers and accelerating global innovation progress, preventing national autarky and the exclusion of states from access to the outputs of scientific and technological creativity. Joint research within international consortia (e.g., CERN, ITER, Human Brain Project), intergovernmental exchange programs (Horizon Europe, US-EU Science and Technology Agreements), as well as partnerships among universities, research centers, and the private sector (e.g., MIT-IBM Watson AI Lab, SK hynix-ASML) demonstrate that openness to knowledge and cooperation remains an essential prerequisite for breakthrough discoveries and their subsequent patent support. Cooperation in addressing ‘global challenges’—such as

climate change, healthcare, sustainable energy, access to fresh water, and clean, unmodified protein (free from mutations and genetic modifications (GMOs) produced by corporations like Monsanto (USA))—is of particular importance, as these technologies cannot be effectively developed and implemented in isolation. They require continuous adjustment and standardization in accordance with widely accepted norms and certifiable safety and quality standards. In this context, scientific and technological cooperation serves not only as a tool for knowledge exchange but also as a form of ‘soft diplomacy’ capable of reducing geopolitical tensions and creating a trust-based environment for technological exchange, diversification of scientific personnel, and the development of sovereign chains in innovative products. Including this aspect in the analysis of international technology trade allows it to be understood not only as a market-driven process but also as one characterized by institutional cooperation. It is precisely the ability to combine “smart” and “soft” power that once again forms the basis for future management approaches, enabling national personnel with the necessary profiles and competencies to withstand pressure from global governance institutions, providing them with opportunities for collaborative development alongside scientists from the “global South”, and allowing the state to leverage technical espionage as an indispensable tool amid the expulsion of researchers from the EAEU and Russia from all major international projects in the fields of energy, biology, space exploration, and quantum computing. Simultaneously, it is precisely our stellarator, representing a new phase in the science of ‘cold plasma,’ that offers the world an additional opportunity to advance safe and relatively affordable nuclear energy. Furthermore, satellite systems based on qubits or cubesats, or implemented through a distributed network of microsattellites, are currently under active discussion by the Space Research Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences and the company Geoscan for the purposes of monitoring solar activity and analyzing energy fluxes. Similar initiatives aimed at concentrating the energy of the sole star of the Solar System are being simultaneously undertaken by the USA and China alongside Russia. Specifically, Meta (designated as an extremist organization and banned in Russia), Elon Musk’s company, and the Chinese firm Overview Energy have signed an agreement to reserve space-based solar power generation capacities. Consequently, competition and sanction-driven measures against Russian scientists are increasingly marginalizing us within the global scientific knowledge landscape, narrowing our participation and hindering the comprehensive development of critical and breakthrough technologies capable of preempting risks and threats facing humanity as a whole.

This scientific article proposes the following innovations, contributing to the advancement of both theory and practice in international technology trade, serving as guidelines for developing scientific approaches capable of simplifying and securing the existing assets of scientific and technological producers across corporations and countries:

5. The authors propose developing a comprehensive model to assess a country's 'technological openness' and to establish a set of indicators evaluating the adaptability of scientific schools and the value of technologies acquired by each state, grounded in the priorities of ongoing digitalization, its ease and cost-effectiveness, and subsequent clustering within each high-tech sector, taking into account GCSS and the country's level of specialization in international technology exchange (ИМТ) and international technology transfer (ИТТ).

Accordingly, the authors suggest considering the creation of a multifactor model integrating indicators such as the export-import balance of technologies measured in both monetary and quantitative terms;

level of patent activity and licensing flows;

access to global innovation chains and GCSS;

institutional openness (existence of bilateral agreements, absence of export controls);

digital integration (access to global platforms, data exchange).

Scientific value: an integrated methodology is proposed for the first time, enabling a quantitative assessment of a country's degree of technological openness within the global context, thus allowing for the forecasting of its innovation potential and susceptibility to technological sanctions.

Detection and classification of 'next-generation technological barriers.'

A novel classification is proposed for the first time, encompassing barriers that transcend traditional tariffs and quotas, aimed at simplifying and formalizing issues surrounding technology exchange and/or access to products of national scientific-technological schools:

Geopolitical barriers (export controls, sanctions);

Digital barriers (data localization, platform restrictions);

Institutional barriers (patent system incompatibilities, lack of license recognition);

Cultural-cognitive barriers (distrust of foreign technologies, technological nationalism, digital feudalism).

Scientific value: enables the systematic organization of contemporary restrictions in technology trade and the formulation of targeted strategies to overcome them at the state and corporate levels.

The concept of technological imbalance in international trade

The concept of technological imbalance is introduced – a condition wherein a country imports technologies but fails to develop its own innovation base, resulting in long-term dependence and a decline in national technological sovereignty.

To achieve this, a methodology must be developed to measure imbalance using the ratio: Technology Imports / Domestic R&D Investments. Available SIPRI data can provide a preliminary evaluation for each country, serving as a foundation not

only for the production of armaments and military equipment but also for defining approaches to the transformation of domestic scientific schools and GCSS in collaboration with regional partners, within the frameworks of strategic alliances or participation in regulated merger and acquisition processes aligned with the profile of each specific implemented technology, in accordance with national scientific and technological sovereignty.

Scientific significance: a quantitative measure of a country's vulnerability in the technological sector is proposed for the first time, allowing for adjustment of national innovation strategies and the avoidance of 'technological dependency traps.'

The 'technology diplomacy' model as a tool for conflict mitigation in technology trade

The concept of technology diplomacy is introduced – the deliberate utilization of bilateral and multilateral agreements, scientific and technical cooperation, joint R&D projects, and standardization to alleviate tensions within the technological sector.

Scientific significance: for the first time, a theoretical framework has been developed for employing diplomatic instruments to resolve technological conflicts, which is highly relevant amid increasing geopolitical tensions.

6. Conclusion

International technology trade is currently undergoing a phase of transformation driven by digitalization, geopolitical dynamics, and the increasing prominence of intellectual property. Traditional approaches to the analysis of international trade are inadequate for understanding contemporary realities. The scientific innovations proposed in this study – a model of technological openness, a classification of new barriers, and the concepts of technological imbalance and technological diplomacy – establish a foundation for further research in the global innovation economy and the international policy of technology transfer and export/import.

The Iranian case triggered further disruption of raw material flows and access to components in the high-tech sector, causing price increases and delays in the supply of components for the production of microchips and electronics, armaments, and life-support systems. This will lead, in the future, to systemic failures across various national security frameworks, increase their dependence on the GCSS and pragmatic approaches, which are undermined by sanction pressures and attempts to enforce economic self-sufficiency on entire countries in the process of technology trade, alongside the persistent drive towards greater sovereignty of national industries responsible for the safe and sustainable development of their populations.

The ongoing energy transition and the emergence of the robot-humanoid order characteristic of Industry 4.0 will not be able to resolve the development challenges of entire regions without upheavals and conflicts if states continue to have their access to knowledge and education eroded by institutions of global governance, impeded by clans of the global oligarchy who execute their plans by redistributing services

and products from the middle class to the strata of the wealthy and ultra-wealthy. This scenario has long been championed by neoconservatives and forms part of the agenda for banksters and netocrats, as openly proclaimed at the Davos Forum by Klaus Schwab and Larry Flint with his 'BlackRock' (in the year 2026), and is further reinforced by the agendas promoted by the Bilderberg and Rome Clubs.

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**OPERATIONAL QUANTIFICATION OF DAMAGE CAUSED BY
A SUDDEN BREACH OF INFORMATION SECURITY
AT A CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE FACILITY: METHODS
AND TOOLS**

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Abstract. *The damage caused by a sudden breach of information security at a critically important infrastructure facility is proposed to be represented as expenditures of time, materials, labor, energy, and financial resources required for restoring the operability of the protected facility. A Python-based program has been developed to enable the rapid estimation of the distribution characteristics of expenditures of time, materials, labor, energy, and financial resources involved in restoring information security at a critically important infrastructure facility. The possibility of employing the developed Python program for the rapid evaluation of the aggregate primary statistical characteristics of the distribution of resource expenditures for restoring the operability of the protected object is demonstrated (using the example of financial resource costs), including the mean value, median, variance, root mean square, coefficient of variation, skewness, kurtosis, minimum and maximum values, as well as the assessment of the accumulated probability structure.*

Keywords: *information security, critical infrastructure, resource intensity, Python program, rapid assessment, expenditure distribution, statistical characteristics,*

Problem Statement. During the operation of protected facilities, numerous exceptional situations occur related to sudden breaches of the security of the protected facility. As noted in the literature (see, for example, [1]), although “*formal*

methods exist for evaluating the effectiveness of information security measures, access control models, and methods for constructing and analyzing object-oriented models of information system protection,” these methods “are limited in their formal representation of all specific properties essential for verifying the fulfillment of information protection requirements.”

At the same time, with the advent of quantum computers, the likelihood of breaches in protection and violations of information security significantly increases, as their use by criminals «*can threaten civil and military communication systems, the economic sphere of the country, as well as other sectors of activity... Each year, cybercriminals evolve and demonstrate new types of multivector attacks, while simultaneously the field of quantum technologies advances, posing even more serious threats to classical information systems... But what will be the consequences if a powerful quantum computer falls into the hands of malicious actors? They will be capable of breaching virtually any security system within a short period, which will lead to adverse consequences ranging from disruptions in the financial system to the leakage of state secrets*» [2].

Furthermore, the information security (IS) violation at the facility arises unexpectedly, and therefore acquiring *initial data for conducting retrospective analysis and damage quantification is difficult and unlikely*.

Thus, the probability of breaching the protection of information resources is considerably high. But how can the potential magnitude of damage caused by information security (IS) breaches at critically important infrastructure facilities be operationally assessed?

This article, building upon previously conducted studies (see [3–7]), proposes original methods and instrumental means for the operational quantitative assessment of damage magnitude resulting from breaches of protection at a critically important infrastructure facility. Meanwhile, **damage** from an IS breach is represented as *expenditures in time, materials, labor, energy, and financial resources* required to restore the operability of the protected facility. Since identical methods and tools can be employed to assess the costs of any resources, the approach to solving the stated problem is demonstrated through the example of estimating the costs of **financial** resources for recovery operations after a breach of the protection of the analyzed object.

1. Operational assessment of financial resource expenditures on recovery operations following an information security breach at a critical infrastructure facility

To quantify the damage expressed as financial resource expenditures required to restore the functionality of the protected facility, we utilize the method of ‘Step-wise refinement during the expert evaluation of indicator values with assessment of the characteristics of the distribution law.’ Let us first recall the specific features and outline the primary advantages of this method [6, 7].

Description of the method. Implementation features. 1) Specialists participating in the expertise are provided with the opportunity to consider objections and proposals from other members of the expert group within an environment free from the influence of personal qualities of the participants, which promotes the activation of the experts' intellectual activity. 2) The concept of "informed intuitive judgment" by the expert specialist is supported through the creation of conditions for active interaction with other experts in fields related to various aspects of the problem under study. 3) Direct communication among specialists is replaced by a sequence of steps, each implementing a full cycle of expertise, including informing the experts about the outcomes of the previous step. Consequently, there is no negative impact on the results of the algorithm implementation caused by the presence of supervisors and subordinates, friends and adversaries, or individuals with differing reaction speeds within the expert group. in different cultural and religious traditions, etc. 4) A quantitative determination of the moment (step number) marking the completion of the expert survey is implemented (based on the magnitude of the change in the coefficient of variation). 5) The method is valid, extensively tested, and has demonstrated its applied utility through use in various subject domains.

The evaluations of each i -th expert at the j -th step $\mathfrak{E}(j)_i$ are approximated by triangular distributions (if three values are provided) or uniform distributions (if the expert specified two values of the indicator). The generalized collective opinion n of experts regarding the sought value of the indicator is defined as the average n of random variables possessing triangular or uniform distributions, obtained by executing at each k -th step of the simulation the function $E(k)_{ob} = (\sum E(k)_i) / n$, ($i \in n$). As instrumental means for implementing the simulation, the software product developed by the authors is used, which allows constructing the simulation model with minimal labor input (in automated mode). As a result of simulation modeling, at each k -th step, statistical characteristics (expected value, variance, coefficient of variation, kurtosis, skewness) and the distribution (table and histogram) of the indicator values – the function $E(k)_{ob} = f(E(k)_i)$ —are obtained. After each step (expertise cycle), members of the expert group are presented with explanations supporting markedly divergent estimates of the indicator values and are offered the opportunity to revise their previous responses if they so desire. At each successive j -th step, the change in the values of the coefficient of variation $K(j)_{var}$ of the function $E(j)_{ob}$ is assessed. If the coefficient of variation deviates from the previous value by, for example, 5% or less, it may be considered that the expert assessments have stabilized, and it is advisable to terminate the evaluation. Based on the simulation modeling results, the confidence intervals of the indicator values and the probability that these values will exceed or fall below a specified threshold are assessed at the final step.

Advantages of the method: 1) *Enhancement of* the accuracy of expert assessment results due to

* the presence of feedback during the implementation of each subsequent iteration; * providing the expert with the possibility of specifying three or two values of the target indicator; * determination, based on the results of simulation modeling, of the probability that the indicator value falls within a specified range of values. 2) Reduction of psychological burden on the expert and mitigation of negative influences on assessment results caused by the presence of supervisors and/or ambitious individuals, since anonymity is maintained: experts do not communicate with each other and are unaware of who provided a specific justification supporting markedly divergent indicator values.

3) *The representation of the cumulative distribution* as the mean (mathematical expectation) *of the sum of triangular or uniform distributions* of assessments provided by individual experts *allows obtaining* the resultant distribution of the indicator values *even under the condition* that experts provide three or two values of the target indicator and there is *a high dispersion of assessments*.

4) Calculation of statistical characteristics of the distributions (mathematical expectation, variance, coefficient of variation, median, skewness, kurtosis) of histograms and distribution tables enables the assessment of the probability that the values of the target indicator fall within a specified range. 5) Identification of spontaneous groupings of experts whose assessments are close relative to the target indicator values permits investigation of the reasons for formation of such groups. Grouping of experts is performed based on a specified threshold probability of a particular interval of the forecasted indicator values.

Using the method, it is possible to determine *how the responses of the expert group participants are correlated*, the degree of this correlation, and which factors account for the presence of such correlation (whether education level, workplace, specialty, work experience, characteristics of the object under analysis, etc., have an influence).

Comparative evaluation of the method's practical utility. In many cases, it is simply impossible to proceed without employing the expert procedure as stipulated by the method under consideration. Indeed, for a *newly developed product* it will be necessary to use an expert poll when *forecasting the demand* for the product, *the operating costs, in the assessment of the total cost of ownership* of the product, and in many other scenarios. Therefore, it is desirable to determine the reliability of the results obtained by applying the method.

To assess the consumer quality of the method (i.e., the extent of its practical utility), we conducted experimental studies under contractual agreements with several major enterprises. Thus, during the development of the information systems 'ASU-remont' for the electric locomotive manufacturing plant NEVZ (Novocherkassk) and the 'Atom mash' plant (Volgodonsk), an evaluation of time costs

for processes and operations related to equipment repair was conducted *by means of time measurement* (both explicitly and implicitly), as well as *by surveying repair personnel* with a work experience exceeding one year.

A similar approach was applied in evaluating time costs for the execution of *other processes and operations* related to orders from the ‘Voskhod’ and ‘Hydroagregat’ plants (Nizhny Novgorod Region), plant No. 412 (Rostov-on-Don), among others, as well as in several tax inspectorates (see, for example, [8–11]).

It was revealed (quite unexpectedly for many of us) that *statistically significant* (with a probability of 0.9–0.95) according to the interdecile ranges, both samples (*the one obtained through explicit and implicit time-tracking measurements, as well as the expert evaluation via the PUZ-OHR method*) belong to the same underlying population.

A numerical example illustrating the implementation of the proposed method. Table 1 provides expert assessments of the financial resources required for recovery operations following a sudden information security breach at the protected facility. The quantity of experts is fully sufficient to demonstrate the functionality of the proposed method and the Python program developed by the authors.

Table 1. Expert assessment of financial resource expenditures for the recovery of information security of the protected object (Step 1)

Number Step	Values of financial expenditures on recovery operations (u. e.)	Expert assessments of the potential magnitude of financial resource expenditures for recovery operations following a breach of the information security of the object				
		E11	E12	E13	E14	E15
1	Minimum	45	30	50	60	30
	Most Likely	85	50	60	70	40
	Maximum	110	70	90	95	60

The results of simulation modeling of the data from Table 1 for expert E11 are presented in Figure 1 and Table 2.

Fig. 1 Histogram of the distribution of financial resource expenditure values for the recovery of the information security of the protected object – expert E11’s estimate

Table 2. Structure of cumulative probability. Step 1. Expert E11's assessment

Values X_{\min}	Values X_{\max}	Frequency	Probability	Cumulative probability
46.7	52.3	22	0.022	0.022
52.3	57.9	44	0.044	0.066
57.9	63.5	73	0.073	0.139
63.5	69.1	84	0.084	0.223
69.1	74.7	111	0.111	0.334
74.7	80.3	129	0.129	0.463
80.3	85.9	170	0.170	0.633
85.9	91.5	141	0.141	0.774
91.5	97.1	123	0.123	0.897
97.1	102.8	77	0.077	0.974
102.8	108.4	26	0.026	1.000

Table 3 shows the simulation results of responses from each expert participating in the survey individually, as well as in the aggregated form after completion of Step 1.

Table 3. Statistical characteristics of the distribution of financial resource expenditure for restoring information security at a facility of critically important infrastructure (Step 1)

Parameters	Values of statistical characteristics of the distribution of financial resource expenditures associated with the restoration of the information security of the object					
	E1	E2	E3	E4	E5	$\sum E_i$
Number of iterations	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000
Mean	80.2	50.2	66.37	75.4	43.4	62.9
Variance	183.8	67.2	68.4	54.1	35.7	16.6
Standard deviation	13.5	8.2	8.3	7.4	5.9	4.1
Coefficient of variation	0.17	0.16	0.13	0.09	0.14	0.07
Skewness	-0.26	-0.06	0.431	0.38	0.32	-0.03
Kurtosis	-0.66	-0.56	-0.6	-0.69	-0.4	-0.11
Minimum	46.6	30.7	50.1	60.9	30.8	50.3
Maximum	108.4	69.6	88.0	94.3	58.5	75.1
Modal interval	80.3: 85.9	48.4: 51.9	57: 60.4	70.0: 73.0	40.9: 43.4	59.3: 61.5

Table 4 presents expert assessments of the financial resource expenditures for recovery operations following a sudden information security breach at the protected object, considering the changes in responses recorded at Step 2, whereas Table 5 reflects changes observed at Step 3.

Table 4. Expert assessment of financial resource expenditures for the recovery of information security of the protected object (Step 2)

Number Step	Values of financial expenditures on recovery operations (u. e.)	Expert assessments of the potential magnitude of financial resource expenditures for recovery operations following a breach of the information security of the object				
		E21	E22	E23	E24	E25
2	Minimum	55	60	50	60	50
	Most Likely	95	90	60	70	65
	Maximum	110	100	90	95	90

***Values of financial resource expenditures modified after the latest step are indicated in bold**

Table 5. Expert assessment of financial resource expenditures for the restoration of information security of the protected object (Step 3)

Number Step	Values of financial expenditures on recovery operations (u. e.)	Expert assessments of the potential magnitude of financial resource expenditures for recovery operations following a breach of the information security of the object				
		E31	E32	E33	E34	E35
3	Minimum	55	60	55	50	50
	Most Likely	95	90	65	60	65
	Maximum	110	100	90	95	90

***Values of financial resource expenditures modified after the latest step are indicated in bold**

Table 6 presents statistical characteristics of the distribution of financial resource expenditures for the restoration of information security of the critically important infrastructure object

Table 6. Statistical characteristics of the distribution of financial resource expenditure for restoring information security at a facility of critically important infrastructure
(results of simulation modeling. $\sum E_{ij}/5$). Steps 1–3.

Parameters	Values of statistical characteristics of the distribution of financial resource expenditures for the restoration of information security of the object		
	f1	f2	f3
Variable			
Comment			
Number of iterations	1000	1000	1000
Mean	62.9	75.9	75.4
Variance	16.6	15.3	16.5
Standard deviation	4.1	3.9	4.07
Coefficient of variation	0.07	0.052	0.054
Skewness	-0.03	-0.04	0.036
Kurtosis	-0.11	-0.045	-0.13
Minimum	50.3	63.8	62.4
Maximum	75.1	89.4	88.5
Modal interval	59.3: 61.5	75.5: 77.8	74.2: 76.6

$(|K_{\text{var}}^{02} - K_{\text{var}}^{03}|) / K_{\text{var}}^{03} < 5\%$, i.e., the expert evaluation can be concluded

(f3)

Fig. 2. Histogram of the distribution of final values of financial resource expenditures for restoring the information security of the protected object – expert assessments E1–E5.

Conclusions

In the article, for the first time

1. It is proposed to present the damage resulting from a sudden information security breach at an object of critically important infrastructure as expenditures of time, materials, labor, energy, and financial resources required for restoring the operability of the protected object.

2. A Python-based program has been developed allowing the rapid assessment of distribution characteristics of time, material, labor, energy, and financial resource expenditures for restoring information security at a critically important infrastructure facility.

3. Demonstrated (using the example of financial resource expenditures) the feasibility of employing the author's Python-based program for operational estimation of the key aggregate statistical characteristics of the distribution of resource expenditures for restoring the operability of the protected facility, including mean value, variance, root mean square value, coefficient of variation, skewness, kurtosis, minimum and maximum values, as well as evaluation of the accumulated probability structure.

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MULTIFACTORIAL ANALYSIS OF THE RISK PROBABILITIES OF AN INNOVATION PROJECT: MODEL, ALGORITHM AND NUMERICAL VERIFICATION

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Abstract. *This paper presents a multifactorial model for assessing the probability of risk in innovation projects, based on three groups of factors: structural (probability of success, market novelty), dynamic (life cycle phase, cumulative deviation from the plan), and operational (liquidity buffer, forecasted time to breakeven). An algorithm for calculating the integral risk probability is presented. The model is verified using an early-stage project example. The impact of variations in input parameters on the risk probability is demonstrated. The mathematical framework of the gamma process for forecasting the remaining time until breakeven, incorporating Bayesian parameter updating, is presented.*

Keywords: *innovation project, risk probability, multifactorial analysis, runway, RUL, Bayesian updating, gamma process.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Risk assessment of an innovation project constitutes a critical task for venture capital investors, corporate incubators, and the founders themselves. In contrast to mature projects, where risk can be evaluated based on historical cash flow volatility, early-stage innovation projects lack sufficient statistical data. Conventional methods – such as discounted cash flow with adjusted discount rates, scoring models, and expert assessments – are either subjective or do not consider the temporal dynamics of risk factors [1, 2]. Digital data aggregation platforms partially resolve the issue of information collection but do not provide integrated analytics with quantitative risk forecasting [3, 4].

The aim of this study is to develop a formalized multifactorial model that enables the quantitative estimation of the risk probability of an innovation project

based on a limited set of observable parameters and provides for the dynamic update of this estimation as new data are received.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of a digital twin for the management of complex systems is addressed in the studies by Glaessgen and Stargel [1], as well as Grieves and Vickers [2], wherein the significance of integrating data and models is underscored. The application of digital twins in industrial contexts is systematically reviewed by Tao et al. [3] and Errandonea et al. [4]. Within the domain of venture investment, current platforms primarily focus on the visualization of metrics but lack predictive analytics incorporating quantitative assessments of uncertainty [5].

Methods for forecasting residual life based on gamma processes with Bayesian parameter updating are comprehensively detailed in the work of Xu, Zhang, and Ye [6]. This methodology permits recursive refinement of forecasts without the necessity of storing the complete observation history, which is critically important for scalable analytical platforms. In the context of innovation projects, this approach facilitates continuous monitoring of accumulated deviations from the plan and enables operational forecasting of the time until reserve exhaustion.

The seminal works on reliability and Bayesian methods – the monographs by Trivedi and Bobbio [7], as well as Hamada et al. [8]—establish the theoretical foundation for modeling probabilistic processes in asset portfolios. Reliability-based design considerations related to digital twins are addressed in studies [9–11]. Despite considerable advancements, the challenge of synthesizing a unified multifactorial model for risk assessment of innovation projects with dynamic forecast updating remains unresolved.

III. RISK FACTORS OF AN INNOVATION PROJECT

Three groups of factors determining the overall risk are identified.

Group 1. Structural factors (S) – characteristics associated with the business model and market position of the project.

S1. The baseline probability of success (p_0). It is determined by the project phase. According to statistics, the ranges are as follows: *pre-seed* – 0.20–0.35, *seed* – 0.35–0.55, *growth* – 0.55–0.75, *scale* – 0.75–0.90.

S2. Coefficient of market novelty ($knov$). Ranges from 0.7 (radical innovation) to 1.3 (incremental innovation). Neutral value – 1.0.

S3. Correlation with the portfolio (ρ). Represents the degree to which the project's outcome is statistically correlated with the outcomes of other projects within the investor's portfolio. A high positive correlation elevates systemic risk and diminishes the diversification effect.

Group 2. Dynamic factors (D) – indicators representing the current state and development trends of the enterprise.

D1. Accumulated deviation from the plan (δ). Calculated as the sum of the ratios of actual deviations to critical limits across three key metrics: budget (δb), schedule (δt), and revenue (δr). Critical thresholds are established based on expert evaluation.

D2. Phase parameter (β). Defined according to the life cycle stage: *pre-seed* – 0.6, *seed* – 1.0, *growth* – 1.5, *scale* – 2.0. This parameter characterizes the changing sensitivity of the project to deviations; during later stages, even minor deviations are considered critical.

D3. Revenue growth rate (g). Expressed as a percentage over the most recent quarter. Negative values signal stagnation or contraction within the business.

Group 3. Operational factors (O) – metrics of liquidity and anticipated financial resilience.

O1. Liquidity buffer *runway* (RW). Measured in months. Calculated as the ratio of available cash to average monthly burn: $RW = \text{Cash} / \text{Monthly Burn}$.

O2. Critical threshold RW (R_{crit}). Minimum allowable liquidity buffer. The standard value for venture projects is set at 6 months.

O3. Predicted remaining useful life until breakeven (RUL). Measured in months. It is calculated using a mathematical model of the gamma process for deviation accumulation with Bayesian parameter updating.

IV. ALGORITHM FOR CALCULATING RISK PROBABILITY

The algorithm comprises five sequential steps.

Step 1. Calculation of the adjusted success probability (p_{adj}). The baseline probability p_0 is multiplied by the market novelty coefficient k_{nov} . If the enterprise is implementing a radical innovation, or alternatively, an incremental one $k_{nov} = 0.7 k_{nov} = 1.3$. Formula: $p_{adj} = p_0 \times 0.7 k_{nov}$, the final value is limited to a maximum of 0.95.

Step 2. Calculation of the cumulative deviation (δ). Critical deviation thresholds are established for three metrics: budget ΔB_{crit} (e.g., 30% of the planned budget for the period), duration ΔT_{crit} (e.g., 3 months), and revenue ΔR_{crit} (e.g., 50% of the planned revenue). The actual deviation for each metric is divided by its respective critical threshold, and the results are summed: $\delta = \delta_b + \delta_t + \delta_r$. Interpretation of values: $\delta < 0.3$ – normal (project within planned boundaries); $0.3 \leq \delta < 0.6$ – warning zone (requires intensified monitoring); $0.6 \leq \delta < 1.0$ – critical zone (intervention is necessary); $\delta \geq 1.0$ – default is inevitable without radical measures.

Step 3. Calculation of the dynamic correction coefficient (k_{dyn}). This coefficient accounts for the accumulated deviation and the phase parameter. The formula is as follows: $k_{dyn} = \exp(-\beta \times \delta)$. The greater the accumulated deviation and the higher the value of β (later phase), the stronger the decline in the probability of success. In the early stages ($\beta < 1$), the reduction exhibits lower sensitivity to deviations, indicating greater investor tolerance for uncertainty during the *pre-seed* and *seed* phases.

Step 4. Calculation of the operational coefficient (k_{op}). Takes into account the ratio of current liquidity reserves to the forecasted time to breakeven. Criteria for determination k_{op} :

- if $RW \geq R_{crit}$ and $RW \geq RUL \times 0.7$, then $k_{op} = 1.0$ (liquidity is sufficient to achieve the objectives);

- if $RW < R_{crit}$ but exceeds $R_{crit} \times 0.5$, then $k_{op} = 0.8$ (moderate liquidity shortage);

- if $RW \leq R_{crit} \times 0.5$, then $k_{op} = 0.5$ (acute liquidity shortage).

Step 5. Calculation of the overall probability.

Overall probability of enterprise success:

$$P_{\text{success}} = p_{\text{adi}} \times k_{\text{dyn}} \times k_{\text{op}}.$$

Risk probability (default, closure, requirement for emergency interventions):

$$P_{\text{rick}} = 1 - P_{\text{success}}$$

V. MATHEMATICAL APPARATUS OF THE GAMMA PROCESS FOR REMAINING USEFUL LIFE PREDICTION RUL

Prediction of the remaining useful life (RUL) is a key element of operational analysis. The mathematical foundation utilized is a model of deviation accumulation based on the gamma process with Bayesian parameter updating [6]. The following vectors are enumerated:

V.1. Definition of the gamma process. Let $Y(t)$ denote a stochastic process characterizing the accumulated deviation from planned metrics at time t expressed in monetary terms. The process commences from zero: $Y(0) = 0$. Increments of the process over disjoint time intervals are assumed to be independent random variables following a gamma distribution. The increment ΔY over an interval of duration Δt has the probability density function:

$$f_T(y|\alpha\Delta t, \beta) = [\beta^{(\alpha\Delta t)} / \Gamma(\alpha\Delta t)] \times y^{(\alpha\Delta t - 1)} \times \exp(-\beta y), y \geq 0,$$

where $\alpha > 0$ denotes the shape parameter, which governs the rate of deviation accumulation (a higher α indicates a faster deviation of the project from the plan), $\beta > 0$ is the scale parameter, representing the process volatility, and $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is Euler's gamma function.

Expected value of the increment: $E[\Delta Y] = \alpha\Delta t / \beta$. Variance of the increment: $Var[\Delta Y] = \alpha\Delta t / \beta^2$.

V.2. Critical condition and time-to-failure distribution. The critical condition necessitating mandatory managerial intervention (default, depletion of reserves, or the requirement for urgent financing) arises when the process $Y(t)$ attains the predetermined threshold C . This threshold may correspond to the total allowable budget overrun or the maximum volume of attracted financing. The time T until reaching the threshold C is characterized by the cumulative distribution function:

$$F_{\tau}(t|\alpha, \beta) = \Psi(\beta C, \alpha t) / \Gamma(\alpha t),$$

where $\Psi(a, x) = \int_x^{\infty} t^{(a-1)} e^{-t} dt$ represents the upper incomplete gamma function.

V.3. Bayesian parameter updating. The initial (prior) values of the parameters α_0 and β_0 are determined based on historical data from analogous projects or expert evaluations. Upon receiving a new observation – the observed increment Δy over the elapsed time interval Δt – the parameters are updated according to the following formulas:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{post} &= \alpha^0 + \Delta y / C, \\ \beta_{post} &= \beta^0 + \Delta t. \end{aligned}$$

A principal advantage of this approach is its recursive nature: updating does not require storing the entire history of observations; it suffices to know the current parameter values and the new observation. This renders the method particularly attractive for deployment in cloud-based analytical platforms with constrained computational resources and in real-time systems.

V.4. Forecasting RUL via the Monte Carlo method.

Residual time to breakeven at the current level of accumulated deviation and threshold C is determined as:

$$RUL = \inf \tau > 0: Y(t + \tau) - Y(t) \geq C - y_t.$$

The Monte Carlo method is employed to construct the RUL distribution. N trajectories of the process $Y(t)$ are generated from the current state y, t with updated parameters α_{post} and β_{post} (recommended $N = 10,000$ to ensure stable estimates). For each trajectory, the instant of reaching the threshold C is recorded. Sample quantiles of the RUL distribution are constructed from the ensemble of trajectories: the median (50th percentile), as well as the bounds of the 80% or 90% confidence intervals. The empirical distribution function of RUL is expressed as:

$$F_{RUL}(r) = (1/N) \times \sum_{s=1}^N 1_{[Y^{(s)}(t+r) - Y^{(s)}(t) \geq C - y_t]},$$

where $1_{[\]}$ – an indicator function.

Similarly, the distribution of future RW values can be forecast based on the joint modeling of *cash flow* and *burn rate*.

VI. EXAMPLE OF NUMERICAL CALCULATION

Consider an innovation project at the *seed* stage with the following parameters.

Table 1. Initial Project Data

Indicator	Value	Remark
p_0	0.45	base success probability (midpoint of the range 0.35–0.55)
k_{nov}	1.2	enhancing innovation
Project budget	1,200 thousand rubles	
Expenditures over 4 months planned/actual	800/920 thousand rubles	
Timeline planned/actual	4/5 months	time to achieve key metric
Revenue Plan vs. Actual	200/140 thousand rubles	
Cash	720 thousand rubles	
Burn	230 thousand rubles	
$\alpha/\beta_0/C$	0.9/18/400 thousand rubles	Gamma process parameters for RUL prediction and critical deviation threshold

Table 2. Step-by-step Calculation

Step	Calculations	Comments
Step 1	$padj = 0.45 \times 1.2 = 0.54$ (54%)	Adjusted Probability of Success
Step 2	Accumulated Deviation (δ) Set Critical Thresholds: by budget $\Delta B_{crit} = 30\% \times 800 = 240$ thousand rubles by schedule $\Delta T_{crit} = 3$ months by revenue $\Delta R_{crit} = 50\% \times 200 = 100$ thousand rubles Actual deviations: budget $920 - 800 = +120$ thousand rubles $\rightarrow \delta_b = 120 / 240 = 0.50$ schedule $5 - 4 = +1$ month $\rightarrow \delta_t = 1 / 3 \approx 0.33$ revenue: $200 - 140 = 60$ thousand rubles shortfall $\rightarrow \delta_r = 60 / 100 = 0.60$ Total accumulated deviation: $\delta = 0.50 + 0.33 + 0.60 = 1.43$	$\delta = 1.43 > 1.0$ – the enterprise is within the critical risk zone; accumulated deviations have exceeded the permissible thresholds
Step 3	Dynamic correction coefficient (k_{dyn}). For the seed stage	Accumulated deviations reduce the probability of success by approximately a factor of 4.2

<p>Step 4</p>	<p>Operational coefficient (k_{op}). Calculate $RW = 720 / 230 \approx 3.13$ months Critical threshold $R_{crit} = 6$ months Forecast of RUL based on the gamma process Current accumulated monetary deviation: budget overrun of 120 thousand rubles. + foregone revenue of 60 thousand rubles = 180 thousand rubles. This value = 180. Threshold $C = 400$ thousand rubles. Distance to threshold $C - = 400 - 180 = 220$ thousand rubles. Monte Carlo method ($N = 10,000$ simulations) with parameters $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 18$ produces the following results for RUL: median 5.6 months; 10th percentile 3.2 months 90th percentile is 9.1 months. Verifying the conditions for k_{op} : $RW (3.13) < R_{crit} (6)$ – condition not satisfied $RW (3.13) > R_{crit} \times 0.5 (3.0)$ – condition satisfied</p>	<p>The 80-percent confidence interval is [3.2, 9.1] months. k_{op} equals 0.8 (moderate liquidity deficit)</p>
<p>Step 5</p>	<p>Final probabilities of success and risk. $P_{success} = p_{adj} \times k_{dyn} \times k_{op} = 0.54 \times 0.239 \times 0.80 = 0.103$ Risk probability: $P_{risk} = 1 - 0.103 = 0.897$</p>	<p>The probability of risk is 89.7% The probability of success is 10.3%</p>

An interpretation of the results is presented. The project is in a critical condition. Despite the relatively high adjusted baseline probability of success (54%), accumulated deviations in budget, schedule, and revenue ($\delta = 1.43$) substantially diminish the likelihood of success. The current liquidity buffer (3.13 months) is insufficient to reach breakeven (median forecast $RUL = 5.6$ months). A risk probability of 89.7% signifies that, absent immediate corrective actions, the enterprise is highly likely to encounter default or necessitate urgent refinancing.

VII. BAYESIAN UPDATING OF THE FORECAST RUL

The RUL forecast can be revised as new data are acquired. This will be illustrated by the continuation of the example. Assume that crisis mitigation measures were implemented within the project, resulting in reduced expenditures and the mobilization of investments. For the subsequent quarter (3 months), new data were obtained: the actual budget variance decreased, with an additional overrun of 30 thousand rubles.

Initial parameters: $\alpha_0 = 0.9, \beta_0 = 18, C = 400$ thousand rubles.

New observation: $\Delta y = 30$ thousand rubles over $\Delta t = 3$ months.

Posterior parameters:

$$\alpha_{post} = \alpha_0 + \Delta y / C = 0.9 + 30 / 400 = 0.9 + 0.075 = 0.975;$$

$$\beta_{post} = \beta_0 + \Delta t = 18 + 3 = 21.$$

New current deviation: $y_{t_{new}} = 180 + 30 = 210$ thousand rubles Remaining distance to threshold: $C - y_{t_{new}} = 400 - 210 = 190$ thousand rubles

The Monte Carlo method with updated parameters ($\alpha_{post} = 0.975$, $\beta_{post} = 21$) produces a new *RUL* forecast: the median is 7.2 months, the 10th percentile is 4.5 months, and the 90th percentile is 11.0 months; the 80% confidence interval is [4.5, 11.0] months.

The recalculation of risk probability incorporating new data produces the following results: *RW* increased to 5.0 months (after additional investments); $k_{op} = 0.8$ (*RW* remains below 6 months but above 3); δ is updated based on the new data.

Let us assume that the budget deviation increased in the reporting:

$$\delta_b = \frac{150}{240} = 0.625;$$

$$\delta = 0.625 + 0.33 + 0.60 = 1.555;$$

$$k_{dyn} = \exp(-1.0 \times 1.555) = 0.211;$$

$$P_{success} = 0.54 \times 0.211 \times 0.80 = 0.091(9.1%);$$

$$P_{risk} = 90.9\%.$$

Although, in the short term, the risk probability has slightly increased (due to the inertia of the reported indicators continuing to reflect accumulated deviations), the *RUL* forecast improved from 5.6 to 7.2 months, thus establishing conditions conducive to future risk reduction assuming the positive trend persists. This illustrates the importance of separate monitoring of the current state and forecast indicators.

VIII. SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

A sensitivity analysis of the final risk probability with respect to changes in key parameters is conducted using the project example.

Table 3. Sensitivity analysis of the risk probability with respect to parameter changes

Scenario	δ	β	k_{dyn}	<i>RW</i> , months	k_{op}	$P_{success}$	P_{risk}	Change in P_{risk} , percentage points
Baseline	1.43	1.0	0.239	3.13	0.80	10.3%	89.7%	—
Reduction of δ by 30%	1.00	1.0	0.368	3.13	0.80	15.9%	84.1%	-5.6
Increase <i>RW</i> to 6 months	1.43	1.0	0.239	6.00	1.00	12.9%	87.1%	-2.6

Transition to growth	1.43	1.5	0.117	3.13	0.80	5.1 %	94.9%	+5.2
Comprehensive improvement	0.80	1.0	0.449	6.00	1.00	24.2%	75.8%	-13.9
Reduction of δ by 50 %	0.72	1.0	0.487	3.13	0.80	21.0%	79.0%	-10.7
Increase RW to 9 months	1.43	1.0	0.239	9.00	1.00	12.9%	87.1%	-2.6

Interpretation of sensitivity analysis results: the greatest effect in reducing risk probability is achieved by decreasing the accumulated deviation δ (scenario 1: -5.6 percentage points with a 30% reduction in δ), indicating the priority of measures aimed at restoring the project to planned budgetary, temporal, and revenue parameters; An increase in RW alone results in a limited effect (scenario 2: -2.6 p.p.), since k_{op} shifts from 0.8 to 1.0, while the fundamental issue of high δ persists; Advancing to a later stage while maintaining high deviations significantly increases the risk (scenario 3: +5.2 p.p.), as the market anticipates greater predictability from a mature project; Comprehensive improvement (scenario 4)—simultaneous reduction of δ to 0.8 and increase of RW to 6 months – yields the greatest decrease in risk probability (-13.9 p.p., down to 75.8%); Further reduction of δ (Scenario 5) continues to improve the metric, albeit with a diminishing return; Increasing RW beyond the critical threshold (Scenario 6) does not yield additional risk reduction, as k_{op} has already reached its maximum value of 1.0.

IX. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed model allows for quantitative evaluation of the innovation project’s risk probability based on three distinct groups of factors. Key findings from the numerical example indicate an initial project risk probability of 89.7%; The largest contribution to the elevated risk was attributed to the accumulated deviation $\delta = 1.43$ (surpassing the critical threshold of 1.0); Bayesian updating of the RUL forecast demonstrated an improvement in the median prediction from 5.6 to 7.2 months following anti-crisis interventions; however, the current risk probability remained high (90.9%) due to the inertia of reporting indicators; Sensitivity analysis identified that reducing accumulated deviations yields the greatest risk mitigation effect (a decrease of 5.6 percentage points with a 30% reduction in δ), while comprehensive improvement of parameters enables lowering the P_{risk} to 75.8%.

Model limitations: expert definition of critical deviation thresholds and prior parameters of the gamma process is required. Calibration may be challenging for new markets and unique technologies. It is recommended to combine the proposed quantitative approach with qualitative expert evaluation by the investment committee.

X. CONCLUSION

A multifactorial model of risk probability assessment for innovation ventures has been developed and verified. The model integrates structural, dynamic, and operational factors into a unified computational algorithm comprising five steps. The algorithm's stepwise structure renders it amenable to automation within analytical platforms. A detailed exposition of the mathematical apparatus of the gamma process with Bayesian parameter updating is provided for forecasting the residual time to breakeven. The numerical example illustrated the model's practical applicability for the early detection of critical states and the quantitative evaluation of managerial decision impacts.

Future research could focus on machine learning of the model's weighting coefficients using historical data from venture capital funds, as well as on integrating the model into investment decision support systems that automatically generate recommendations.

Table 4. Summary Results of the Numerical Example

Indicator	Initial State	After Crisis Management Measures	Change
P_{adj}	54%	54%	0 p.p.
Accumulated Deviation δ	1.43	1.56	+0.13
k_{dyn}	0.239	0.211	-0.028
RW	3.13 months	5.0 months	+1.87 months
Median <i>RUL</i>	5.6 months	7.2 months	+1.6 months
k_{op}	0.80	0.80	0
$P_{success}$	10.3%	9.1%	-1.2 p.p.
P_{risk}	89.7%	90.9%	+1.2 p.p.

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FEATURES OF THE FORMATION OF THE COST OF A GOLD MINING ENTERPRISE

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Abstract. *The article examines the process of cost formation at a gold mining enterprise and develops recommendations for its reduction, which is particularly relevant for enterprises in this sector. Based on the financial statements of one of the gold mining enterprises in the Magadan region, the production costs were analyzed, and the features of their formation were examined, which made it possible to identify several issues: material costs constitute a significant share of the total production costs; increase in the cost of material resources; increase in labor expenses. As a result, measures were developed to reduce production costs: acquiring new equipment for execution of works, which will reduce defects during construction, installation, and assembly operations, increase labor productivity, and save materials; outsource part of the staff; ensure the supply of materials from suppliers in large batches, thereby reducing transportation costs.*

Keywords: *cost, gold mining enterprise, production cost.*

Introduction

Cost and expenditure analysis is a strategically important tool that facilitates economic decision-making. The analysis of cost formation in the products of a gold mining enterprise enables the comparison of the economic efficiency of various options and ultimately the selection of the option that offers the greatest

benefit at the lowest cost. The cost and expense management system of any enterprise is established with the objective of minimizing and controlling them.

The relevance of the research topic lies in the identification of internal reserves that enable the reduction of production costs and their efficient utilization. This, in turn, allows for enhancing the efficiency of the enterprise's operations, as well as achieving higher rates of profit growth and production profitability. The purpose of the study is to identify the features of cost formation at a gold mining enterprise and to develop recommendations for its reduction.

Materials and Methods of Research

As is known, cost reflects the complete aggregate of all expenses incurred by the enterprise for the production and subsequent sale of its products [4, p. 105]. Analysis of costs and cost formation is a tool for decision-making. It can be employed to identify the actions that should be undertaken in the future. This analysis provides a quantitative perspective on the issue and thereby allows for decisions based on factual data rather than on the opinions of others or on intuition. Undoubtedly, it is essential to consider the factors influencing the cost level of a gold mining enterprise, specifically:

- market factors (including prices and tariffs);
- internal production factors (such as the duration of the production cycle, the condition of supply and procurement, the efficiency of sales activities, transportation cost levels, repair expenses, losses due to defects, waste, the quality of labor and of the materials and technical means used, as well as personnel qualifications).

The full cost of production at a gold mining enterprise includes expenses related to labor, means, and objects of labor involved in production; expenses associated with product distribution, namely: packaging, storage, loading, and transportation; costs not directly related to production and sales (including payments for water, land reclamation, etc.).

Various methods of managing the production cost at a gold mining enterprise are distinguished. These methods were originally developed for enterprises across various sectors but share common principles. Let us highlight the following: a systematic approach to cost management; the consistency of methods applied at various levels of cost management; cost management throughout all stages of the product life cycle; an integrated combination of cost optimization with a high quality of the manufactured products (works, services); the continuous implementation of cost reduction methods, among others.

Savings that enable the actual reduction of the production cost of a gold mining enterprise can be calculated based on the following typical list of factors:

- 1) Modernization of production method technologies involves the introduction of modern equipment and production principles. It is important to emphasize the study of the feasibility of applying new, more advantageous raw materials,

improving the qualitative characteristics of the products, which will contribute to meeting consumer demand, as well as other factors that will enhance the technical level of production. Additionally, the savings achieved through the implementation of corrective measures in the previous period should be taken into account. It should be noted that if several such measures are planned to be carried out over multiple years rather than a single year, the savings will be determined for the reporting year only based on the volume of work incorporating new technologies, without considering the scale of implementation prior to the beginning of that year [6, p. 11]. The reduction in production costs can be realized through the automation of production and management, the utilization of more powerful computing equipment, and the modernization of various stages of production, as well as the utilization of waste generated by the same production process and the use of various raw material substitutes;

2) improvement of production and labor organization. Undoubtedly, cost reduction is influenced by optimizing workforce size, adjusting work schedules, and modifying labor payment methods. Continuous improvement in production management allows for reducing production costs. Efficient use of fixed assets, enhancement of material and technical supply, and optimization of transportation expenses all contribute to lowering the cost per unit of output. If simultaneous improvements in both production technology and its organization are planned, it is necessary to calculate savings for each factor individually. In cases where it is not possible to separate the factors, savings can be determined by groups of factors.

There are two main methods that enable the determination of the cost of a gold mining enterprise by elements of expenses and by cost accounting items.

The main factors affecting changes in the cost of products at a gold mining enterprise can be grouped as follows: improvement of the technical level of production (integrated production automation, enhancement of production technology, etc.); improvement of the management system, production organization, and labor; change in the volume and structure of the produced output; introduction and mastery of new production capacities; seasonal and other industry-specific factors; changes in prices of manufactured products and consumed resources (raw materials, energy, etc.).

The gold market is characterized by its use as insurance and reserve in many countries and simultaneously as an industrial raw material and an investment asset. To control production costs, it is essential to understand the production technology. This is because each gold mining source has its own characteristics and fundamentally differs from others.

At present, gold is mainly extracted from ores, not only from gold ores but also from ores whose primary minerals are other non-ferrous metals, specifically copper, zinc, silver, and lead. In this case, gold is considered an associated product.

The research employed the following methods: vertical and horizontal statistical analysis, as well as economic-statistical techniques (comparison, compilation and grouping, and the method of absolute and relative values).

The information base of the study was the accounting (financial) statements of a gold mining enterprise in the Magadan region, as well as the author's research findings on the cost formation of subsoil users. The analysis of cost formation was carried out using the example of a gold mining enterprise (JSC) in the Magadan region. The cost of finished products of the JSC – extracted ore – includes only operational mine preparation, operational exploration, and mining works.

Operational mine-preparatory works include overburden removal related to scaling and stabilization of pit slopes, excavation of cut trenches, temporary ramps, drainage ditches, and similar tasks. Exploration-operational works involve driving exploratory workings and drilling boreholes to delineate the boundaries of ore bodies, determine the directions of mining operations, and specify the quantity and quality of prepared and mine-ready reserves of the mineral resource.

Mining operations are considered to be the activities related to the extraction from the earth's interior and the lifting of ore and waste rock to the surface. These operations incur similar expenses: drilling, charging with explosives, blasting, ground support installation, loading of the blasted rock mass into transport vehicles, transportation, and transshipment. By-product ore is included in the report on fulfillment of the plan but is not included in the cost calculation of ore extraction nor in the composition of the finished products of the initial processing stage.

The ore processing procedure carried out by the JSC consists of separating gold from the barren rock to obtain an enriched product. The main operations of the technological process include crushing, screening, grinding, flotation, gravity concentration, dewatering, as well as electrolytic gold recovery, cleaning, and roasting of concentrates. Next, the concentrate is transported to the refining plant.

Products that have not completed all the stages prescribed by the technological process are classified as work in progress and are valued according to the product type. The planned cost per ton of ore, which is included in work in progress, is determined in the annual plan of the JSC and constitutes a constant value for the reporting year, formed from the following cost items: auxiliary materials for technological purposes; energy for technological purposes; wages of production workers; social insurance contributions; depreciation charges and contributions to the repair fund for drilling equipment.

The basis for determining the volumes of completed work and finished product output are documents: for mining operations – the surveyor's measurement report; Regarding gold – this is a cash handling record of the metal accepted by the gold receiving cashier, as well as an entry in the cash book of the gold receiving cashier.

Planned cost estimates of the JSC are prepared annually with distribution by quarters (if necessary – by months). Their basis consists of technically justified norms of consumption of material and labor resources, monetary funds, and calculations of cost changes according to technical and economic factors.

Actual calculations are performed monthly, consolidating data from the entire JSC. This is due to the fact that mining enterprises have a complex structure which, besides the mines and the main production enterprise of the JSC, includes a number of auxiliary units, such as repair workshops, boiler houses, etc. and support services: canteen, hotel, and residential facilities.

A distinctive feature of fixed asset depreciation at mining enterprises is that their service life depends not on the degree of physical and moral wear, but on the period of deposit exploitation. In the cost calculation of mining preparation works and mineral extraction, depreciation of fixed assets is determined by the traditional method (according to depreciation rates) if the equipment service life, considering the deposit's exploitation period, is less than 4 years or exceeds 25 years [1, p. 317].

The volume of extracted mineral is determined according to the JSC's commodity transport waybills, i.e. by the weight of the shipped useful mineral, adjusted for losses during storage at warehouses and for the weight of useful mineral during mining capital works.

In the cost formation structure of gold mining at a JSC, a significant portion is accounted for by costs of fuel and energy resources. Due to the continual decrease in the grade of precious metal in the metal-containing ore, energy costs in the production cost of pure metal will steadily increase, leading to a rise in the cost of gold production. To optimize these costs, it is necessary to introduce restrictions on the use of fuel and energy resources, including for diesel fuel and to switch to more advantageous suppliers for the provision of such types of resources.

An analysis of expenses was conducted based on data from the financial performance report for the analyzed period (see Table 1).

The amount of expenses related to ordinary activities increases annually, with an expense growth rate of 30.22% in 2022. Throughout the entire analyzed period, the product's total cost structure is dominated entirely by its cost price – 100%.

The following factors influence changes in expenses: the volume of work performed; prices and tariffs applied to expenses; structure and specific expenses for performing individual types of extraction. The reasons for changes in individual expenses should be established. The calculation of the impact of the efficiency of production resource utilization on the change in the amount of production expenses is presented in Table 2.

Table 1. Trends in expenses for the ordinary activities of the JSC in 2020–2022, thousand RUB

Indicators	2020	2021	2022	Absolute deviation (+/-)		Growth rate, %	
				2021 from 2020	2022 from 2021	2021 from 2020	2022 from 2021
Cost of sales	21 440 878	21 675 172	20 449 244	234 294	-1 225 928	101.09	94.34
Administrative expenses	1 156 482	1 527 122	1 310 673	370 640	-216 449	132.05	85.83
Other expenses	1 485 792	1 233 125	1 005 9 502	-252 667	8 826 377	82.99	815.77
Total expenses:	24 083 152	24 435 419	31 819 419	352 267	7 384 000	101.46	130.22

Table 2. Impact of the efficiency of production resource utilization JSC on expense changes

Factor	Change in cost of production, thousand rubles	
	Calculation	Result, +/-
1. Increase in material intensity	+3.41 x 726.55	+2,477.54
2. Increase in labor intensity	+9.95 x 726.55	+7,229.17
3. Increase in the depreciation intensity of work	+0.99 x 726.55	+719, 28
4. Reduction of unit costs	-10.35 x 726.55	-7,519.79
Total:	+4.00 x 726.55	+2,906.20

Thus, the reduction in unit costs caused a decrease in production expenses by 7,519.792 thousand rubles, while the increase in material intensity, labor intensity, and depreciation intensity led to an increase in production expenses by 10,425.99 thousand rubles (2,477.54 thousand rubles + 7,229.17 thousand rubles + 719.28 thousand rubles).

The production process is an aggregate of business operations associated with the execution of works and the provision of services during the creation of products, and the actual cost is determined, which includes the costs associated with their production [3, p. 160]. Subsequently, the technical and economic indicators of gold production were calculated (see Table 3).

As indicated by the figures in Table 3, the departmental cost of gold produced in 2022 totaled 14,799,235 thousand rubles, while the production cost was 18,066,288 thousand rubles. Subsequently, we analyzed the cost structure according to the main indicators of gold mining and production (see Table 4).

Table 3. Calculation of the cost indicators of gold production at the JSC for 2020–2022, thousand rubles

Indicators	2020	2021	2022	Absolute deviation (+/-)		Rate of growth, %	
				2021 from 2020	2022 from 2021	2021 from 2020	2022 from 2021
Mining Costs	8 656 400	8 725 516	8 811 105	691 16	85 589	100.80	100.98
Costs of Enrichment and Smelting	5 902 400	5 941 338	5 988 130	38 938	46 792	100.66	100.79
Departmental Cost of Gold	14 558 800	14 666 855	14 799 235	108 055	132 380	100.74	100.90
Production Cost of Gold	17 732 762	17 891 931	18 066 288	1 59 169	174 357	100.90	100.97

Table 4. Cost Structure of Gold Production at the JSC for 2020–2022, Thousand Rubles

Cost Category	2020		2021		2022	
	Thousand Rubles	Share, %	Thousand Rubles	Share, %	Thousand Rubles	Share, %
Total Costs, Including:	14 558 800	100.00	14 666 854	100.00	14 799 235	100.00
Costs of Ore Extraction	8 656 400	59.46	8 725 516	59.49	8 811 105	59.54
Costs of Enrichment and Smelting	5 902 400	40.54	5 941 338	40.51	5 988 130	40.46

Data from Table 4 indicate that a significant portion of the JSC's expenses is allocated to ore extraction, amounting to 59.54% of the total costs. Costs associated with enrichment and smelting accounted for 40.46% of the total expenses. The analysis of technical and economic indicators (TEI) at the enterprise indicates profitability as well as effective operation and development of the gold mining JSC. A slight reduction in costs will allow for significant savings. Effective management of such expenses will contribute to reducing the cost of gold extraction and processing, thereby increasing non-operating income. Optimization of such values will undoubtedly have a positive impact on profitability growth [2, p. 135].

It is also necessary to pursue a policy aimed at reducing the cost of extraction and processing through heap leaching. The costs of extracting 1 ton of gold by traditional methods average 1,501.7 million rubles. The implementation of heap leaching at the ore dump site with a content of up to 0.96 g/t will enable a reduction in extraction and processing costs. Successful implementation of heap leaching technology requires capital investments, shortened production preparation timelines, and a sufficiently low cost of gold recovery.

Approaches to reducing production and sales costs of products (works, services) are examined from the standpoint of methods to achieve an optimal combination of cost reduction and quality improvement, achievable primarily through technical, organizational, and economic means [5, p. 58].

Conclusion

The results obtained allowed for determining the impact of individual factors on cost formation, as well as identifying the primary directions for reducing production expenses. Our analysis of the cost of production (works, services) revealed problems at the JSC: a considerable share of material expenses in the cost of works; an increase in the cost of material resources.

To resolve the above issues, the JSC should: 1) purchase newer equipment for production activities, which will reduce defects during construction, installation, and assembly works, increase labor productivity, and achieve material savings; 2) outsource part of the workforce; 3) ensure material deliveries from suppliers in larger batches, thereby reducing transportation costs.

Based on an analysis of the production cost (works, services) at the JSC, we proposed measures to reduce it: 1) reduce material expenses by implementing new equipment for the execution of works, which will decrease defects during construction, installation, and finishing operations, increase labor productivity, and yield material savings; 2) reduce labor costs through outsourcing, thereby achieving an economic benefit of 997.92 thousand rubles. The JSC uses a single allocation base for distributing indirect costs – the wages of the primary production workers, which is understandable given the labor-intensive nature of the JSC's production. Therefore, it is necessary to differentiate these costs into homogeneous groups and identify indicators that have the greatest influence on their magnitude.

The use of this allocation method contributes to the elimination of distortions in the cost of products (works, services), which are typical of traditional accounting based on the sequential distribution of costs using volume-based indicators. Therefore, the developed method provides more complete, reliable, and timely information for managing expenses.

Thus, the implementation of the proposed measures to reduce the cost of products (works, services) will enable the JSC to achieve an economic benefit, increasing gross profit by 1 118 618 thousand. rubles, the sales profitability will increase by 0.2%.

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TRAINING PERSONNEL FOR THE TOURISM INDUSTRY IN AUSTRIA: STRUCTURE, MECHANISMS AND KEY CHARACTERISTICS¹

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the system of professional training for the tourism industry in Austria. The multi-level structure of specialized education, including secondary vocational schools, colleges, universities of applied sciences and universities, is examined. Key mechanisms for ensuring quality of training are identified: continuity of educational levels, dual education, system of regulation and control, as well as the active role of social partnership. Special attention is paid to forms of additional professional education and career guidance work. The Austrian model is characterized by a close connection between theory and practice, flexibility of educational trajectories, and integration into European quality standards.*

Keywords: *personnel training system, Austria, tourism industry, vocational education, dual education, continuity of educational levels, social partnership.*

Introduction

Austria's tourism industry is one of the key sectors of the national economy, which determines high requirements for the quality of professional personnel training. The effectiveness of the Austrian model of training specialists for tourism and hospitality is recognized internationally and is of considerable interest for improving national education systems. The purpose of this article is to analyze the structure, mechanisms, and key characteristics of the professional training system for the tourism industry in Austria.

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Structure and components of the vocational education system in tourism

Analysis of the structure of vocational education in tourism in Austria reveals a complex diversity of educational offerings. The system of specialized tourism education includes the following components: regulatory constraints (requirements for educational activities, educational programs); multi-level educational institutions; subjects of educational activities (trainers and trainees); governing and controlling bodies in vocational education; public and other associations of subjects of educational activities and institutions engaged in educational activities in tourism [1].

The conceptual foundations of vocational education in Austria are: the connection between theory and practice; actual continuity of different educational levels; ensuring an end-to-end system of regulation and quality control of education at all levels. The connection with practice is based on social partnership: the Austrian Chamber of Commerce, industry associations of employers, relevant ministries and institutions engaged in vocational education closely cooperate in the development and implementation of educational policy [2].

Mechanisms for implementing continuity of educational levels

As defined by the Austrian Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Culture, in Austrian vocational education there are no educational levels that cannot be upgraded, regardless of whether the education is classical or dual. The mechanisms for implementing continuity of educational levels include differentiation of educational programs, unification of requirements for educational activities, ensuring a full continuity line, ensuring coherence through the introduction of a modular training structure with a mandatory basic module, ensuring the “embeddedness” of educational levels, as well as the “credit” of certified competencies at subsequent levels of study [3].

System of regulation and quality control

Ensuring an end-to-end system of regulation and quality control of education is aimed at forming measurable universal, methodological, and professional competencies at each level and each educational stage. The key components of the system are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 – Components of the system of regulation and quality control of education in the tourism sector of Austria

System component	Content
Updating the content of education	Updating the content of education is initiated by the Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Culture and the Chamber of Commerce
Ensuring the quality of formal schooling	Ensured by introducing a quality management system (since 2005), taking into account the Common Quality Assurance Framework (CQAF) for vocational education

System component	Content
Requirements for the implementation of the educational process	Requirements are formulated in national educational standards. Quality control of formed competencies is carried out through the introduction of national tests. Educational standards for higher professional education are developed in close cooperation with neighboring states. For blue-collar occupations, a competency model is developed, focused on mastering action competencies (when performing functional duties)

Source: [1]

Educational institutions in the tourism sector

Institutions engaged in educational activities in the tourism sector in Austria are divided into several levels (Table 2).

Table 2 – Educational institutions in the tourism sector of Austria

Type of educational institution	Duration of study	Content of education	Education document
Secondary (incomplete) vocational schools in tourism (BMS)	3 years	Completed vocational education. Along with classroom training, training is conducted in laboratories, compulsory internships are provided	Certificate of vocational education
Additional course after completing secondary vocational school	2–3 years	Training for the purpose of gaining access to further education (up to the school-leaving certificate)	School-leaving certificate based on the results of the qualification exam
«Full» vocational schools	5 years	Vocational training + training for the purpose of gaining access to further education (up to the school-leaving certificate)	Certificate of vocational education + school-leaving certificate
College (requires school-leaving certificate, vocational certificate or passing a qualification exam)	2 years (full-time), 3 years (evening)	Vocational training	Diploma

Type of educational institution	Duration of study	Content of education	Education document
Secondary vocational hotel schools (Hfs)	3 years	Training in professions in the field of hotel and restaurant service. Mandatory long-term internships (at least 24 weeks)	Certificate of vocational education
Universities of applied sciences, universities (first level of higher education)	6–8 semesters of bachelor's degree	Practical experience or vocational education required for admission. Emphasis on management	Diploma
Universities of applied sciences, universities (second level of higher education)	2–4 semesters of master's degree	Narrow specialization	Diploma
Universities (doctoral studies)	4–6 semesters	–	Doctoral degree

Source: [1]

Dual education

A special place in the education system in tourism in Austria is occupied by dual education, carried out simultaneously at a training enterprise and in an educational institution. Dual education in Austria assumes 80% of study time at the training enterprise and 20% – in the educational institution. Students enrolled in the dual education system perform specific functional duties and receive a scholarship from the enterprise. The dual education system does not provide for training for positions of high qualification levels or those requiring a high degree of responsibility [3, 4].

Table 3 presents the main areas of dual education in the tourism sector of Austria.

Table 3 – Areas of dual education in the tourism sector of Austria

Profession	Duration of study
Cook	3 years
Restaurant manager	3 years
Gastronomy specialist	4 years
Assistant in hotel business	3 years
Specialist in system gastronomy (in fast food chains)	3 years
Assistant in travel agency	3 years
Fitness instructor	3 years

Profession	Duration of study
Office manager	3 years
Event technologist, technical support of events	3 years
Sports administrator	3 years
Transport administrator	3 years

Source: [1]

Additional professional education

The concept of “lifelong learning” is reflected in various forms of additional professional education, which is implemented both at tourism enterprises and in educational institutions. According to the nature of the education received, the following main groups can be distinguished: horizontal additional education (to acquire additional competencies without raising the qualification level) and vertical additional education (to raise the qualification level or educational stage) [5].

Career guidance work

Social partnership for the interaction of professional associations and subjects of educational activities is carried out in the form of career guidance activities, among which the following groups are distinguished: guidance at the secondary level of education; guidance in vocational schools; guidance in higher schools; guidance at the Austrian Employment Service; guidance in the social partnership system; guidance through the provision of apprentice places; guidance in the system of additional professional education [6,7].

Conclusion

The analysis of the structure and content of the education model in the tourism sector of Austria reveals the most important characteristics of specialized tourism education in this country: its “end-to-end” systemic nature, allowing the principle of continuity of educational levels to be implemented; practice-orientation of such forms of educational activity as dual education or training at universities of applied sciences or in incomplete vocational schools (enabling early employment of graduates); a wide range of educational trajectories based on a block-modular format for building courses; an integrated approach to solving the problems of specialized tourism education based on expanding the possibilities of horizontal and vertical development of competencies, targeted training of various groups of trainers, and career guidance activities at all educational levels [7].

The Austrian model of personnel training for the tourism industry demonstrates high efficiency due to the integration of formal and non-formal education, active participation of employers in the development and implementation of educational programs, as well as flexibility that allows students to build individual educational trajectories. The presented characteristics can be used in a comparative analysis of

Western European models to determine invariant parameters of effective systems of specialized education.

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